

Thesis Title:

**An Investigation of the Drivers and Barriers Towards the
Use of Internet Banking in the UK**

By:

Ajmal Mohammad Yosaf
BA (Hons), MBA (Finance)

Supervised by:

Dr. Rajendra Kumar

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for the degree of Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to a very special person in my life. To my beloved mother and best friend, Peeshaka Yousaf

Declaration

I hereby declare that the findings and results in this thesis are the outcome of my genuine effort and hard work, except where otherwise acknowledged. I further declare that all the contents of this research are original and has not been submitted previously for any award degree.

Ajmal Mohammad Yosaf

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Abstract

The rapid advancements in information communication technologies has significantly changed the way how customers conduct their day to day banking activities. The growth and availability of internet technology has made it possible for customers to carry out of their banking transactions from remote location without having to visit a bank branch. The usage of internet banking has increased tremendously over the past decade and this is expected to grow further in the coming years. Studies suggest that it is critically important for banks to understand the key factors and determinants that influence customer's intention in accepting and using internet banking services.

The primary aim of this research is to investigate both the drivers and barriers towards the adoption and usage of internet banking in the UK. The study seeks to examine the key factors that influence customers' decision to use internet banking. It uses Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as the basis for developing a conceptual model of internet banking acceptance for this study. However, the original TAM is augmented with additional components, including the role of trust and perceived risk and demographic characteristics in order to better explain and predict UK's customers' attitude towards using internet banking services. In sum, the present study integrates the TAM, environmental uncertainty factors (trust and perceived risk, and user's demographic characteristics (gender, age and level of education) into a coherent model of internet banking acceptance.

This study seeks to adopt a mixed method approach consisting of both the questionnaire survey and semi-structured interviews. The primary data for the present study was collected mainly through questionnaire distributed to internet banking users across different bank branches in London. The researcher also conducted a maximum of 5 semi-structured interviews with bank managers in order to have a better understanding of the phenomenon being investigated. The secondary data was obtained from authentic sources such as Emerald, Ebscohost, Science Direct and other reliable web sources. The nature of the study is mostly quantitative in nature and based on positivist philosophy and Interpretivist approach. Overall, the research has been conducted in a highly respectful and ethical manner. The survey data was analysed using a software called Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Various descriptive and statistical tests were conducted to test the formulated hypotheses (see chapter 5).

The empirical findings show that (1) both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use has significant positive effect on intention; (2) trust positively influence customer's intention to use internet banking, whereas perceived risk was found to negatively influence customer's decision; (3) trust also reduces customer's perception of risk regarding internet banking use; (4) customer's perception of privacy and security directly affects their level of trust; (5) customer's age influence their choice to use internet banking, however, gender and level of education was found to have no

significant impact. In summary, out of the 14 hypotheses proposed for this study, 11 were supported. In general, the conceptual model developed for this study was found to be strong in explaining customer's acceptance of internet banking in the UK. The practical and theoretical contributions of this research are addressed in the last chapter. In summary, the findings from this thesis increases our understanding of the underlying factors that influence the acceptance of internet banking. Awareness of these factors are critical for banks and decision makers to encourage and increase the adoption of online banking services in the UK.

Keywords:

Internet Banking, Online Banking, UK, Perceived Usefulness (PU), Perceived Ease of Use (PEU), Behavioural Intention, Perceived Trust, Perceived Risk, Perceived Privacy, Perceived Security, Technology Acceptance Model, Internet Banking Acceptance, Internet Banking Adoption. Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC).

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CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.0 Background to the study

The fast development of internet technology has significant and evitable impacts on the global financial industries with far reaching impacts. More specifically, the growth of internet technology is having tremendous impacts on how retail banks operate their businesses and customers manage their everyday banking activities. One part of these technologies which is rapidly growing is the use of Internet banking. Internet banking has become a contemporary business phenomenon across the globe and consumers' adoption of online banking has tremendously increased over the past two decades. Consumers are shifting from traditional branch banking to online banking at a very rapid pace because of the various benefits and opportunities associated with it. As Per British Bankers' Association report (2016) the number of online banking users in the UK has increased to almost 29.7 million from 21.5 million in 2015 and 15.4 million in 2014.

The pressure of this rapidly changing technological environment has made it necessary for both public and commercial banks to constantly re-examine their current service delivery in order to keep up with the individual customers technological preferences (Robertson, 2009). A recent survey based on the UK major high street banks cited by CMA (2015) revealed that banks that fail to provide internet banking services will lose almost 50% over the coming five years. Therefore, banks around the world have been deploying effective electronic banking services as a strategic resource to achieve competitive advantage. There are several motives as to why banks are encouraging consumers towards the use of e-banking; they are to lower their operating costs, increase efficiency, improve their banking services, boost profitability and most importantly enhance customer experience and satisfaction. Among them, Mohana et al. (2014) states that reduction of the operational costs by downsizing the number of network branches and service staff is the main motivational factor for the adoption of internet banking by retail banks. Internet banking is claimed to be the cheapest distribution channel for commercial banks operations (Khalfan et al, 2006). DeYoung (2005) claims that for commercial banks the average transaction through internet costs as little as 0.01 US\$ as compared to 0.027 US\$ for ATM, 0.057 US\$ for telephone

banking and 3.69 US\$ for a branch-based banking. Apart from financial motives, banks also encourage the use of electronic banking to provide a more convenient and efficient service to enable its consumers to manage their daily banking needs electronically 24 hours a day from anywhere without having to visit a bank branch.

Although there is significant growth and popularity in the usage of internet banking in almost every country, many people still feel resistant to accept and use this channel. As stated by Yousafzai and Soriano (2011) most consumers in the USA either do not adopt this service at all or do not continue to use it after they adopt it. Similarly, Patsiotis, Hughes and Webber (2012) claims that large number of customers in the UK access banks' website but only a minority number of them conduct online transactions. Consumers in some counties of the England have classified online banking as less important compared to other banking channels such as telephone banking and ATM. Several factors have been identified behind the non-adoption of online banking such as, perceived risk, lack of trust, inaccessibility, lack of knowledge about the service and IT fatigue (Agwu, 2013).

Banks and other financial organisations must realise that the success of internet banking is determined by consumers' acceptance of it. Gkoutzinis (2010) claims that banks will not be able to reap the benefits associated with online banking unless the consumers fully accept and utilise its capabilities. Therefore, to be successful, banks must place greater emphasis on understanding customers' requirements and their technological preferences. As stated by CIO (2017) retail banks must pay regular attention to consumers' requirements in order to understand the key factors that influence their decision towards adopting this service. Moreover, banks must have the required technological infrastructure in place in order to be able to demonstrate the potential benefits of internet banking and persuade customers to accept and use this new channel. Eriksson, Kerem and Nilsson (2004) claims that the introduction of any new technology is wastage of resources unless accepted by consumers. For this reason, it is essential for retail banks to find the best ways to manage and promote internet banking in order to have the best chances of customer acceptance.

In the UK, Internet banking service were first introduced in 1983 with the name of 'Homelink' by the Royal Bank of Scotland and Nottingham Banking Society (Tait and Davis, 1989). However, this service did not gain widespread acceptance and was largely discontinued (McVandon and Vinson (1987). The number of online banking customers was low until the late 90s; however, it started to increase with advancements in

computer and internet technologies. By the mid of 2000s the market for internet banking grew sharply and changed the competitive landscape of the UK banking industry. Growth in the internet, consumers' familiarity with the technology, demographic trends and low costs of personal computers gave significant rise to the adoption and use of internet banking in the United Kingdom (Yousafzai, 2005). It is of no surprise that the number of online banking customers alone in the UK reached to 18.5 million by 2005 (International Data Corporation, 2005). These numbers have been significantly increasing over the past decade, and today the number of online banking customers in the UK have reached its peak with 4.3 million logins a day (BBA report, 2016). In the past, banks were mainly competing against one another on interest rate, loans and savings accounts; however, the new battleground is to offer the best technology to its customers (Chung and Paynter, 2012). All major banks in the UK are constantly improving and expanding the provision of internet banking services to its customers. In this 'mobile-first' decade banks that provide supportive and service-driven banking services will succeed.

Although number of e-banking customers are growing rapidly, many people in the UK still do not use this service due to privacy, security and trust concerns. Therefore, studying and understanding the factors that influence the adoption of internet banking service is crucial for banks. The present study aims to address this important phenomenon. This research will investigate the key factors that influence the adoption and usage of internet banking and the findings from this research will help banks to come up with sound strategies that will maximise the adoption of this channel.

1.2 Rationale for the research

Previous studies have suggested that understanding customer acceptance is the key for the success of internet banking. These studies have also called for future research that should provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that facilitate or inhibit this customer-based electronic revolution. As stated above, it has become a crucial importance for retail banks to understand the key factors that affect consumer intention towards the use of internet banking. Understanding of key user's characteristics will help banks to better predict the users and non-users of this new technology. There are number of technology acceptance models that can prove very useful in assisting banks to understand the critical factors that affects users' intention to accept or reject this new banking channel.

Review of the literature indicates that previous studies have mainly focused on the drivers of internet banking. However, there is little or no study that shed light on the barriers or inhibitors of this service. Previous studies have not explored the factors that affect the non-users of internet banking or why people discontinue this service after adopting. Therefore, a comprehensive study is needed that should focus on both the drivers and as well as barriers towards the acceptance of internet banking in the UK. An understanding of how to increase the user experience of existing customers and bring back the dormant customers to internet banking is important. Banks must understand the key factors that not only affect the users but also the non-users of internet banking in order increase the adoption rate of this service in the UK.

The main rationale for choosing this topic is because the adoption of online banking has tremendously increased in developed nations over the past decade, and the researcher is really interested to investigate the key factors that affect the usage and non-usage of this service in three major cities of the United Kingdom: London, Birmingham and Manchester. As stated by Wu (2012), literature have paid little attention to consumer resistance to online banking as compared to the attention paid to the adopters of this service. Most internet banking studies have focused on the factors that positively affect the adoption of this service, such as PU and PEU. It is therefore necessary to see both sides of the coin by investigating both the adopters and non-adopters of this service. The objective of this study is to identify both the key factors that affect both the adoption and non-adoption of online banking.

1.3 Review of Previous Internet Banking Research

The focus of international internet banking studies has shifted from technological developments to customer behaviour. Today majority of researches focus on customer belief and perceptions towards the use of internet banking. Substantial body of literature suggests that there is direct link between customer's perception, behavioural intention and actual use. Table 1.1 below lists number of international studies that have investigated customer's adoption of internet banking. Majority of these studies have focused on the positive aspects of internet banking with little focus on the issues of barriers to this service. Moreover, there are very little studies that focuses on both the drivers and as well as the inhibiting factors of internet banking adoption.

Table 1.1: Review of Previous Internet Banking Research

Study <i>Topic for Analysis</i>	Findings
Moles (2000) <i>Internet Banking Marketing in Denmark</i>	For banks to retain customer loyalty, they must adapt and customise their offerings in order to meet the individual customer's needs.
Aladwani (2001) <i>Drivers and Challenges of Internet Banking in Kuwait</i>	For banks, the main drivers of internet banking are to provide faster, reliable and easier service, enhance competitive position, improve bank's image, reduce operational costs, reduce HRM costs and create new markets.
Jun and Sai (2001) <i>Service Quality in Internet Banking</i>	Three main dimensions of service quality were identified: customer service quality, online service quality and the quality of services provided by the bank.
Ekin and Polatoglu (2001) <i>Internet Banking Acceptance in Turkey</i>	The main factors that positively influence the adoption of internet banking are: relative advantage, trialability, perceived risk, complexity and observability. The study also found that consumers who is using online banking from long time find it to be very useful and reliable.
Guarau (2002) <i>Electronic Banking in Transition Economies (Romania)</i>	In transition economies, the implementation of internet banking is limited due to the factors, such as, incomplete legislation, low internet penetration, risky financial systems, opportunistic behaviour of banks and lack of knowledge about the internet.
Liao and Cheung (2002) <i>Customer attitude towards electronic banking in Singapore</i>	Key attitudes that positively influence attitude towards online banking are accuracy, security, user friendliness, transaction speed, user involvement and convenience.

Cunningham and Gerrard (2002) <i>Diffusion of internet banking in Singapore</i>	Internet banking adoption is influenced by these eight factors: social desirability, convenience, compatibility, complexity, confidentiality, accessibility and economic benefits.
Wang et al (2003) <i>Adoption of Internet banking in Taiwan</i>	Using TAM, the study found that PU, PEU and perceived credibility were positively correlated with the internet banking adoption.
Akenci et al (2004) <i>Adoption of internet banking among Turkish Sophisticated Customers</i>	Non-users of internet banking were not aware of the significant benefit of this service, preferred to use branch service despite having access to internet and were not confident in using internet banking services.
Eriksson et al (2005) <i>Internet banking acceptance in Estonia</i>	Based on TAM Model, the study found that trust positively influence both PU and PEU which ultimately affects customers intention to use internet banking.
Lasser et al (2005) <i>Internet banking adoption in USA</i>	The study found that domain specific consumer innovation and self-efficacy has positive impact on the adoption of online banking.
Singhal and Padhmanabhan (2008) <i>Study on Consumer Adoption towards internet banking: Major contributing factors</i>	This study found that convenience, reliability, real-time access, ease of use and saving transaction costs are the main factors that positively contribute to the adoption and usage of internet banking among the customers.
AlMohaimmeed (2010) <i>Consumer Behaviour Towards Internet Banking in Saudi Arabia.</i>	There is a strong and positive relationship between online banking and customer loyalty and satisfaction.
Wu (2012) <i>Investigation the case of Chinese internet banking customers</i>	Perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are the two key determinants that influence the adoption of internet banking among customers.
Mohamed (2013) <i>Improving the Libyan customer trust and acceptance of online banking</i>	Relative advantage, ease of use, trust, security issues, privacy issues and technical support directly impact internet banking adoption. Moreover, factors such as, unreliable national telecommunication infrastructure, illiteracy, lack of technological knowledge among bank's

	staff and corruption were negatively influencing the diffusion of online banking.
Bashir and Madhavaiah (2015) <i>Consumer attitude and behavioural intention towards internet banking adoption in India</i>	Intrinsic motivation affects user's trust in the acceptance of internet banking.
Mansour (2016) <i>An analysis of business' acceptance of internet banking: an integration of e-trust to the TAM</i>	Integrity and credibility positively influence perceived usefulness and also has a direct effect on customers' attitude.

Source: Many as indicated above

Previous research on internet banking have identified number of different factors that affect the adoption of this service. For instance, for Karjaluoto et al (2002) the adoption of internet banking is influenced by past experience and their attitude towards computer technologies. According to Gerrard and Cunningham (2003) convenience, compatibility accessibility, complexity and other economic benefits affects consumer behaviour to accept and use online banking services. In another research Liao and Cheung (2002) found that security, accuracy, user involvement, user friendliness, transaction speed and convenience are the key factors influencing internet banking adoption. Majority of internet banking studies suggest that customer concerns over security, privacy and reliability play a major role in user's intention to adoption internet banking. Liao and Cheung (2002) claims that the issue of security and privacy led customers to take cautious approach to use online banking. Therefore, internet service providers need to demonstrate solutions that will compensate customers for the losses incurred due to internet fraud or transactional failure.

Studies on internet banking also suggest that although customer prefer to use mix delivery channels, the branch network dominance will be less obvious in the future as the customers are shifting towards internet banking and mobile banking at a very rapid pace. However, Gerrard, Cunningham and Devlin (2006) argue that banks must integrate internet banking into other delivery channels so that customers are able to interact face-to-face with the staff who can deal with the customer's problems and

issues effectively. Internet banking should not replace the traditional branch banking system and the customer-bank relationship should not be ignored while implementing online banking strategies.

1.4 Research aim and objectives

The fundamental aim of the present study is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the key factors that influence consumers' intentions to adopt and use internet banking services in the UK. The following research objectives have been set to achieve this aim of the study:

1. Critically review the literature on internet banking and relevant theories/models to develop a conceptual framework for this research.
2. Identify the factors influencing UK consumers' intention towards the adoption and usage of internet banking.
3. Examine the role of customers' trust in the acceptance of internet banking.
4. Investigate whether differences between customers' demographic characteristics have any effects on their perception to adopt internet banking.
5. Finally, contribute to the body of knowledge in the area of technology acceptance, and make recommendations to banks about how to improve customer acceptance of internet banking.

1.5 Research Questions

To achieve the above research objectives, this study aims to answer the following research question:

1. How consumers' intention to use internet banking are formed and what factors directly influence their decision to use and adopt this service?
2. What is the role of customer's trust in the acceptance of internet banking? How consumer trust is developed?
3. Are there adoption differences between segments of customers based on their demographic characteristics?
4. What are the main factors impeding consumer decision to adopt and use internet banking?
5. What strategies should UK banks adopt to facilitate and maximise the adoption of internet banking

1.6 Theoretical and Practical Contribution of the Present Research

The present study aims to provide both the theoretical and practical contribution in the following ways:

1. This study will contribute to the existing literature of technology acceptance by adding additional variables to the original TAM model that influence the acceptance of online banking among customers in the UK.
2. Develop a conceptual framework of internet banking acceptance by integrating the trust model and technology index with the TAM and apply them in the context of online banking.
3. The present study also contributes to the literature of trust by examining the role of trust in the context of internet banking and also the key factors that affect internet trust. The present study also proposes that trust is a multi-dimensional construct and the meaning of trust is better understood by viewing each dimension separately.
4. The current research also makes an important contribution to technology acceptance literature by investigating the key role of demographic characteristics and technology readiness in internet banking adoption.
5. Apart from theoretical contribution, the present study will prove useful for banks to understand the key factors affecting customer acceptance of internet banking and respond to the individual needs of these consumers. The findings of this study will help bank's strategists and managers to come up with effective strategies for promoting this service to identified segments.
6. Further, findings from this study can be useful for banks to identify the factors that inhibit the adoption of this service. This understanding will help banks to plan and implement measure in order to overcome these inhibiting factors and increase the adoption of internet banking among UK customers. Additionally, the current study analyses the quality perceptions of customer about internet banking which will help banks to devise effective strategies to improve quality of service that will lead to customer satisfaction.

1.7 Context of the Study: United Kingdom

United Kingdom has been chosen as the context for the primary data collection for this study. United Kingdom is a state made of historic countries of England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland with a population of almost 62.5 million (BBC, 2017). Banking system in the UK is considered to have started in England in the 17th century. Currently, only few large banks, including the Lloyds Group, the Royal Bank of Scotland (RBS), Barclays, HSBC, NatWest are dominating the UK banking sector (Economics Online, 2017). These banks are the main credit source in the UK financial market and play a major role in contributing to the state's economy. These banks manage over 75% of the UK current accounts and 85% of the business accounts. According to Deloitte (2015) the UK is a major innovator in the banking industry across the globe that have invented various current account features. It is evident from the banking reports that the UK banking sector is growing at a very rapid pace over the past 40 years. Its total assets have increased from 100% to 450% of the GDP and this is expected to grow further in the future. According to KPMG, (2016) the UK banking sector is bigger than that of other developed countries such as Japan, USA, Germany and France in terms of number of assets.

United Kingdom has always been at the forefront of adopting new technologies. The IT sector has grown tremendously over the past decade and the internet penetration in the country has recently reached to 89% and is ranked as 2nd in Europe and 10th in the whole world in terms of number of internet users. (Statista, 2017). This is expected to grow rapidly in the future due to the country's underlying economic and technological strength. This rapid technological growth has fuelled internet banking and particularly mobile banking adoption and usage in the country. Online banking services in the UK were officially available to customers in 1989 by RBS and Nottingham Banking Society. Over the past decade, this service has grown exponentially and has revolutionised the way banks provide their services and customers conduct their daily banking activities. According to Cebr (2016) the UK internet banking usage is predicted to reach 66% by 2020 as compared to 53% in 2014. This means that an increase of almost 7.5 million internet banking users which will provide significant opportunities for retail banks. The number of internet banking users in the UK is projected to reach 35.1 million by 2020 as compared to 27.7 million in 2014. According to Statista (2017) more than half of Brits now use internet banking, compared to under a third (30%) in

2007. The chart below the percentage of UK based internet banking users have increased notably in the past decade.

Figure 1.1: Proportion of UK Adults using internet banking

Source: Cebr Analysis (2015)

According to the British Banking Association (2016) around 70% of the population are the younger age groups that prefer to bank over the internet. Looking at this chart, it is projected that this upward trend in the number of people using internet banking is likely to increase. It is expected that by 2020, around 9.4 billion could be transferred per week using online banking. The chart below shows the future trend in the adoption and usage of internet banking in the UK.

Figure 1.2: Forecast of the proportion of UK adults using internet banking

Source: Cebr Analysis (2015)

Cebr (2016) claims that the UK's state of the art IT infrastructure together with the widespread ownership of the smartphones with internet connection has boosted the

popularity of both internet banking and mobile banking. In 2010, just one in ten adults were accessing their account on mobile which rose to 20% in 2012 and 35% in 2014. Around 40,000 mobile banking apps were downloaded a day in 2016, a 25% rise from the previous year. Similarly, BBA (2016) claims 9.6 million internet banking logins a day and 11.2 million logins of mobile banking. The European Financial Management Association suggests that today almost 60% of all banking transactions are taking online and this is expected to rise sharply in the future. This will provide huge opportunity for banking providers to capture these new comers to the internet banking market. BBA (2016) suggest that this repaid growth in mobile and internet banking more banks and building societies to more of their services online. The figure 1.3 below shows the projected rise in internet and mobile banking and the decline in telephone banking and branch transactions by 2020.

Figure 1.3: Move in Banking Transactions

Source: BBA (2016)

However, banks must face the fact that these internet banking developments are nothing unless the customers adopt and use them. According to King (207) there will be little return from these investments if customers fail to accept this service. Despite the wide popularity and growth of internet banking, people still feel resistant to use such services due to privacy and security concerns. Moreover, the complex nature of financial services and open nature of internet renders the adoption of this service. Banks therefore must ensure that customers have the combined understandings of both the internet channel and financial services when marketing internet banking services, which is also the primary focus of this research.

1.8 Structure of the Thesis

To achieve the overall aim of this research, this thesis is divided into five sections comprising 6 chapters. Figure 1.4 is the illustration of the structure of the whole thesis. **Section One** is the introduction chapter introducing the research background, rationale for the research and as well as outlines the main research questions and objectives. This section also explores previous internet banking studies and as well as shed light on the trends of internet banking in the UK.

Section Two is the literature review section and consists of four parts. The first part of this chapter is literature review of technology acceptance models. The objective of this chapter is to review and compare important theoretical models such as Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDF), the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and most importantly, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The second part of this chapter reviews the role of customer's trust and perceived risk in the acceptance of internet banking. The chapter also proposes trust model for internet banking by reviewing the trust literature. The third part of this chapter is the internet banking chapter which investigate the main factors that affect both the users and non-users of internet banking. The chapter also examines the critical role of customers' demographic variables (gender, age and level of education) on the TAM relationship. The fourth part of this chapter provides a background of internet banking in the UK. The aim of this chapter is to explore the developments of internet banking services in the UK over the last decade. This part will also provide an overview of UK banking sector and its competitive structure.

Section Three is devoted to conceptual framework and methodology used for this research. Chapter three develops conceptual framework for internet banking acceptance. This chapter incorporates the critical factors affecting customers' internet banking acceptance behaviour. The chapter also proposes hypotheses in order to determine the relationship between these factors. Chapter four is the methodology section which describe the research framework developed, the philosophy, the design, data collection strategy and data analysis method adopted for this research. Justifications for the adopted research method will also be given in this chapter.

Section Four is the most critical section of the overall thesis. This section is devoted to the analysis and findings of the research. The primary data collected for the present study was analysed using various descriptive and statistical testing using SPSS.

Finally, **Section Five** is the overall summary of the whole research. This chapter will include review of research objective, answer to the research questions, major findings, limitation, recommendation for future research and conclusions.

Figure 1.4: Structure of the Thesis

CHAPTER TWO

Literature Review

Chapter two is the literature review chapter comprising four sections: (1) review of technology acceptance models, (2) the concept of trust in internet banking, (3) internet banking research and (4) internet banking in the UK.

Section One:

Review of Technology Acceptance Models

2.1 Introduction

This chapter of the thesis aims to discuss and review the key theoretical frameworks related to technology acceptance, such as the technology acceptance model (TAM), the innovation diffusion theory (IDT), the theory of reasoned actions (TRA) and the theory of planned behaviour (TPB). These theoretical models will lay down the foundation for proposing and developing a theoretical framework for the present study. Research suggest that Technology Acceptance Model is the most useful and tested model for explaining and predicting technology acceptance. Therefore, the present study will focus more on TAM framework for empirical investigation and theoretical model development.

2.2 Theoretical Models of User Acceptance of Technology

Over the past years, researchers have identified number of theoretical models that explains the determinants of IT adoption and usage. These models include the Fishbein and Azjen's (1975) Theory of Reasoned Actions (TRA) and Azjen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behaviour (TBP). The TRA and TBP are proven to be well-researched models in explaining and predicting user's behavioural intention in almost every field. Another powerful intention model is the Davis's (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) that explains and predicts determinants of new technology usage based on two beliefs: the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use of technology. Finally, the Roger's (1983) Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT) is also a prominent framework for explaining the acceptance of new technology. These technology acceptance theories are discussed in detail in the following sections of this chapter.

2.2.1 The Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT)

Rogers (1983) have presented one of the most popular models for the adoption of new innovation, called the *Diffusion of Innovation*. Diffusion of innovation theory explains how an innovation, a new idea about a product or service is spread among specific population or social system. In simple terms, the innovation diffusion theory describes how technology become accepted and adopted by members of a given group. This theory has guided researchers and organisations to study the adoption of numerous technological innovations for several years. Innovation Diffusion Theory states that information about innovation is communicated through certain channels where potential adopters use it to form perceptions; these perceptions, together with other related factors then directly impact their actual intention to adopt or reject such innovation (Rogers, 1983), Brown (1999). As outlined in the figure 2-1 Individuals progress through 5 stages during the innovation diffusion process: knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation and confirmation.

In the first stage, users are introduced to the innovation and get an idea of how it works. This is followed by the persuasion stage where users form favourable or unfavourable attitudes regarding this innovation. In the decision stage users decide whether to accept or reject this new innovation based on its characteristics and advantages. In this stage, users weigh the advantages and disadvantages of the new innovation and then decide whether to adopt or not adoption this innovation. This is followed by the implementation stage where user actually start using the innovation. Finally, in the confirmation stage, user finalizes the decision by adopting the innovation. See figure 2-1.

Figure 2.1: Innovation Diffusion Process (Source: Rogers 1995)

According to Roger (1991) these five factors that influence the adoption of an innovation. (see Table 2-1). These factors determine why and how certain innovations are adopted faster than the others. Each of these factors are different for adopters of innovation as compared with non-adopters (Moore and Benbasat, 1993). These innovation attributes are: 1) relative advantage, (2) compatibility, (3) ease of use, (4) observability, and (5) trialability.

Table 2.1: Perceived Attributes of An Innovation	
Characteristics of an Innovation	Definition
Relative advantage	This is the degree to which an innovation is perceived superior or better to the current practice. Example of relative advantage can be convenience, social prestige, economic advantage or satisfaction.
Compatibility	This characteristic is about how well an innovation meets the needs and experiences of the potential user. An innovation that is incompatible with the values and

	norms of the users is unlikely to be adopted among the users.
Ease of Use	This is about how difficult or easy an innovation is to adopt and use. Innovations that are simpler and easy to understand are adopted more quickly than the ones that require users to develop new skills and understandings. (Premkumar et al (1994).
Trialability	This dimension defines the extent to which an innovation provides tangible results.
Observable Results	This dimension defines the extent to which an innovation provides tangible results. Users are more likely to adopt an innovation if they see visible results.

In summary, Rogers (2003) states that innovation with more relative advantage, compatibility, simplicity and trialability and observability will have higher chances of adoption among social groups. Rogers also argues that a new idea even with obvious relative advantages is difficult to get adopted, therefore it must have all the above 5 perceived attributes of innovation in order to speed up the innovation diffusion process. Information Technology researches indicate all these attributes positively influence members' likelihood of adopting a new technology. Moore and Benbasat (1991) contributed to Roger's work and added two additional attributes, namely image and voluntariness.

In addition to the above five attributes of innovation, Rogers (1995) classified adopters of innovation into five categories (Table 2-2). This classification includes innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards (Rogers, 1995 p 162). Adopters of innovation are classified based on their innovativeness level.

Table 2.2: Perceived Attributes of An Innovation	
Adopter category	Definition
Innovators	Innovators are willing to take risks and are always the first to adopt an innovation. They are the gatekeepers and are interested to experience new ideas. However, for Rogers (2003) they are rare and accounts for only 2.5% of the social group.
Early Adopters.	Individuals in this category are the second fastest in adopting an innovation and accounts for 13.5% of the population. Early adopters play leadership role and other members of the group come to them for advice or information about an innovation.
Early Majority	This is the next 35% of the population to adopt an innovation. Individuals in this category are slower than the innovators and early adopters in the adoption process and do not adopt an innovation until the other half of the peers in the group have adopted it. They need to see evidence that the innovation will work for them before they adopt it.
Late Majority	Individuals in this category are even slower and wait until majority of their peers adopt an innovation. Late majority comprises 35% of the population and are highly risk averse and approach an innovation with high degree of caution scepticism
Laggards	This is the last 16% of the individuals to adopt an innovation. These people are very sceptical and resistance to change and the hardest group to bring on board. They are the most localised group of the social system and have a conservative and traditional view of the innovation.

Rogers (2003) divides these five categories of adopters into two main groups: early adopters and late adopters. Early adopters consist of innovators, early adopters and early majority, whereas late adopters include late majority and laggards (Agarwal and Prasad, 1998). The differences between these two groups are mainly due to individuals' socioeconomic status, personality variables, and communication behaviours. For instance, individual in the social group who are less educated, less wealthy and the like are normally the last to adopt an innovation. Rogers also states that early adopters and

late adopters cannot be differentiated based on their age difference; however, this categorization and its characteristics are beyond the scope of this study.

Figure 2.2: *Categories of Adopters (Source: Rogers 2003)*

2.2.1.1 Criticism of Innovation Diffusion Theory

Although the IDT is a widely used model in IT acceptance research, researchers have put forwards many critics regarding its application. One of the main criticisms of this model is that it is an overlay simplified representation of a complex reality. When the diffusion model is applied for advanced production technologies where decisions are too complex; thus, it cannot be gathered by Innovation Diffusion Theory's Cognitive Power. (Vaugh and Schiavone, 2010). Another criticism of this model is that adopters of innovation fall with different categories for different innovation. i.e. individual falling in laggard category for one innovation can be an early adopter for another innovation (Rogers, 2003). Furthermore, Sahin (2006) argue that this model is mainly based on individual's decision to adopt an innovation; however, when complex organisation processes are in place then innovation diffusion model is less applicable. Apart from this, another criticism is put forward by Dibra (2015) who states that human and human networks are too complex; therefore, it is extremely difficult if not impossible for Innovation Diffusion Theory to measure what exactly caused an adoption of innovation. There might be several other forces affecting an individual's decision to adopt new technology or innovation.

2.2.2 The Theory of Reasoned Actions (TRA)

The Theory of Reasoned Action was developed in the 1960s by Icek Ajzen and Martin Fishbein and is a model that aims to explain human intention to engage in a certain behaviour. The TRA is a famous theory that have been used in technology adoption and number of other research fields. According to this model, a person's behaviour to do a particular action is predicted by two main factors: A person's attitude towards that behaviour and his/her subjective norms (Fishbein and Ajzen ,1975, p.62). In other words, the TRA theory focus on three main constructs: (1) behavioural intention, (2) attitude and (3) subjective norm. Theory of Reasoned Action hypothesizes an individual's intention is mainly determined by two determinants: a personal factor which is called 'attitude towards behaviour' and opinions of individual's social environment term as 'subjective norm'.

$$\text{Behavioural Intention} = \text{Attitude} (w1) + \text{Subjective Norm} (w2)$$

Attitude is the person's positive or negative assessment of performing a particular behaviour. In other words, attitude reflect an individual's general feeling about the intended behaviour. The TRA assumes that the higher the positive feeling of performing a certain behaviour, the higher the intention towards that behaviour. (Fishbein, 1991). Attitude towards the behaviour is determined by combination of two related factors: (1) individual's belief regarding the outcome of the behaviour and (2) his/her evaluation of the potential outcome (consequences) of that behaviour. Attitude can be illustrated as follows:

$$\text{Attitude} = \text{Behavioural Beliefs} * \text{Evaluations}$$

Subjective norm is concerned with an individual's perceived social pressure whether to engage or not engage in a given behaviour (Mathieson (1991). As the name implies, subjective norms are influenced by the subjects around us: parents, friends, partners, colleagues and so on. The TRA suggests that people often act based on their perception of whether these subjects and groups would approve or disapprove the behaviour. However, apart from social pressure, individual's decision to adopt a certain behaviour is also influenced by how motivated they are to comply with their views (Ajzen, 1975).

$$\text{Subjective Norm} = \text{Normative Belief} * \text{Motivation to Comply}$$

Figure 2.3 below diagrams the Theory of Reasoned Action.

Figure 2.3: Theory of Reasoned Action

Source: Ajzen (1975)

As clear from the above diagram, behavioural intention is influenced by a person’s attitude and subjective norms. Attitude, in turn, is predicted by their behavioural belief and evaluation.

The Theory of Reasoned Action has been used in a variety of research settings, from information systems (Loiacono et al., 2007; Rensel et al., 2006) to predicting knowledge sharing intentions (Bock et al, 2005), healthcare, crime investigation (Shih and Fang, 2006), study customer behaviour and several others. However, the purpose of this study is to examine the factors that influence individuals’ intention to adopt internet banking, mainly related with technology adoption.

2.2.21 Critiques of the TRA

Likewise, any other theoretical framework, the theory of reasoned action has also been criticised by many scholars and researchers. Firstly, the major limitation of this model is presented by Foxall (1997) who claims that TRA fails to take into the account the non-attitudinal or situational factors that can influence or enhance person's prediction of behaviour. Another critical comment put forth by Davis et al (1989) is that TRA is general framework and does not consider the specific belief that are operative for a particular behaviour. He further suggests that when employing the TRA model researchers must identify beliefs that are salient for subjects. Further, the TRA model has been criticised by Planning (2015) for failing to predict outcomes from the behaviour. The TRA deals only with the prediction of behaviour but provides no information regarding the outcomes of the behaviour in questions.

Another major limitation of that TRA model is that it assumes that behaviours are totally under volitional control. It fails to acknowledge that person's behaviour might be directed or limited by several constraints, meaning that there are actions that can be determined by several other uncontrollable factors (Shepherd et al (1989). Sometimes additional skills and resources are required to engage in a certain behaviour. For instance, if a person does not have access to resources such as personal computer and internet, he/she might not be able to use internet banking services. (Sarver,1983). In simple terms, TRA fails to predict actual behaviour when a person has low level of voluntary control.

2.2.3 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) was proposed by Ajzen (1991) as a refinement and extension to the earlier theory of reasoned actions (TRA) by incorporating a third element, perceived behavioural control. The TPB suggest that apart from attitude and subjective norm, individual's behavioural intentions are also influenced by perceived behavioural control (Ajzen, 1991).

Figure 2.5: *Theory of Planned Behaviour*
Source: Ajzen (1991)

According to this theory, individual's actual behaviour is influenced by three main factors:

- 1. Behavioural Beliefs:** The outcome and consequences of the intended behaviour.
- 2. Normative Beliefs:** The social pressure of the subjects around us.
- 3. Control Beliefs:** The presence of resources and opportunities that may influence person's decision about the targeted behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

When combined, behavioural beliefs, normative beliefs and control beliefs result in the formation of an intention and this in turn results in the actual behaviour. In general, the more favourable the behavioural and normative beliefs of the individual, the stronger his/her intention will be to engage in a given behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

$$\text{Behavioural Intentions} = \text{Attitude } (w1) + \text{Subjective Norm } (w2) + \text{Perceived Behavioural Control } (w3)$$

The theory of planned behaviour assumes that actual behaviour is influenced by two main factors: (1) Person's motivation to engage in a behaviour and (2) Person's confidence in his/her ability to perform that behaviour. In other words, behaviour is influenced by behavioural intention and perceived behavioural control. As per Azjen (1991) it is more likely that a person will engage in a given behaviour when there is sufficient degree of control over that behaviour. Two rationales have been provided for this hypothesis. First, if intention is held constant, the person likelihood to engage in a behaviour will increase with PBC. For instance, if two individuals have the same level of intention to use internet banking, the person who is more confident in his/her ability to use this technology will benefit more from it than the person who is not confident or doubt his/her ability. Secondly, PBC can be used as a substitute for actual control when measuring the link between behavioural control and behavioural achievements.

As per Azjen (1991 p.188) the importance of subjective norm, attitude and perceived behavioural control in measuring people intention varies from situation to situation and behaviour to behaviour. In some settings, only attitude determinant might be significant while in other situations all the three determinants might be important. For example, a study based on 128 applications developers cited by Riemenschneider and Hardgrave (2002) indicated that only attitude and subjective norm determinants were found to be useful in measuring developers' intention. Perceived behavioural control (PBC) did not influence their intention and was however, not useful.

Apart from this, several other studies have compared the TPB model to other theoretical frameworks. For instance, Hansen, Jensen and Solgaard (2004) employed the TRA and TPB simultaneously to predict user's behavioural intention in grocery buying. It was found that both models (TRA and TPB) were useful in explaining high proportion (more than 55%) of the variance in consumer behaviour to engage in the future online grocery purchase. However, theory of planned behaviour (TPB) with the inclusion of perceived behavioural control (PBC) proved more useful and provided more accurate results in predicting user's intention towards online grocery buying. Similarly, Kisamore (2010) applied the Theory of Planned Behaviour in predicting students' academic misconduct intention and behaviour. A sample of 241 business undergraduate students were studied and it was found that TPB accounted for 21% of the variance in cheating intention and 36% cheating behaviour. The study also found that TPB was a valuable tool for predicting behavioural intentions of the individual (Cameron et al, 2012).

Several researches have incorporated additional constructs to the TPB model to enhance its applicability in various settings. For example, Morris, Venkate and Ackerman (2005) added additional elements such as gender and age to the TPB model. Based on the 342 responses from five firms, it was found that differences in individual's gender were not important when employing new technology. The study also revealed that attitude and subjective norms were important to men than women.

Based on the 16 studies of intention prediction using the TPB model cited by Azjen and Madden (1986); Van Ryn and Vinokur (1990); Azjen (1991) it was found that the inclusion of perceived behavioural control (PBC) has added significant value to the TRA and has improved its applicability in the prediction of behavioural intentions. Similarly, Seyal and Rahman (2017) claims that TPB is a very useful model for understanding individuals' behavioural intentions towards technology acceptance and usage. He further suggests that the TPB has a very strong theoretical anchor and is applicable in wide range of settings. In sum, the TPB has guided researchers and organisations in a number of technology-related contexts, including predicting employees' reaction to new technologies (Venkatesh *et al*, 2004 and Morris *et al*, 2005), predicting individual intentions towards e-commerce (Pavlou and Chai, 2002; Uzoka *et al*, 2007), explaining customer acceptance of online shopping (George, 2004; Shim *et al*, 2007), and online grocery buying intention (Hansen *et al*, 2004). The TPB has been successfully employed by researchers for explaining customer perception of internet banking (Hernandez and Mazzon, 2007). Apart from these, the TPB have been applied to numerous other contexts; however, they are outside the scope of the current research.

It can be concluded from the above studies that TPB has proven to be the most powerful diagnostic tool for explaining and predicting technological systems acceptance and adoption. It was also noted that the TPB outperform TRA in technology acceptance research for the fact that consumer intention to engage in online environment (e.g. internet banking, online shopping) does not occur solely because they decide to act but on their level of control they over the given behaviour.

2.2.3.1 Criticism of the TPB

Although popular and successful, the TPB is still criticised by several researchers and academic scholars. First, the TPB is not self-sufficient, meaning that attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control alone are not enough to predict people's intention and behaviour (Kraft et al, 2005). There are several other external factors and variables that must be taken into consideration such as desire and need, anticipated regret, personal and moral norms, experience from past behaviour and most importantly self-identity (Ajzen 2011; McEachan, Conner, Taylor and Lawton, 2011). Another major critique of this model is put forward by Alselaimi (2010) who claims that repeated performances becomes routine behaviours and does not require much perceived behavioural control for its execution. He further suggests that in habituation actions initiation of the behaviour becomes automatic and control over the behaviour is no longer required.

A further limitation of this model is that human attitude and behaviour may vary based on different empirical settings and therefore there is a need for a tailored and personalised scale that can better explain and predict user's behavioural intention.

Ajzen (1991) has suggested that the TPB model is open to further elaboration:

The Theory of Planned Behaviour is, in principle, open to inclusion of additional elements if it can be shown that they capture significant proportion of variance in intention or behaviour after the theories' current variables have been taken into account (P.199).

2.2.4 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

As mentioned above, there are number of technology acceptance models that explains and predicts customer acceptance of new technology; however, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has proven to be the most powerful and widely used framework of technology acceptance.

For this reason, the present study aims to use TAM as the basis for researching consumers' behaviour about the acceptance of internet banking technology in the UK.

Figure 2.6: The Technology Acceptance Model

Source: Davis, (1989).

As shown in the above diagram, the TAM is an extension of the TRA framework and hypothesizes that users' motivation to adopt new technology is determined by their behavioural intention and behavioural intention is in turn influenced by their attitude towards using that technology. The attitude of the user is jointly influenced by two major beliefs: Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use. Perceived usefulness is the degree to which user believe that utilising a particular technology or technique will result in improved job performance. In simple terms, perceived usefulness is about how useful or effective the potential technology is to adopt and use. PU was initially used for organisational settings; however, later it was applied to other common tasks and non-organisational settings (e.g. Online shopping, internet banking etc.). On the other hand, perceived ease of use (PEU) is the user's perception about how effortless and hassle free the potential technology is to adopt and use.

PU and PEU are the main determinants that directly influences user's attitude whether to accept or reject the new technology. Davis (1989) also suggests that PU and PEU are interrelated (For instance, even if a new technology is useful, users will not adopt it if it is complicated to understand). As Per Davis (1989) the PU and PEU are the two most

significant determinants of the TAM model that explain user acceptance of technology. These two determinants are influenced by various external factors such as design of the system, service quality, training, documents and other support mechanisms related to technology usage (Davis, 1989).

The TAM model has been used in wide variety of researches relating to user acceptance of technology (Rauniar et al., 2014; Sharif Abbasi et al., 2011; Abbasi et al., 2015). TAM was originally developed to test employees' attitude towards word processor technology in 1989. Since then, TAM has extended to explain and predict user's behaviour in various technology settings, including e-mail, graphics software, voice messages, personal computer (Igarria and Livari, 1995) internet (Gefen and Straub, 2000), internet banking (Yousafzai, 2007), internet shopping among others. Davis (1989) compared TRA, TPB and TAM in examining user's behaviour towards the acceptance of word processing program. Result revealed that TAM was more powerful in explaining user behaviour as compared to TRA and TPB. It was found that TAM was able to explain up to 51% of variance in the behavioural intention. These results were summarised in two points: (1) PU was a major determinant in explaining students' intention to use personal computers, (2) PEU had a major impact on intention as well. Similarly, Mathieson (1991) studied Western University's 262 junior and senior management students' intention to adoption spread sheet software by using TAM and TPB models. The results from the study indicated that both TAM and TPB were suitable models to predict individuals' intention; however, the TAM was more powerful and empirically advantageous. Moreover, the TAM was easier to apply and better predicted students' behavioural intention towards using information system.

Yousafzai (2007) and Fusilier & Durlabhji (2005) have compared the applicability of the TAM model across different countries: USA, Japan and the Switzerland. The purpose of the study was to test employees' perception on using their company's intranet e-mail system. The study concluded that TAM model was very useful to predict user's behaviour both in USA and Switzerland but not in Japan. Furthermore, Gentry and Calantone compared the TRA, TPB and TAM to predict the users' behaviour towards web technology. The study found that all three models were effective; however, the TAM was more superior and powerful in explaining variance in the behavioural intention. Burton and Hubona (2006) conducted another study to predict and explain people behaviour towards online bidding. He compared the TPB and TAM and found that both models were effective in explaining the variance of up to 84% to

87% in behavioural intentions to bid online; however, the TAM framework was more parsimonious than the TPB. The study also found that PU and PEU are the main predictors of the user's willingness to bid online.

The TAM model is claimed to be the most powerful and popular model of technology acceptance due to three main reasons: (1) It is parsimonious and IT-specific, specifically designed for investigation and prediction of user's attitude towards wide range of computer technologies and information systems. According to Venkatesh (2000) TAM has proven to be the most powerful and robust model of technology acceptance over the past decade. (2) it has a very strong theoretical base and empirically supported and validated by numerous authors and researchers over the last two decades (e.g. Venkatesh, 2000; Moon and Kim, 2001; Hsia, 2007; Tseng and Hsia, 2008; Fareed et al, 2012; Al-Mohammad, 2014). (3) It has a very strong explanatory power as compared to technology acceptance frameworks and models (Mathieson, Peacock and Chin 2001).

Originally formulated in the USA, TAM has been widely used and tested in different environments and countries overtime. The first TAM study outside the United States was conducted by Philips *et al* (1994). He employed and validated the TAM model in China and found that culture can play a major role in the predictive capacity of TAM. The TAM determinants (PU and PEU) will respond differently in different countries and cultures. Table 2-4 below lists number of TAM studies by country classification. The data is retrieved from the journal published in 2006 and can be considered as outdated; however, it provides an overview of TAM studies conducted outside the USA.

Austria	1 (77)	Hong Kong	12 (3695)	Singapore	4 (1508)
Australia	3 (747)	Japan	3 (493)	South Korea	5 (3920)
Brazil	1 (79)	Jordan	1 (121)	Sudan	1 (45)
Brunei	1 (166)	Kuwait	1 (387)	Switzerland	2 (304)
Canada	4 (1147)	Lebanon	1 (35)	Taiwan	5 (663)
China	1 (303)	Netherlands	4 (1129)	Turkey	1 (52)
Denmark	1 (45)	Nigeria	2 (231)	UAE	2 (450)
Egypt	1 (45)	New Zealand	2 (460)	UK	8 (1536)
Finland	2 (900)	Saudi Arabia	1 (28)	USA	98 (17787)
France	1 (110)				
Total sample size for TAM studies = 36463					

Note: No of studies (cumulative sample size for the country)

Table 2.3: TAM Studies by Country Classification

Source: Shumaila Y. Yousafzai, Gorden R. Foxall and John G. Pallister (2006)

Apart from this, Shih (2004) lists number of TAM studies for different information systems

Information Systems/Organisations	Example/Country	Author/s
Key office IS applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spreadsheet Lotus 1-2-3 • WordPerfect • Word • Excel 	(Mathieson, 1991; Adams et al., 1992; Hendrickson et al., 1993; Segars and Grover, 1993; Taylor and Todd, 1995a; Taylor and Todd, 1995b; Chau, 1996; Venkatesh and Davis, 1996; Doll et al., 1998)
Communication technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email • Voice mail • Customer dial-up system • Fax 	(Adams et al., 1992; Segars and Grover, 1993; Subramanian, 1994; Straub et al., 1995; Szjna, 1996; Venkatesh and Davis, 1996; Gefen and Straub, 1997)
Database systems	-	(Hendrickson et al., 1993; Szajan, 1994; Doll et al., 1998; Venkatesh et al., 2003)
Workstations	-	(Moore and Benasat, 1991; Lucas and Spittler, 1999)
Microcomputers	-	(Igbria et al., 1995; Igbria et al., 1996; Agarwal and Prasad, 1999)
Telemedicine technology for physicians	-	(Hu et al., 1999; Chau and Hu, 2001; Chau and Hu, 2002)
Internet-related IS applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WWW • WWW information services • Online services • Virtual workplace systems • Digital libraries 	(Venkatesh and Moriis, 2000; Agarwal and Prasad, 1998; Parthasarathy and Bhattacharjee, 1998, Venkatesh, 1999; Chau and Hu, 2001)
B2C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web-based bookstores • Online services firm 	(Koufaris 2002; Gefen et al., 2003)
Financial institution	• America	(Straub et al, 1995)
Integrated steel company	• Canada	(Montazemi et al., 1996)
Public tertiary hospitals	• Hong Kong	(Hu et al., 1999)
Universities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University of Michigan • Boston University • Minnesota University • Open University of Hong Kong 	(Davis et al., 1989; Davis, 1989; Venkatesh and Davis, 1996; Hong et al., 2001)

Table 2.4: Use of TAM for different Information Systems
Source: Shih (2004)

The above table shows that TAM model has guided researchers and organisations in various end-user technologies and information systems ranging from office applications to communication technologies, web applications, B2B services, financial software among others. For this reason, the TAM has been chosen for this study which will act as the base for developing a conceptual framework.

2.2.4.1 The Role of Attitude in TAM

As stated above, users' behavioural intention directly determined by their attitude towards using that system (Davis, 1989). Attitude was considered as the key determinant to predict user acceptance of technology in the original TAM model. However, as more studies were conducted on TAM, it was argued that the attitude construct is not necessary and the explanatory power of the TAM remains the same without the mediating attitude element. Various researches on the TAM indicate that the attitude construct might be necessary like many other behavioural variables, but it is not sufficient condition for predicting user acceptance of technology.

The attitude construct is claimed to be not useful in TAM model due to these three main reasons. First, perceived usefulness directly determines behavioural intention about using the technology and the need for attitude construct is not important. Secondly, there is a weak direct link between PEU and attitude. Third, TAM is parsimonious on its own. As per Davis, (1989) when TAM model is applied to technologies where other factors are taken into account such as PU and PEU the attitude construct is not a strong predictor of intentions. Various studies have employed the TAM model without the attitude construct and the predicting power of the model still remain strong (Yousafzai, 2007; Chaung, 2008; Gumussoy & Calisir, 2009 and Al-Mohammad, 2014). This is supported by Taylor and Todd (1995) who claims that in setting where performance of the technology is the key, intentions to use that technology are formed based on performance considerations rather than user's attitude.

However, several other authors contradict with the above statements and believe that attitude is the main mediator of behavioural intentions that filters information and shape the individual perception of the technology. It is further claimed that the attitude construct is discounted from the TAM model without significant theoretical support. According to Davis (1989) individual's decision to use new technology is determined by PU and PEU and behavioural intentions, and attitude act as the best partial mediator.

2.2.4.2 Importance of PU and PEU in the TAM

The Technology Acceptance model (TAM) postulates that user's intention to accept or reject new technology is influenced by two main determinants: (1) perceived usefulness (PU) which is defined as the *degree to which user believe that utilising a particular technology or technique will result in improved job performance*, and perceived ease of use (PEU) which is defined as *is the user's perception about how effortless and hassle free the potential technology is to adopt and use*. (Davis, 1989). However, researches have emphasized the importance of PU over the PEU as the main determinants of technology acceptance. In other words, PU plays a key role in influencing user's technology adoption decision more than the PEU. As per Davis (1989) even if a system requires some effort but is useful to the potential user will inhibit adoption. Two studies conducted by David (1989) based on four applications and involving 152 users found that perceived usefulness was more strongly and directly related to these systems usages. He further stated that people are keen to cope with efforts in using a technology that will improve their job performance; however, application even easy to use will not be adopted if it does not offer useful results to potential user. Majority of the studies have not confirmed a direct link between PEU and technology usage. Some scholars have termed the PEU as a '*step child*' determinant of the TAM.

The role of PEU in technology acceptance model, however, is subject to huge debate. In contradicted studies Fareed and Mustafa (2002) and Al-Mohammad (2007) claims that PEU has a strong, direct and equal effect than PU on technology adoption. Similarly, in contrast to Davis (1989) study, Lim and Ting (2012) states there is direct link between PEU and behavioural intention. Even some studies claim a negative relationship between PU and acceptance of new technology (Teo, et al, 2004). Further, results from Aulamie (2013) study reveals that PEU positively influence user's intention to accept new technology. He found that users who participated in different training programs noted that PEU mainly influence their intention as compared to PU. On the other hand, Igbaria and Livari (1995) applied the TAM in Finland and their results revealed PU is not sufficient to influence individuals' behaviour.

Researchers have also recommended the role of experience, gender (Venkatesh and Morris (2000) and task type (Moon and Kim, 2001) in determining the importance of PU and PEU. In sum, research suggests that the role of PU and PEU varies for different

technology types, user population and different time periods. It is therefore concluded that TAM literature has not effectively explained these inconsistencies.

2.2.4.3 Dependent Variable in the TAM

In the original TAM, Davis, (1986) used ‘actual use’ as the dependent variable to examine the acceptance of technology. However, further literature on TAM suggests ‘behavioural intention’ as the ultimate dependent variable as compared to actual use. After conducting an in-depth analysis of TAM and considering the nature of this study, the researcher aims to use ‘behavioural intention’ as the dependent variable for two reasons. First, it is clear from the previous researches that user’s actual behaviour is directly influenced by their behavioural intention (Davis, 1989; Khan Jan, 2002). Secondly, the present study aims to study the consumers’ behaviour towards internet banking in the UK. Therefore, the researcher believes that the use of behavioural intention as the ultimate dependent variable is theoretically justifiable and appropriate for this study.

2.2.4.4 External Variables in the TAM

As stated earlier, the TAM hypothesizes that there are two main determinants of intention, PU and PEU. However, the TAM fails to explain these how perceptions (PU and PEU) are formed and how they can be manipulated to increase the users’ acceptance of technology (Mathieson, 1991). Researchers have identified number of possible antecedents of perceived usefulness and ease of use towards technology usage. In other words, there are number of external factors that can have a direct impact on PU and PEU. For instance, Venkatesh (2000) conducted three studies in three different settings and the results revealed that control, intrinsic motivation and emotion served as the anchors in forming perceived ease of use. Similarly, Stern *et al.*, (2008) investigated the antecedents of PU and PEU in the context of online auction system. The study found that affinity with the computer and level of risk tolerance significantly influence PU and PEU.

The first external variable added to the TAM by Davis *et al.*, (1992) was output quality, and since then the researchers have identified number of external variables for PU and PEU. These external variables have been divided into four categories: organisational, system, user’s personal characteristics and other variables.

2.2.4.5 Extension of Technology Acceptance Model (ETAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model originally developed by Davis (1986) has been adapted and extended in many ways with more than 700 citations put forth by several authors. The first extension to the TAM was proposed by Venkatesh and Davis (2000) to investigate the factors that affect user's perception of usefulness of a system. Therefore, they proposed five variables: subjective norm, output quality, result demonstrability, image and job relevance as the key factors or determinants that affect perceived usefulness. This model was labelled, the TAM 2 model. The extended model was found to be more useful and was able to explain 40% - 60% variance of user's perceptions of usefulness. A second most important extension was proposed by Venkatesh and Bala (2008) to identify the antecedents of perceived ease of use. The proposed variables were self-efficacy, external control, computer playfulness, computer anxiety, objective usability and perceived enjoyment. The model was called, the TAM 3 model. As per Venkatesh et al (2003) the predictive capability of the TAM was significantly increased after the inclusion of moderating variables. The TAM 2 and TAM 3 models are shown in the figures below:

Figure 2.7: TAM 2

Source: Venkatesh and Davis, 2000)

Figure 2.8: TAM 3

Source: Venkatesh and Bala, 2008)

Apart from the TAM 2 and TAM 3, researchers have extended the technology acceptance model in many other ways. For instance, Gumussoy and Calisir (2009) have integrated the TPB and IDT with the TAM to enhance its predictive power. The model was employed to identify the factors influencing customer's intention to use auction in the companies. The study found that subjective norm, PU and perceived behavioural control together explained 76% of variance in employees' intention towards using auctions. Similarly, Lee (2009) integrated the TAM with TPB and ECM models to explain people continued use of e-learning services. The study found that the predictive and explanatory power of these three models is more than that of TAM alone.

The TAM was also extended by Gefen *et al.*, (2003) by including the trust aspect in user's adoption of electronic commerce. The study was designed with the aim to

investigate how important the concept of trust is for the customer in e-vendor business. The results showed that repeat customer has more trust in the e-vendor as compared to potential customer for the fact that the website is perceived useful and easier to use. Furthermore, Pikkarainen *et al*, (2004) suggested that TAM model is useful but additional aspects needs to be included such as privacy and security along with PU and PEU to fully understand the adoption behaviour towards internet banking services.

Lai et al, (2005) integrated the IDT with the TAM and suggested that these models combined have more predictive and explanatory power in explaining customer’s use of electronic banking in the USA. Most importantly, researchers have associated the issue of trust with TAM in adoption decision of internet banking services. Researchers also claim that trust in the services provided positively affect customer behaviour towards internet banking and other related distribution channels. Luo et al (2010) states that online trust plays a critical role in influencing user’s decision to accept or reject internet banking. Therefore, many studies have highlighted the importance of trust construct with TAM when studying user’s acceptance of e-banking services.

Furthermore, study conducted by Lewis et al (2010) suggests that compatibility, risk and perceived usefulness together are the key factors that affect user’s intention towards mobile banking adoption. Ozdemir, Hoecht and Trott (2008) studies internet banking adoption in Turkey. The study found that adopters of internet banking perceived the channel useful, ease to use and less risky as compared to those who do not adopt this service. In another study, Yiu, Grant and Edgar (2007) investigated the link between PU and PEU and personal effectiveness and found that these variables play a key role in shaping consumer behavioural intention towards internet banking. On the other hand, Wessels and Drenman (2010) study revealed that PU, perceived risk, compatibility, and cost are all related in the customer acceptance of mobile banking in Australia.

The table below provide the list of studies that have extended the original TAM:

Table 2.5: Extended Studies of the Original TAM Model		
Study	Core constructs added to the TAM	Key findings about the new constructs
Dishaw and Strong (1991)	Task characteristics, experience, tool functionality and task technology fit	Task technology fit affect PEU and actual use of the technology.
Venkatesh and Davis (2000)	Subjective Norm, Image, Job Relevance, Voluntariness, output	These variables directly influence PU and PEU which in

	quality, result demonstrability and PEU	turn affect user's behavioural intention.
Moon and Kim (2001)	Perceived playfulness and perceived enjoyment	PEU is directly determined by perceived playfulness. Perceived playfulness has a more direct effect on people's attitude as compared to PU.
Matheison et al (2001)	User's resources	User acceptance or rejection of technology is determined by his/her financial ability and access to other resources and opportunities. This is also related to PU and PEU.
Chen et al, (2002)	Compatibility	Compatibility influences user's perception of usefulness and is a main determinant that affect consumer's attitude towards using a particular system.
Gefen et al (2003)	Familiarity and Trust	Familiarity and trust are found to be the key determinants of user accepting of online stores, mainly for potential customers.
Klopping and McKinney	TTF (Tast-technology fit)	TTF directly influence PU, PEU and ultimately behavioural intention to use a technology.
Vijayasarathy (2004)	Privacy, Security, Compatibility, and Self-efficacy	Compatibility and security are the main factors that affect consumer attitude towards online shopping.
Shih (2004)	Relevance	PU, PEU and customer's attitude to use internet is determined by how relevant the information is.
Hsu and Lu (2004)	Social Influences and flow experience	User intention to play online games are strongly influenced by social norms and flow experience but not by perceived critical mass. Most importantly, flow experience is also strongly and directly related to PEU.
Burton Jones and Hubona (2005)	Seniority, age and education level	Difference in individuals' demographics characteristics affect the frequency and volume of technology acceptance. Furthermore, these differences indirectly influence PU and PEU.

Luarn and Lin (2005)	Credibility, Self-efficacy and Financial cost.	Self-efficacy, credibility and financial costs are the main determinants that influence consumer intention to accept and use mobile banking services. Perceived credibility has strong predictive power than the TAM constructs alone.
Lee et al (2006)	Subjective Norm and Self identity	Self-identity directly influence technology acceptance, while subjective norm has not effect.
Burton Jones and Hubona (2006)	Level of education, system experience	System experience positively influence PEU which in turn affect technology usage and frequency.
Porter and Donthu (2006)	Demographic variables (age, income level, race and education level).	Age, education, race and income level mediate consumer attitude towards the use of internet.
Schepers and Wetzels (2007)	Subjective Norm	Subjective norms significantly influence PU and behavioural intention of the users.
Wu et al (2007)	PU, PEU and other system factors	PU and PEU directly influence actual use of technology
Amin et (2008)	Perceived credibility, perceived expressiveness (Amount of information on mobile cards for customers)	The study found that PU, PEU perceived credibility and perceived expressiveness are the key determinants that predicts the Malaysian customers' intention to use mobile phone cards. `
Gummusoy and Caliser (2009)	Compatibility, subjective norm PBC	Consumer's decision to accept or reject a technology is mainly influenced by PU, PBC and subjective norm.
Lee (2009)	perceived benefits, risk trust, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control.	The study found that risk, perceived benefits, and perceived usefulness (PU) directly influence individuals' behavioural intention to engage in online trading. It was also found that trust also play a significant role.

Source: Almohaimmeed (2010) and This research

2.2.4.6 Criticism of the TAM

Although several studies have confirmed the robustness of the technology acceptance model, there are also many limitations put forth by the researchers. First, as stated above, the TAM model considers PU and PEU as the key determinants of intention; however, it pay no attention to how customer's perception towards these beliefs are formed (Mathieson, 1990). There are number of external variables (as shown in Table 2-4) that influence the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness.

Secondly, TAM assumes the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use fully explain the effects of external variables on behavioural intentions. However, several researchers have criticised this assumption and claim that this assumption is overstated (Jones and Hubona, 2006). For instance, a study conducted by Jones and Hubona (2006) involving 106 IT administrative staff found that differences in demographic characteristics (age, education level, seniority) had significant and direct effect on frequency and volume of usage.

Third, many studies have claimed that the explanatory power of the original TAM is low which accounts for explaining 40% variance in the behavioural intentions Venkatesh and Davis, 2000; Sun and Zhong, 2005; Fareed et al, 2009). Sun and Zhong claims that the explanatory power of the TAM is affected by several other factors such as study environment, participant type and the type of study being conducted. He further suggests that the addition of new variables will improve the explanatory power of the TAM.

Fourth, TAM has also been criticised for inconsistencies between its main constructs, i.e. PU and PEU. For instance, several studies have confirmed positive and significant relationship between perceived ease of use and behavioural intention (Davis, 1989; Davis and Venkatesh, 2000; Gefen *et al*, 2003). However, number of other researches claims no direct link between PEU and user's intention (e.g., Davis *et al*, 1992; Chau, 1996; Straub *et al*, 1997; Park, 2009). As per Venkatesh and Morries (2000) perceived ease of use is perceived differently based on user's experience, system complexity and gender.

Furthermore, another main criticism of the TAM is that it uses self-reported data instead of real actual data to measure technology usage. Some researchers claim that TAM measure is subjective in nature, and is thus unreliable in measuring actual use of the technology (Yousafzai, Foxall and Pallister, 2007). For instance, most of the studies

conducted on TAM use students or employees as the participant in controlled environments, and therefore, the results obtained from these studies cannot be generalized to the real world (Oluwole, 2015). Researchers argue that these students and employees might have different motivations such as obtaining grades, rewards and so on. Another major limitation is put forth by Yousafzai et al (2007) who claims that majority of the studies carried out on TAM predict technology usage in voluntary settings, very few studies considered systems that were for mandatory use. However, in real world, organisations require user to use the available systems with little or no choice for alternatives.

Straub, *et al* (1997) criticises the TAM for not suitable across cultures. Number of researchers have applied the TAM outside North America and found that it is not as successful in predicting user acceptance of technology. He further claims that Hofstede's cultural dimension of uncertainty avoidance, power distance and individualism may limit the applicability of TAM in other countries.

In the later research, it was also found that the TAM model fails to include other important variables such as perceived risk and perceived trust what might play a crucial role in predicting user technology acceptance. As stated by Olushola and Abiola (2016) that trust plays a key role in the success of the e-commerce acceptance. Even if the potential technology is perceived useful and easy to use, consumer will not accept it unless addresses the trust issue.

Davis and Venkatesh (2000) and Venkatesh, *et al* (2005) suggest that there are several other competing models of technology acceptance such as TRA and TPB which hold strong theoretical base. Therefore, TAM should be associated with these competing models for a more informative picture and assistance.

2.2.4.7 Use of TAM in Internet Banking Research

As stated above, the Technology Acceptance Model is the most powerful and highly cited model that has guided researchers and practitioners in many technology adoption studies. Originally defined for organisational settings, TAM and its extensions have been widely used in many studies for predicting and explaining user's acceptance of different end-user technologies. More specifically, literature shows evidence of numerous studies that have used TAM for internet banking adoption. The current study thus will use TAM as the basis for developing a conceptual framework of internet banking acceptance.

TAM for online banking was first used by Bhattacharjee (2001) in a cross-field survey. The main constructs used in the research were PU, intention to use information system, satisfaction and confirmation. The result from the study revealed that satisfaction was the strongest predictor for user acceptance of any information systems. Since then, TAM has been extended in many ways and has been applied to internet banking adoption researches around the globe. Dabholkar and Bagozzi (2002) was the second researcher who employed TAM for investigating of situational factors on consumers' attitude for self-service technologies (SST). Similarly, Karjaluoto, Mattila and Pento (2002) applied the TAM to study the attitude of customers toward internet banking services. The study used a structured equation model and segmented the customer based on non-users, potential users and existing users. The study found that previous experience with technology and attitude towards technology were the main factors that influence their behaviour towards internet banking services.

Pikkarainen et al. (2004) proposed four new constructs to the original TAM to study customer acceptance of online banking services. These constructs were: perceived enjoyment, security and privacy, quality of internet connection and previous experience with online banking. These new constructs were found to have a positive overall impact on customer's attitude to use online banking. The model was tested in Finland and results from the study indicate that previous experience with online banking website perceived usefulness were the main drivers that influenced consumer acceptance of online banking. However, their model was criticised for failing to include several other important factors influencing acceptance of online banking, as mentioned in TAM 2. Similarly, Yiu *et al.* (2007) explored the TAM literature and proposed two new factors: risk and personal innovativeness. They suggest that apart from PU and PEU, perceived

risk and personal innovativeness also directly influence internet banking adoption. Findings from their survey revealed that ability to perform banking activities anywhere, anytime and reduction in processing times were the key determinants that affects the use of internet banking among customers.

The table below provides the list of internet banking studies that have used TAM.

Table 2.6: List of Internet Banking Studies that Used TAM		
Internet Banking Study	Variables added to the TAM	Key Findings
Bhattacharjee (2001)	Satisfaction and Confirmation	Customer's satisfaction with internet banking directly influence their intention to use the service.
Dabholkar and Bagozzi (2002)	Waiting time, social anxiety and time pressure	
Karjaluoto et al. (2002)	Prior experience with technology, attitude towards computers, occupation, household income	Customer's existing experience with computers and attitude affects their intention to use internet banking.
Porter and Donthu (2006)	Perceived access barrier	The study was designed to find why demographic-based differences (such as age, educational level, income level) affect internet banking use. Age affects both PU and PEU usefulness, income and race affects PU and education level affects perceived ease of use.
Pikkarainen et al. (2004)	Privacy and security, information of online banking and internet connection quality	These four attributes together influence internet banking adoption among customers.
Yiu et al. (2007)	Perceived risk and personal innovativeness	Customer adoption of online banking is directly influenced by PU, PEU, personal innovativeness and perceived risk.
Sukkar and Hasan (2005)	Economics, politics, Infrastructure, as well as cultural and trust issues	Cross-cultural differences and other circumstances affects the applicability of TAM across different nations. Internet banking adoption is influenced

		differently in different countries; therefore, TAM must include cultural and other macro-environmental factors to make it universally applicable.
Alalwan et al. (2016)	Perceived risk and self-efficacy	Consumer's decision to use mobile banking is influenced by PU, PEU, self-efficacy and perceived risk.
Kesharwani and Bisht (2012)	Trust, perceived risk, social influence, website design and perceived behavioural control.	Online trust negatively influences perceived risk. Social influence and PEU positively affect online banking adoption and usage.
Shanmugam (2015)	Relative advantage, perceived risk, personal innovativeness, social norms and perceived costs	Relative advantage and perceived costs are found to be the strongest predictors among Zimbabwe internet banking customers.

Source: Many as indicated above

The table above is the indication of how TAM has been employed in numerous internet banking researches. TAM is a very prominent and parsimonious model that has guided scholars and researchers in technology acceptance researches. However, the original TAM model developed in 1986 is inadequate for today's technological environment because the technologies and transaction in internet banking are very different from that of conventional IT infrastructure. Therefore, the present study is adding extra variables to the model such as the issues of trust, security, risk and demographics to develop a more comprehensive and robust framework of customer acceptance of internet banking in the UK.

2.2.5 Comparison of the TRA, the TPB, and the TAM

1. Degree of Generality

The first and foremost difference between the three models noted by Mathieson (1991) is the degree of generality. In TAM, the PU and PEU are the key factors of technology acceptance and be generalized to different technologies and populations. However, the TRA and TPB, uses situation specific belief and suggests beliefs applied to one technology cannot be generalised to other systems. Additionally, the TRA and TPB are more complex compared to the TAM and require different reference groups and control variables to apply it across different context.

2. Social Variables

Another major difference between the three models is the presence of social variables. Davis. *et al* (1986) TAM model does not include any social variables and claims that social norms are not significant. However, studies suggest that social variables are important for explaining the variance in behavioural intention. The TRA and TPB, on the other hand include social variables as compared to the TAM. The idea that subjective norms are the key determinants of IT usage is still unclear and subject to huge debate. Davis *et al* (1986) and Matheison (1991) claims that there is not significant relationship between subjective norm and intention to use. However, Moore and Benbasat (1991) argue that for organisational settings subjective norm is an important determinant of IT usage.

3. Behavioural Control

The issue of perceived behavioural control (PBC) is another main difference between the three models. Perceived behavioural control refers to the resources or opportunities needed for a particular act. The TAM uses PEOU determinant for describing internal control factors but It ignores external control factors which might be the key determinants of technology acceptance. TPB, on the other hand identifies the important control variables (both internal and external) for each situation.

4. Measurement Instruments

Studies suggest that TAM has sound measurement instruments as compared to TPB and TRA because it simplifies the comparison of results across different studies. The TAM measurement scales are also claims to be highly reliable as compared to other technology acceptance frameworks.

5. Parsimony

Although research suggests all the three models are relatively parsimonious, the 5-variables TAM is more parsimonious and less complex to apply as compared to the 8-variables TBP and 6-variables TRA. Researchers claims that TPB is very complex to understand and difficult to apply as compared to TAM. The TAM with 5 constructs explain 36% of the variance in technology usage. When applying the models in practice, Parsimony plays a key role for full understanding of the phenomenon. Although TAM might have less explanatory power than TRA and TPB, it maintains high parsimonious power is less costly to apply in all contexts.

2.3 Section summary

Section one discussed and analysed the key models related to technology acceptance. The chapter reviewed four main theoretical frameworks and also explored previous studies concerning these models. The researcher will propose conceptual framework of internet banking acceptance based on these models. The chapter also conducted an in-depth analysis of the TAM and found that its fundamental constructs (PU and PEU) alone might not be adequate to explain and predict technology usage. The results from the above discussion indicate that TAM oversee the situation-specific factors, external factors and as well as the users' demographic characteristics that plays key role in the prediction of behaviour. Furthermore, TAM also fail to overlook other important factors such as perceived trust and risk that can play a key role in internet banking adoption. To overcome this limitation of the TAM, the subsequent chapter discusses the concept of trust and perceived risk in internet banking research which play a central role on understanding and predicting user behaviour to engage in online activities.

SECTION TWO:

Role of Trust in Internet Banking Acceptance

Introduction

Internet banking is growing at the speed of light across the globe and trust has been identified as the critical construct towards its acceptance. Consumer trust plays a key role in any commerce business, particularly in internet banking. This chapter will review the importance of customer trust in the acceptance of internet banking. The chapter will discuss the notions and definitions of internet trust. The chapter will also investigate various factors that affects customer's trust in internet banking. This will guide the researcher to develop a model of trust for internet banking acceptance for this study.

2.5 Definition of Trust

Prior to investigate the significance of trust in electronic finance, it is important to understand the meaning of trust and identify its antecedents and dimensions. Researchers have proposed numerous definitions of trust; however, there is a widespread disagreement about its characteristics and outcomes. Mayer *et al*, (2014) provides several reasons for this disagreement among the researchers: (1) every discipline view trust from its own perspective based on the nature of study being conducted; (2) the difficulty of defining the issue of trust; (3) failing to associate trust and risk; (4) failure to consider both the trustor and the trustee. Despite this disagreement on definition of trust, scholars have proposed two important elements that are common across almost every research and theory. They are: (1) risk and vulnerability perceived by the third party and (2) the perception that the trustee will behave in a positive manner towards the trusting party. From this, it can be deduced that trust is always based on user's positive expectations of the trustee (Mustafa, et al, 2009).

Trust is a vast and debatable subject and there is not a single definition of trust. Researchers have defined trust in several ways in different context, such as psychology, philosophy, science, management and marketing. Table 2.7 outlines the definitions of trust related to electronic commerce and online banking.

Table 2.7: Definitions of Trust		
Author	Research Area	Trust Definition
Sitkin and Ruth (1993)	Management	User's positive expectations regarding the outcome from trusting party.
Mayet et al (1995)	E-Commerce	User's willingness to accept risk and vulnerability based on their positive expectations that the trustee will behave in a positive manner irrespective of their ability to monitor or control the actions of the trustee.
Chervany and McKnight (2002)	Organisational Relationship	Trustor believes and willingness to depend on another party.
Chopra and Wallance (2002)	Electronic Environment	Individual's willingness to rely on trustee based on the confidence that trustee's actions will result in desirable outcomes.
Pavlou (2003)	E-Commerce	Trust is the consumers' willingness to become vulnerable to online retailers taking into consideration their characteristics.
Yousafzai et al. (2007)	Online Banking	A psychological state which enables the customer to conduct their banking activities on the internet expecting that banks will fulfil its obligations, irrespective of the fact that the customer will monitor and control the activities of the bank.
Corritore et al (2003)	Online Environment	Trustor's confident that his or her vulnerability will not be exploited in an online situation characterised by uncertainty and risk.
Law (2007)	Electronic Banking	The positive confidence of the user on the trustee's (online banking provider) ability and integrity.

Source: Various as indicated above

From the core definitions of trust above (e.g. Mayer *et al* 1995; Yousafzai *et al*, 2007; Law, 2007) applied to electronic commerce context, the current study defines trust on internet banking as “*The willingness of a customer to become vulnerable to the internet by conducting their banking services online based on their positive expectations that the bank and structural assurance of the bank's website.* This definition focuses on two important aspects of trust in context of internet banking. First, it emphasises on customer's trust on trustee (i.e. the bank), and secondly, captures customer's trust on the transaction medium (the internet).

From the above definitions and discussions, it can be deduced that customer will use internet banking services based on their evaluation of ability and integrity of the bank and reliability of the internet banking website. There are two main uncertainties, namely

environmental uncertainty and system uncertainty that might hinder consumer decision to adopt online banking services. However, when a bank is considered as highly trustworthy it will reduce customer uncertainty regarding the bank and its behaviour regarding electronic transaction process. Similarly, when a bank has security and privacy policies in places in its website, it will reduce user's system related uncertainties. For instance, high level of structural assurance on the bank's website will minimise the number of hackers and ultimately attract more customers to conduct online banking services.

2.6 Importance of Trust in Internet Banking

Trust plays a significant role in many social and economic interactions, particularly e-commerce, that involves high level of uncertainty and dependency. Since online transactions are subject to uncertainties, researchers state that trust is the critical factor that ensures the successful proliferation of e-commerce. According to Gefen and Straub (2003) the major factor that influences the successful proliferation of E-commerce, identified by Federal Administration and the Better Business Bureau and other major corporations is the people's trust in the internet vendor (i.e. the companies that sells goods and service over the internet). Similarly, Yousafzai et al, (2007) claims that in business-customer relationship over the internet, trust is the same as love in marriage: it binds them together to make strong and long-term relationship, increases the level of security, and reduces defences. Literature of internet banking have paid significant attention to the issue of trust and consider this as the key driver in the growth and adoption of such service. Gefen (2000) suggest that for retail banks to succeed in this highly competitive environment, they must build, confirm, and maintain trust with their customers.

The banking sector is highly associated with the issue of trust because of privacy and security concerns. In the electronic world, due to the uncertain nature of online environment and the absence of physical communication between the customer and staff, trust is of high importance. Teo and Liu (2005) state that it is the customer's privacy and security concerns that inhibit their decision to adopt and use internet banking services. When customers are not confident about the characteristics of their bank and the online environment, they will unlikely to use internet banking. Aladwani (2001) identified customer's trust as a highly important challenge for the adoption of online banking. (See Table 2.8).

Table 2.8: Future Challenges for Internet Banking

Online banking future challenges

Challenge	Rating of IT managers	Rating of senior management	Overall rank
Internet security	1	3	1
Customers' trust	2	1	2
The speed of service delivery	4	2	3
Customers' information privacy	3	6	4
Customers' awareness	5	9	5
Continuity of the service	6	10	6
Spread of computer use	8	4	7
Spread of Internet use	7	5	8
Difficulty of using online banking by some customers	12	7	9
Pricing of Internet service	10	8	10
Internet infrastructure in the country	11	12	11
Cost of maintaining the site	9	15	12
Lack of legal regulations	13	13	13
ISP monopoly	15	11	14
Difficulty of maintaining the site	14	14	15

Source: Aladwin (2001)

It is evident from table 2.8 that issues that are highly ranked are related to customer trust in internet banking. Customer trust in internet banking transactions are highly important because of the unsecure nature of the online environment, the uncertainty of the transaction medium and the extensive use of technology. As stated above, the online environment lacks face-to-face communication and other assurance mechanisms of which human are mainly dependent. Other important concerns such as reliability of the internet, privacy, security and fraud issues decreases customer perception of control and increase their hesitation towards the adoption of online banking. This provides the banks with unique challenges to find ways increase the perception of trust foster relationship with their customers.

According to Pavlia, (2009) the survival of banks mainly depends on its ability to encourage its consumers to bank online. Banks must have a trust-based collaboration process in place to build mutually valuable relationship with their online customers. Pavlia (2009) further claims that trust is the foundation of electronic banking and plays a crucial role to facilitate the interactions between the customers and the bank.

However, the way banks develop trust with their customer and its impact on internet banking is not yet well concluded. The issue of trust in online banking is a vast and debatable area of interest and the related literature have focused more on general issues of e-commerce. The next section explains the antecedents of online trust.

2.7 Factors Affecting Consumer Trust

If the concept of trust is an important aspect of E-commerce, then it should be a prime concern for E-businesses providers to understand the antecedents of this trust. Researchers have identified number of factors that affect consumer trust in electronic environment. These factors include characteristics of the online vendor, perceived security, perceived privacy, service quality, ease of use, legal frameworks and customer service. The table 2.9 below provides a compelling list of factors that contribute to customers' trust in electronic commerce.

Table 2.9: Review of Research on Factors Contributing to Online Trust

Study <i>Topic of Analysis</i>	Factors Introduced	Findings
Jarvenpaa et al (1999) <i>Antecedents of trust in Global virtual team</i>	1. Ability 2. Integrity 3. Benevolence 4. Propensity to trust	
Kini and Coobineh (1998) <i>Role of Trust in Adopting E-commerce</i>	1. Personality 2. Task 3. System Security	
Cheskin (1999) <i>Trustworthiness Elements</i>	1. Safeguard Assurance 2. Vendors' Reputation 3. Website Security 4. Ease of Navigation 5. Order Fulfilment 6. Website Design	The first and foremost important step in building trust is to make sure that that user's personal information is safeguarded. Vendors' characteristics and customer past experience also leads towards the positive development of customer trust.
Dayel et al, (1999) <i>Factors of Online Trust</i>	1. State-of-art Security 2. Merchant Legitimacy 3. Customer Control 4. Fulfilment 5. Consumer Collaboration	In virtual environment, consumers are looking beyond the functional benefits of the products (such as quality and price) and services. Security and privacy are the main concerns when shopping online.
Hoffman, et al (1999) <i>How to build online trust?</i>	1. Perceived Privacy 2. Perceived Security	Customers' lack of control in the virtual environment negatively affects their privacy and security perception which, in turn, leads to low level of trust.
Gefen (2000) <i>The role of familiarity in establishing Trust</i>	1. Familiarity 2. Trust Disposition	Familiarity and trust on an internet vendor positively influences the

		consumer intention to engage in online shopping.
Gefen and Straub (2000) <i>Managing customer trust and B2C relation</i>	1. Information Richness 2. Perceived Social Presence	Social presence positively affects customer's perception regarding online trust and this in turn motivates to conduct online transactions.
Palmer et al, (2000) <i>How to Improve online trust?</i>	_____	The primary factors that improve online trust are the privacy statement and third-party involvement.
Javernpaa et al, (2000) <i>What influences consumer's trust?</i>	1. Perceived Reputation 2. Perceived Size	Differences in reputation and size affect how consumer assess the trustworthiness of e-stores. It also affects their perception of risk and willingness to use the e-store.
Schneiderman (2000) <i>Improving customer online trust</i>	_____	Customer testimonials, past experience, easy to locate and read security and privacy policies and trust third party's seal improve online trust.
Smith et al, (2000) <i>Indicators of online trust</i>	1. Community 2. Selection of items 3. Privacy 4. Search Engine	Trust is the key factor to electronic commerce concerning the risks related to the customer privacy and security imposed by the internet.
Urban et al, (2000) <i>How online trust is improved?</i>	_____	For improving online trust e-business must provide reliable services, unbiased information and keep promises.
Warrington et al, (2000) <i>How to gain competitive advantage by building online trust?</i>	_____	Privacy policy, security policy, extended warranty, recognition of company and website appearance can build trust. As the time goes trust improves and this leads to favourable perceptions and customer loyalty.
Lee and Turban (2001) <i>Models of trust for customer online shopping.</i>	1. Perceived Trustworthiness 2. Trustworthiness of Transaction Medium 3. Situational and infrastructural factors Individual's own propensity to trust	Trustworthiness of the internet vendor, trust on transaction medium (Internet technical competence and performance level) and contextual factors (i.e. security effectiveness) are the primary factors that influences consumer trust.
Fogg et al, (2001) <i>Drivers of website credibility.</i>	_____	Ease of use, expertise trustworthiness are the main factors that affect website credibility.
Methew et al, (2001) <i>How to enhance online trust</i>	_____	Product warranty and return policy, credit card loss assurance, ability to contact customer services, and most importantly the availability to friendly user-interface enhances online trust.

Belanger et al, (2002)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Privacy Statements 2. Privacy Seals 3. Security Features 4. Security Seals 	For online vendor to gain customer satisfaction and grow, they must not compromise on security and privacy concern.
Bhattachjee (2002) <i>Individuals trust in online vendor</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Familiarity 2. Benevolence 3. integrity 4. Ability 	Trust has three core constructs: ability, benevolence and integrity. Trust affect consumer willingness to interact with an online firm.
Gefen (2002) <i>Relationship between trust and customer loyalty</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ability 2. Benevolence 3. Integrity 	Ability, integrity and benevolence are the key constructs of trustworthiness.
McKnight and Chervany (2002)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Structured Assurance 2. Perceived Quality 3. Perceived Reputation 	Online trust is built on the ability and integrity of the online vendor and trusting intentions, that is the customer willingness to depend.
Mukherjee and Nath (2003) <i>Trust in online relationship banking</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication 2. Share values 3. Opportunistic Behaviour 	Shared values, security, privacy and reputation can act as the main accelerators of trust and thus build commitments between consumers and online vendor.
Ratnasingham and Pavlov (2003) <i>Technology trust in e-commerce</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Best Business Practices 2. Security structures 	Transaction integrity, authentication, best business practices, confidentiality, and non-repudiation and the primary antecedents of online trust.
Gefen et al, (2004) <i>Cultural diversity and trust in E-government Adoption</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Propensity to Trust 2. Cultural Similarity 	Propensity of individuals to trust perceived cultural similarity establishes trust and this trust leads to usefulness of IT.
Ganguly et al, (2010) <i>Influence of website characteristics on trust in online travel portals</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Social Presence 2. Security 3. Two Way Communication 4. Self -Efficacy 	Higher perception of privacy and security in the website results in higher customer trust. Constructed communication with online travel portals results in customer trust.
Eid (2011) <i>Determinants of customer satisfaction and trust in E-commerce</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Information Quality 2. User Interface Quality 3. Perceived Security 4. Perceived Privacy 	Perceived security and privacy leads to customer satisfaction and trust and this, in turn, leads to customer loyalty.
Srinivasan (2013) <i>Role of trust in e-business success</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ease of placing orders 2. Order Confirmation 3. Order Tracking 4. Post-Sales Service 	Ease of placing orders and order tracking significantly contribute for enhancing transaction trust.

Source: Various as indicated above

The above table presented number of factors that contribute toward the establishment of trust in e-commerce. Some of these factors are more critical than the others in building trust. For instance, for Hoffman et al, (1999) the issue of security and privacy directly influence online trust. They claim that when customer have adequate control over the actions of online vendor if influences his/her perception of privacy and security. They also argue that consumers will only consider the additional web features, such reputation, ease of use and familiarity, after the privacy and security mechanisms are in place by the online vendor. In the early adoption stages of online banking many people shied away from online transfers simple because of security concern.

Other authors view online trust in the light of past-experience. For example, Jarvenpaa et al, (2000) suggest that in the early stages of technology adoption, trust building is more dependent on the performance of technology but in the later stages trust have more to do with differences in online vendors' implementation of internet technology. Similarly, Urban et al, (2000) claims that the quantity, quality and timelessness of information can also contribute towards the enhancement of trust.

Another key factor that contribute towards online trust is the technical competence and performance of the transaction medium (i.e. internet) and the underlying characteristics that govern that medium. Ong and Lin (2015) has identified number of performance measures that can be used to test the competency of the transaction medium including download speed, reliability, availability and connectivity. However, reliability of the medium is the primary concern for customer when transmitting personal and financial information over the internet (Hsiao, *et al.* 2010). This is because there is always the risk of unauthorised interrupting the information. Customers' perception of the technological competency of the internet plays important role in their behaviour towards internet banking.

Furthermore, Pavlou (2002) suggest that customer trust is jointly influenced by trustworthiness of the online-vendor, trustworthiness of the internet, individual's trust propensity and other contextual factors. Kim, Prabhakar and Park (2009) suggests six factors that enhance customer perception regarding the online vendor's trustworthiness. They are: safeguard assurance, reputation of marketers, the professionalism of the website, robust order fulfilment, ease of navigation and website technology. However, some authors argue that although the trustworthiness of the online merchant is important, it is not adequate for an online transaction to take place. Trustworthiness of the transaction medium (i.e. internet) is also important.

Finally, two-way communication between the customer and online vendor significantly contributes towards the establishment of trust between both parties (Krauter and Faullant, 2008). E-business must give customer the option to communicate with online store in case of any issues arising with the order.

2.8 Trust Model for Internet Banking

The present study proposes a trust model for internet banking acceptance based on trust literature discussed above. The model is shown in Figure 5-1 below. This model of trust will be integrated with the main conceptual model for this study which will be developed later in chapter five. The present study hypothesises that customer trust on internet banking is influenced by two main factors:

1. Banks' Trustworthiness
2. Structural Assurance of Bank's Website

The model also suggests that perceived risk in the online transactions will negatively affect customer intention to use internet banking. In sum, online trust and perceived risk jointly influence customer's intention to use online banking. This is clearly shown in the diagram below.

Figure 2.9: Model of Trust for Internet Banking

Source: This Research

2.8.1 Trust → Perceived Risk → Intention to use Internet Banking

Perceived risk is defined as the consumer's perception of the uncertainty and the possible negative consequences of engaging in a particular activity (Khan, 2014 p.141).

Perceived risk plays a vital role in e-commerce as compared to traditional commerce due to its uncertain nature and uncertainty of the global internet medium. As stated by Gefen *et al*, (2003) the concept of risk commands as a central role in the field of electronic commerce.

2.8.2 Perceived Bank Trustworthiness

According to McKnight *et al*, (1998) the amount of trust that a trustor will put on the trustee is mainly based on the positive characteristics and attributes of the trustee. In online banking environment, customer conduct sensitive banking transactions solely based on their level of trust on the trustworthiness of the bank. Bank trustworthiness is defined as the customer's perception about how trustworthy the trusting party (i.e. the bank) is. Perceived trustworthiness is the characteristics of the trustee and is based on the number of desirable attributes. Literature on trust suggests several characteristics of the trustee to evaluate their level of trustworthiness. However, Mayer *et al*, (1995), Lee and Turban (2001) and Yousafzai *et al* (2003) proposes three main elements of trustworthiness, i.e. ability, integrity and benevolence that are frequently used in the trust literature. They suggest that when a company possess these three traits consumer will perceive it as a reliable exchange partner and will put their trust in it. The current study thus will use these three main characteristics in order to assess the trustworthiness of banks that provide internet banking services.

Ability is defined as the group of skills, competence and characteristics of the trustee that will influence customer trust (Mayer *et al*, 1995). In the context of online banking, perceived ability is the customers' perception that the bank has the necessary skills and competence to provide electronic banking services coherent with their expectations.

Integrity is the customer's belief that the trustee will adhere the agreements and fulfil all the obligations that are acceptable to the customer. In internet banking context, integrity refers to the bank's characteristics such as honesty, creditability, consistency and reliability.

Finally, **Benevolence** is defined by Mayer *et al*, (1995) as "the extent to which a trustee (bank) will do good things to the trustor (customer). Benevolence belief reduces uncertainties and introduces faith in the customer and bank relationship.

Knoll and Gill (2011) states that bank's ability integrity and benevolence plays a crucial role in influencing customer decision to bank online. This is mainly because these three attributes reduce customer perception of uncertainty regarding online transactions. For instance, positive belief about bank's will ensure the customer that the bank has the necessary skills and competence to effectively deliver internet banking services. Similarly, the integrity and benevolence of the bank will assure the customer that the bank is trustworthy and will adhere to the principles when dealing with online banking customers.

2.8.3 Structural Assurance of the Bank's Website

Bank's trustworthiness is not adequate for trusting relationship, customer trust is also largely relied on the structural assurance of the internet medium. Structural assurance of the internet medium is defined by McKnight et al, (2002) as "the belief that the bank's website has the required protective legal (e.g. privacy and security policies, third party assurance) and technological structures (e.g. firewall and anti-virus) that ensures the customer that the vendor's website is safe for financial transactions. In online banking context, structural assurance of the transaction medium (internet) plays a key role, since it reduces consumers' uncertainty related to system errors and security and privacy policies. As stated by Akhlaq and Ahmed (2013) such protection assures the customers that it is safe and secure from any unauthorised activities and financial loss. Considering the nature of electronic finance that is highly sensitive, banks must have maximum assurance in place for consumers to trust them (Cheung and Lee, 2006). Following this discussion, the current study proposes that high structural assurance of the bank's website positively influence consumer trust and promotes their intention towards internet banking services. This is because when customer perceive that they are protected by regulatory frameworks, it is likely that they will trust the bank website to conduct their financial transactions.

2.9 Section Summary

Section two discussed the role and importance of trust in the internet banking acceptance. The chapter accomplished two main objectives; first, it reviewed the main factors that affect customer trust; and secondly, the chapter proposed a trust model for internet banking acceptance for this study. This is noted from the discussion that the trust dilemma plays a key role in the acceptance of internet banking and helps the bank to transform a potential customer to an active customer.

SECTION THREE:

Internet Banking Research

Introduction

This section of the chapter aims to review the general concepts related internet banking acceptance. The chapter will start by the presenting the basic definitions and types of electronic banking followed by the benefits and challenges of this service. Since this study focuses on the customer behaviour perspective, the present chapter will mainly discuss the determinants and factors of online banking adoption. Most importantly, the chapter will also discuss the critical role of demographic variables in internet banking acceptance.

2.10 What is Internet Banking?

The term “internet banking” is a very broad concept and can be described in many ways. It is also called online banking and electronic banking and can be delivered through several distribution channels. In simple terms, internet banking is defined as the provision of traditional banking services such as accessing accounts, depositing check, transfer funds and buying financial products or services through the internet using a computer, mobile phone or telephone (Eriksson, Kerem and Nilsson, 2005). This service is very convenient that allows customers to access and manage their financial information electronically and remotely via the bank’s website 24/7 without having to visit the bank branch.

The rapid growth in internet and computer technology is fuelling the use of online banking across the globe and this is expected to rise in the future (Zuccaro and Savard, 2010). Invention of technologies such as ATM and credit cards in 1960 followed by internet banking services in 1990 and now mobile banking have fundamentally changed the banking industry and how banks carry out their daily activities. According to British Banker’s Association report (2016) there are 4.3 million internet banking logins per day in the UK. Similarly, according to a report from eight major high street in the UK, the number

2.11 Benefits of Internet Banking

Internet banking provides numerous benefits and advantages to both the customers and the banks. Below is the detailed discussion of the advantages of internet banking.

2.11.1 Benefits for the Banks

The main benefits of online banking to banks are efficiency enhancement, cost savings, reaching new segments of population, providing better customer service and many more.

Among these, the main motivation for banks to promote the use of online banking is cost savings (Bradley and Stewart, 2002). With internet banking, banks are able to minimize their expenses and make substantial savings. A survey conducted by Rawashdeh, (2009) concluded that the running cost of online banking is 10% to 15% of the total bank's revenue compared to 50% to 60% of the branch-based banking. Similarly, Robinson (2000) found out that the cost of online banking transaction is significantly lower than the branch-based transaction. The average cost of online transaction via the internet is \$0.01 compared to an ATM transaction which costs \$0.47, a check transaction \$ 0.97 and a branch transaction \$1.07. These savings can then be passed on to the customers in terms of high rates on deposits and lower rates on loans which will provide the bank with a competitive advantage.

The second key advantage of internet banking for banks is that it strengthens the relationship between the customer and the bank (Yiu et al, 2007). Internet banking enables the banks to offer banking services to its consumers 24/7 in their office or home which creates customer loyalty. In this highly dynamic and competitive environment, banks must provide customers with personalised and customised service to keep them engaged, capture their intention and build an online relationship (Mols, 2000).

Thirdly, the provision of online banking creates a barrier for customer exiting. Sheshunoff (2000) claims once a customer become a full-time member with the bank, then that customer will not move to another financial institution. However, this assumption might not be accurate in western countries, particularly the UK and USA where banks facilitate the switching of their customers' accounts to other financial institution because the law permits it.

Apart from these, the other main benefits of online banking for banks are the greater customer loyalty, greater and quicker reach to market, ability to understand customers' needs and the ability to market new products and services to customers quickly and efficiently.

2.11.2 Benefits for the customers

The emergence of internet banking is providing the customers with variety of benefits and opportunities. Among these benefits, the convenience of being able to access accounts from anywhere and ability to conduct financial transaction without having to visit the bank branch are the key motivating factors for customer to adopt internet banking. Below are some of the major advantages of online banking but are not limited to these:

Customer's Convenience: This is the most important benefits of internet banking that outweigh all the shortcoming. Online banking increases customer convenience, because they do not have to travel to the bank branch to carry out basic banking activities like paying bills, transferring funds, applying for loans and also waiting in long queues (Ekin and Polatoglu, 2001). Online banking can be accessed 24 hours a day and 365 days a years where real-time account information is available to the customers at the touch of few buttons. Apart from this, though the use of online baking it has also become very easy and convenient to update and maintain their account information without having to visit the branch. A US survey cited by Hiltunen et al. (2004) found that convenience was the driving force behind customers' usage of internet banking services.

Saves Time: One of the major benefit of internet banking is the saving of time and fast and accurate transaction (Karjaluo, 2002). With the adoption of internet banking, it is no longer required to wait in long queues at the bank branch.

Mobility: Another key advantage of online banking is that it can be performed from anywhere in the world as far as the customer is connected to the internet. Even if the customer is away from business premises or on vocation, they can still manage their daily banking needs. More interestingly, Banks have created mobile apps which makes it very easy and convenient for both personal and corporate customer to conduct their financial transactions smoothly.

Services: Internet Technology has also made is very easier for customers to access to variety of additional services which might not be available through traditional branch banking. These services include functional budgeting, financial planning capabilities, investment analysis, loan calculators, and equity trading platforms which are available online on the most major bank's website.

Transfer money between account: Online banking allows the customer make payments and transfer money between accounts more quickly and easily. It is more convenient

than using telephone banking or branch banking. Similarly, internet banking also allows the customer to even make international payments in a matter of seconds.

Although internet banking offers several benefits to banks and their customer, people still feel resistant to use this service. This is mainly because of security and privacy concerns. Therefore, it is important for banks to keep close relationship with their customers and make them aware of the benefits of this new service and this is what the aim of this study is.

2.12 Factors influencing Users of internet banking

According to Pikkarainen *et al.* (2004) researchers have identified numerous factors that influence the adoption of this service. Most of these factors have been developed from previous research studies and models such as TAM, TPB and Innovation Diffusion Theory. For instance, Jahangir and Begum (2008) have identified four main factors that positively influence customer's decision to use internet banking in Bangladesh. These factors are: Perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, privacy concerns and customer attitude, which are directly related to the adoption of e-banking. Similarly, in Turkey, Polatuglo and Ekin (2009) found that relative advantage, trialability, observability, complexity, and compatibility influenced the adoption of internet banking. In the same line, Chung (2006) claims that the intention to use internet banking is mainly determined website security and PEU. by perceived ease of use and perceived web security. In addition, Pikkarainen et al (2004) suggest that PU, PEU along with privacy and security concerns are the key factors related to the adoption of online banking in Finland. Furthermore, Chong et al (2010) states that trustworthiness and positive characteristics of the bank also reduces customer's perception of risk associated with online banking.

Studies also suggest that convenience and efficiency of the internet banking delivery are the main factors that influence users' decision to adopt this service (Bruno, 2003). A survey based on US online banking customers cited by Kolodinsky and Hogarth (2004) revealed that convenience is the main motivator for internet banking adoption in terms of 24/7 access and time saving. Apart from convenience, the speed of transaction, better access to information, and better communication are some of the main motivational factors for customers to use internet banking.

Other important factors that may influence consumer adoption decision are the issues of security, privacy, trust and risk (Mortimer et al, 2015). Recent survey cited by Al-

Ajam and Md Nor (2015) found that customer fear regarding the financial transaction security can inhibit the adoption of online banking service. As per Malhotra and Singh (2007) internet banking consumers are more concerned about the privacy and security issues than the non-internet banking customer because of the nature of the service. Apart from security issue, the concept of trust has also been found a significant factor in the adoption decision of internet banking services.

Several studies have also integrated more than one technology acceptance models in order to investigate these factors.

To find more factors that influence user's acceptance of online banking, researchers have integrated more than one technology acceptance models. For instance, Yaghoubi & Bahmani (2010) proposed a theoretical model based on TAM and TPB in order to investigate the factor that affect the adoption of online banking in Iran. Their result revealed that PBC and PU mainly affects the usage of electronic banking among customers. Similarly, Ok and Shon (2006) encompassed TPB and TRA to predict users' intention to accept internet banking in South Korea. The results revealed that perceived behavioural control and attitude plays a central role in affecting user's decision to adopt online banking. The study also found that both theories, TRA and TPB, were very effective in studying the behavioural intention of customers. In the same line, Yiu et al (2007) adapted the TAM model and found that perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, personal innovativeness and perceived risk directly influence the diffusion of internet banking.

Another important factor that plays a key role in the adoption decision of e-banking is the issue of trust. Research relating to online banking have paid increased attention to the issue of trust. For example, Suh and Han (2012) investigated the role of trust in the acceptance of online banking in South Korea. Their study found that greater trustworthiness of the bank motivates customers to conduct online banking with the same bank. Additionally, Dimitriadis and Kyrezis (2008) found that reputation of the bank and trust in the service delivery are the main determinants of electronic banking services.

Finally, demographic characteristics among the users also influence the adoption decision of internet banking. As per Polasik and Wisniewski (2009) customer's demographic characteristics act as the key determinants of internet banking adoption in developed economies. This view is supported by Yousafzai et al (2006) who claims that demographic variables moderate between perceived usefulness and actual use and

perceived ease of use and actual use of internet banking. In parallel with the study of Yousafzai et al (2006), Ndubisi and Sinti (2006) state that internet banking is mostly adopted by young people in Botswana and highlighted that people over the age of 65 are mostly reluctant to use this service. The detailed discussion of the role of demographic variables and personal characteristics in internet banking is explained later in this chapter. Table 2.10 summarizes the important factors that influence the adoption of internet banking identified by previous studies.

Table 2.10: Factors for the Adoption of Internet Banking							
Study	Perceived Usefulness	Perceived Ease of Use	Risk	Trust	Attitude	Privacy and Security	Customer Demographics
Polatoghu and Ekin (2001)	√		√				√
Suh and Han (2002)	√	√		√			
Singh (2004)		√					
Lee and Laforit (2005)							√
Eriksson et al (2005)	√	√		√			
Yousafzai et al (2005)	√	√	√	√		√	√
Cheng et al (2006)	√	√				√	
Awamleh and Fernandis (2006)	√		√				
Ramayah et al (2006)	√						√
Jahangir and Begum (2008)	√	√		√	√		
Lee (2009)	√		√		√	√	
Mohammad (2012)	√	√			√		

Source: Various as stated above

2.13 Factors influencing non-users of Internet banking

Although the usage of internet banking is growing rapidly, there are several underlying factors that inhibit its diffusion among the customers. Studies have identified number of factors influencing non-adopters of internet banking. The most important factor that inhibit the adoption of online banking is the customer's concern relating to security and privacy issues (Black et al, 2002). A survey based on Australian customers cited by Kesharwani and Bisht (2012) found that security and privacy concerns play a critical role in affecting individuals' decision to accept or reject internet banking. Similarly, Mzoughi and M'Sallem (2013) claims that security and privacy are the customers' subjective expectations about the financial loss due to uncertain environment of internet media. Online banking contains many vulnerabilities that can lead to not only monetary loss, but also violate customers' privacy.

Gerrard et al (2006) have identified eight factors that inhibit consumer intention to use online banking in Singapore. Among these, two major factors are customer's perception of risk and lack of perceived need. Other six factors are: lack of experience with the service, lack of human touch, inaccessibility, IT fatigue and Inertia. In the same line, Shanmugam et al, (2015) conducted another study in Greece and found that difficulty of using the service, lack of information, and fear of changes in the banking sector negatively affect consumer intention to use electronic banking services. The study also revealed that cost relating to internet banking had little impact on individual's adoption decision.

Another important factor that causes non-adoption of internet banking is the concept of perceived risk (Yiu et al, 2007). Yiu et al (2007) added two constructs to the original TAM namely; perceived risk and personal innovativeness. His results confirmed that these two factors positively influence consumers' decision to accept internet banking services. Furthermore, individual's perception of financial risk is also considered as the main reason behind the non-adoption of electronic banking.

Several studies have also found that customers do not accept and use internet banking because of the complexity of difficulty of the service. (Lassar et al., 2005; Lee et al., 2005; Gerrad et al., 2006). Researchers claim that complexity of using a technology negatively affect user's intention towards its adoption. Technologies such as online banking, ATM and mobile banking are not accepted by customers, particularly by elderly individuals, because they consider them as highly technological complex

services (Gerrard et al, 2006). According to Cunningham and Devlin (2009), high level of technology complexity results in lower level of perceived ease of use for customers, and hence lowering the customers' behavioural intentions to adopt e-banking services. Researchers have also hypothesized that customers might not be using internet banking services due to pricing concerns (Sayar & Wolfe, 2007). They argue that for customers to be able to use online banking they must have access to two things: Access to a laptop/personal computer and access to internet connection. Both services require costs to customers. Moreover, in some countries, customers are charged in the form of service tax for services such as online bill payments, online shopping or booking tickets for holiday.

Other most important factors inhibiting the diffusion of internet banking are lack of user-friendly technology and customer demand, lack of suitable skills, high initial set up costs (Durkin, 2004). Demographic and personal factors can also play a role in delaying the diffusion of internet banking channels. For example, some customers might not conduct online banking transactions due to low income, low education level or the lack of information about this channel.

Recent studies have segmented non-adopters of internet banking into three different categories. These groups of non-adopters are proposers, opponents and rejecters. The rejecters are much more intense as compared to proposers Vol. 28 (5), pp.622-636. and opponents and shows high resistance to internet banking regarding risk, security tradition and image.

The table below presents number of factors that influence non-adoption of internet banking. These factors are based on previous studies.

Table 2.11: Factors for Non- Adoption of Internet Banking

Study	E I	Internet banking services awareness	Usefulness	Triability	Compatibility	Ease of Use	Individual Characteristics	Accessibility	Computer Self- efficacy	Behavioural Control
Sathye (1999)	√	√	√							
Tan & Teo(2000)	√		√	√	√					
Wang et al. (2003)			√			√			√	
Pikkarainen et al. (2004)			√							
Hanakul and Fink (2005)			√				√			√
Abu Shanab (2005)							√		√	
Lassar et al (2005)							√			
Nor (2005)	√		√	√	√		√			√
Gerrard et al. (2006)					√					

Ndubisi & Sinthi (2006)			√			√	√		√	
Al Hajri (2008)			√			√				
Nor et al. (2008)	√					√				
Alam et al. (2009)			√							

Source: Many, as stated above

Note: EI = Environmental Uncertainty (Privacy and security concerns, Trust and Risk)

2.14 Comparison of Users and Non-users of Internet Banking

Previous studies have compared the adopters and non-adopters of internet banking on many occasions. Awamleh and Fernandes (2006) conducted a study to investigate the key factors affecting customer's intention to use internet banking in United Arab Emirates. The study found significant differences between the adopters and non-adopters of internet banking. Adopters of online banking were mainly influenced by factors like perceived usefulness, convenience, accessibility and relative advantage while non-users were influenced by perceived risk. Ozdemir et al (2008) also found a major difference between the adopters and non-adopters in Turkey. His study found that for adopters, internet banking is friendlier, less risky and more useful as compared to non-adopters. Similarly, Laforet and Li (2005) studied the consumer perception of internet banking in China and found that users of this service have more confidence on system reliability, whereas non-users hold negative view of the service and do not conduct sensitive financial transaction over the internet. In the same line, Kaabachi, Mrad and Petrescu (2017) studied internet banking acceptance in South Africa and found that lack of knowledge, cost and time consumption are the main inhibiting factors of internet banking adoption.

Demographic variables and customer characteristics are another main difference between the user and non-users of internet banking. For instance, as per Koksai (2016) adopters of internet banking are mostly middle-age male individuals who are more technology oriented and view the positive side of new technology. However, non-adopters of internet banking are most likely elderly people who are always oriented to traditional channels of banking and feel hesitant to use new technology.

To summarise, it is noted from the above discussion that users and non-users of internet banking have different attitude towards the same channel. Factors that influence users of internet banking are different for non-users of this service. Therefore, it is very critical for financial institution to identify the factors that influence the users and non-users of internet banking in order to come up with effective marketing strategies. Most particularly, the banks must identify the reasons for non-adoption or discontinuation of online banking and then work on that to be able to provide a better service and increase its customer base and market share. Furthermore, banks must have the knowledge of key customer-specific factors of internet banking adoption in order to enhance customer experience.

2.15 Demographic Characteristics and Adoption of Internet Banking

As discussed in the above chapter, technology developments will not bring any benefits to the table unless the customers both adopt and use them. Although banks have invested substantial resources in internet banking technologies, key factors upon which the growth of internet banking largely depends have been undermined. The growth and success of internet banking mainly depends on the technology readiness of the intended users. Therefore, it is extremely important for banks to understand how and why customers develop different perceptions about internet banking and as well as the important role of demographic characteristics in the adoption decision process. As per Riquelme and Rios (2002), the fast-paced technological developments in financial sector is requiring banks to be able to predict customers' innovative tendencies. The next section will investigate the effects of demographic variables, such as gender, age and education level on internet banking adoption decision.

2.15.1 Role of Gender and Age

Research has noted that gender and age have a major influence on customers' perceptions and behavioural intentions (Venkatesh and Morris, 2000). As per Riquelme and Rios (2010) demographic characteristics of individuals often influences perceptions of technology, particularly online behaviour. Therefore, it is important to study and understand the key role of these factors in internet banking acceptance. So, if decision to adopt technology-based products and services are based on demographic characteristics, such as gender and age, then it is very critical for banks to design appropriate marketing strategies and campaigns. However, there are number of competing studies that suggest that the demographic factors are less important as compared to the characteristics of technology itself in determining user adoption and rejection of new technology. Other researches have adopted a user-centric view and claims that the demographic characteristics, particularly age and gender, plays a key role to influence users' decision to accept or reject new technology. The present study proposes that three key demographic variables i.e., gender, age and education level act as the key moderating variables that affect the TAM relationship (See figure 4.3).

Studies on age differences suggest that customers' age significantly influences their choice of internet banking adoption. Younger customers are more optimistic towards the acceptance of technology-based products and services, such as internet banking (Lee and Lee's, 2000). Shiraz (2014) supports this view by adding that younger groups

are more technology-savvy and have high propensity towards the acceptance of internet banking. Older people, on the other hand, tend to have a negative view of new technologies and feel reluctant to accept and use them. Research on technology acceptance suggest that individuals with increased age are less optimistic about new technologies as compared to younger aged groups.

Regarding the gender, studies suggest that there are differences in the way males and females perceive different technologies. Sun and Zhang (2006) claims that the adoption and usage of internet banking depends on the gender of the individual. However, recent surveys suggest in today's highly technological environment, gender gap towards the acceptance of new technology had decreased and does not have direct effect on user's behavioural intention.

2.15.2 Role of Education

Research on technology acceptance suggest that level of education also plays an important role in influencing customer's attitude towards new technology (Fareed et al, 2009). Several studies have indicated that individuals with high level of education tend to have high propensity towards technology innovations, such as internet banking (Mustafa, 2011; Al Somali et al, 2008; Yeung et al, 2006). Naeem et al, (2012) asserted that users with high education level has always high propensity towards accepting new technology.

2.15.3 TAM and the Role of Demographics

As discussed in chapter 2, several theoretical models have been proposed by numerous authors that conceptualize the process by which new technologies are adopted. The Technology Acceptance Model was found to be the widely used and most tested model of technology acceptance as compared to other theoretical perspectives. The Technology Acceptance Model hypothesizes that individual's acceptance of new technology is determined by two main constructs: PU and PEU. TAM focuses solely on system specific constructs that explains how technology attributes, such as PU and PEU, affects individual's perceptions of new technology. TAM ignores other important environmental and personality characteristics that might play a vital role in consumer's adoption decision (Greene and Norbury, 2011). Hence, it is argued that customer's demographic characteristics, such gender, age and education level influences the potential acceptance of new technology. The present study propose that customer's demographics serve as a key moderator in the relationship between consumer's

perceptions and behavioural intentions. Figure 2.10 below shows how customer’s demographic moderates the relationship between TAM constructs and behavioural intention. Relationship between perceived risk, trust and intention is taken from trust model of internet banking in section 2.

Figure 2.10: *Role of Demographic Characteristics*
Source: *This Research*

It can be deduced from the above diagram that demographic characteristics of individuals does play a role in their decision to adopt internet banking. The three demographic dimensions, such as age, gender and education level plays a vital role in user’s adoption of new technology. For instance, customer’s technology adoption is determined by the perception of ease of use, specifically the degree to which the internet banking website is effortless and well-structured. Referring to the three demographic dimensions, younger customers may not pay much attention to ease of use because they are always willing to accept new technology, and in fact prefer, to “figure it out” themselves any challenges they may encounter. Conversely, older customers who are less innovative may want or need extra advice, guidance, and support in order to use internet banking services. Similarly, Ho and Ko (2008) noted that internet banking technology are not free from great risks, uncertainty and imprecision. Younger and

more educated individuals do not fear the technology, are more prone to risks and are able to cope with high level of uncertainty (Parasuraman, 2000). These individuals will develop more positive intentions towards the use of online banking.

Summary of section 1, 2 and 3

A systematic and critical literature of internet banking acceptance was conducted in the above chapters to propose a model of internet banking for this study. Chapter two discussed and compared the main theoretical frameworks of user acceptance of technology and found that TAM is the most powerful and parsimonious as compared to other technology acceptance models. However, it was also noted from the discussion that the PU and PEU constructs of TAM are not enough to reflect upon the internet banking acceptance and suggestion for additional variables was made. Chapter three analysed the important role of trust and risk in the acceptance of internet banking. The chapter concluded that the concept of trust is a serious contributor to the technology acceptance behaviour. The present chapter examined the moderating role of user's demographic characteristics and technology readiness on technology acceptance behaviour. It was also noted that banks must take individual differences into account which will help them to predict who will be the user of this new technology (Internet Banking).

The subsequent chapter will shed light on the UK banking sector.

SECTION FOUR:

Internet Banking in the UK

2.16 Introduction

The primary purpose of this chapter is to provide a brief background of the UK banking industry and most importantly the internet banking trends. The chapter will provide a brief overview of UK banking sector and will shed light on its competitive landscape. The chapter will also focus on history of internet banking in the UK, and its rapid developments over the past two decades. Finally, the chapter will pay attention towards the internet banking adoption of UK customers and the factors that affect their adoption decision.

2.17 An Overview of the UK Banking Industry

According to BBA (2016) the UK banking industry is the largest in Europe and 4th largest in the world. The sector comprises of both building societies and banks and collectively known as UK monetary financial institutions – MFIs. The banking sector is the major contributor to the country's economic growth. As of January 2015, the industry employed approximately 1.1 million people across the country, with banks directly employing around 400,000 people. Currently, the banking industry represent around 7.9 of the country's GDP. The banking industry in the UK has grown significantly over the past few years. The UK banking market can be grouped into six broad categories:

1. **Large National Banks:** These banks are the main service providers of both personal and business banking and provides services such as current accounts, mortgages, credit cards, savings, and other personal banking services. There are currently five large banks in the UK that have national coverage called (the “**Big Five**”). These banks are; Barclays plc, HSBC Bank plc, Lloyds Banking Group, also include Halifax and Royal Bank of Scotland, NatWest Bank and Santander UK plc (Bank of England, 2017).
2. **Challenger Banks:** These are smaller lending institutions owned by its members that provide banking and other financial services, especially mortgage lending and savings to customer in the UK. However, today majority of these offer retail banking products, such as credit cards and current accounts. Main building societies in the UK are Nationwide Building Society, Yorkshire Building Society, Nottingham Building Society etc.

3. **Building Societies:** These are smaller lending institutions owned by its members that provide banking and other financial services, especially mortgage lending and savings to customer in the UK. However, today majority of these offer retail banking products, such as credit cards and current accounts. Main building societies in the UK are Nationwide Building Society, Yorkshire Building Society, Nottingham Building Society etc.
4. **Credit Unions:** Credit Unions are smaller lending institutions than building societies and are owned by members. These organisations provide services to those customers who are unable to access retail banking product through high street banks.
5. **Monoline Product Providers:** These providers full range of retail banking services but rather focus on offering specific products, such as credit cards.
6. **Other Lenders:** These organisations include other types of financial service providers, such as payday lenders, specialist mortgage lenders and other online specialists.

Among these, the Big Five (Barclays, HSBC, Lloyds Group, NatWest and Santander) represent 85% of the personal and business banking and 57% of the mortgage market in the UK (Statista, 2016). These are the main banks that have significant national presence and established customer base.

2.17.1 Main Players of the Industry (The Big Five)

As stated above, the UK retail and commercial banking market is dominated by five major banks, called the “Big Five”. These are: Barclays, HSBC, Lloyds Group, NatWest and Santander. These banks manage over 85% of the UK current and business accounts and employ around 560,000 people (BBA, 2017). These are the leading UK high street banks that offers a selection of online banking, mortgages, personal loans, credit cards, savings, business loans, currents accounts and many more.

The table below shows the current market share and ratings of these banks. Currently, Lloyds Group has majority of the market share (27%) in terms of personal and business current accounts. A total of more than one quarter (27%) of all current accounts are with Lloyds Group.

Table 2.12: Market share of UK High Street Banks

Bank	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016	Rating
Lloyds Group	28.6%	30%	27%	27%	27%	1
Barclays	6.7%	13%	16%	18%	18%	2
HSBC	4.1%	14%	14%	14%	12%	4
Santander	13%	12%	9%	10%	10%	5
RBS	6.3%	16%	14%	18%	18%	3

Source: Statista (2016)

2.18 The Impact of Digital Technology

The UK banking sector is experiencing a significant shift towards digitalisation. The most fundamental force that is changing the financial services sector is information technology (IT). Information technology is rapidly changing the way financial service providers offer their services. According to Deloitte (2016) technological forces are affecting banks more than any other sector across the globe. The banking system in the UK has become increasingly multi-channel, as digital channels such as internet banking and mobile banking is taking over traditional methods such as branch banking and telephone banking (BBA, 2016). Today, UK retail banking customers are shifting towards online banking for speed and convenience. Internet banking is on the rise, with over 7.5 million logins a day, compared to only 2.6 million logins a day in 2014 (BBA, 2015).

The question is whether the banking sector will take advantage of these new technological opportunities, or whether it will have to struggle to maintain its current position in the market. The answer obviously is that banks must take a lead by taking advantage of technology in order to deliver their financial services. According to PWC (2016) the pace of technological innovation in banking sector will increase, and banks must alter their current strategies in order to adapt and respond to these technological developments. Likewise, Dangolani (2011) claims that today banks competitive reach is not determined by branch networks, but rather by their technological skills. He further suggests that technology in banking industry will change everything, and will become a potential enabler of increased service and reduced cost.

2.19 Internet Banking and its developments in the UK

The rapid developments in information and communication technology has changed the UK banking sector with far reaching impacts (BBA, 2015). The most radical innovation in financial sector is the adoption of internet banking. Consumers are increasingly shifting towards internet banking and mobile banking to manage their finances. Major UK banks have experienced a skyrocketing usage of internet banking in the past few years. According to British Bankers Association report (2016) there were 10.5 million internet banking logins per day, a 10% increase as compared to the last year. Similarly, an independent research conducted by RBS revealed that 63% of the UK consumers put their smartphone as their main platform for choice of banking (The Guardian, 2016). Another report conducted by BBA (2016) revealed that there were 8 million more downloads of mobile banking apps as compared to the last year in the UK.

Experts predict that the amount of internet banking usage we talk about today will be doubled over the next ten years. UK adults using mobile and internet banking has climbed sharply in recent years, and is projected to continue increasing over the next half decade. New research from CACI for BBA (2016) revealed that in 2020 customers will use internet to manage their current accounts 2.3 billion times, as compared to only 895 million in 2015. This increase in online banking will result in tremendous number of branch closures. It has been reported that there is a 32% decline in the average branch visit per day. According to BBA report (2016) customer bank branch interactions declined from 476 million in 2011 to 278 million in 2016. This is forecasted to continue over the next five years. CACI claims that in 2021 customer bank branch interaction will be 185 million a year equating to 51 branch visits daily on average. Likewise, BBA (2016) also revealed that there is a 43% decline in telephone banking over the last 5 years. The graph below shows how the usage of internet banking has increase over the last ten years. It can be clearly seen from the diagram that there is an active and steady growth in online banking over the past decade, with the share rose to 63% of the individuals use internet banking on regular basis in 2017.

Figure 2.11: Internet Banking Penetration in UK from 2007 to 2017

Source: Statista, 2017

The BBA (2016) reported that approximately £6.4 billion were transferred using internet banking per week, and this is projected to increase to as much as 9.4 billion by 2020. The figure above illustrates that today six in ten UK adults is using internet banking services and this is projected to grow further. As stated by Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), internet banking users interact with their banks 20 times more than those that bank in the branch.

2.19.1 How the Digital Banking Revolution Unfolded?

Internet banking and other form of digital banking technologies have evolved in the UK over time. The table below shows how digital banking in the UK has evolved since.

Table 2.13: How digital Banking Unfolded

2014

April	Lloyds Banks launched the Lloyds digital index, which is the UK's first annual measure of small businesses digital capabilities.
June	London Black Cab taxi started to accept payments by smartphones.
August	Barclays extended mobile phone payments service ping it internationally.
August	BBA data showed bank customers transferred £6.9 billion in 2013 using internet banking, and up to £ 5 billion in 2009.

September	Lloyds bank launched a system in their online banking app allowing customers to book appointments.
September	Contactless payments accepted on London Underground and most of other transport modes.
November	Nationwide became the first bank in the UK that started offering real-time balance access to smart watches.
December	Barclays introduced check imaging option in its mobile banking app. This allow customers to deposit their checks using apps without having to visit the branch.

2015

January	BBA research revealed that old people, between the age of 70 and 100 started using internet banking. These were about 2.3 million customers who were resisting to use online banking before.
February	Barclays launched Twitter payments through Pingit.
March	Halifax launched biometric and heartbeat technology to verify and authenticate its customers' identities.
June	Data from BBA (2016) revealed that contactless payments technology saves customers a great amount of time.
July	Lloyds Bank also introduced cheque-imaging facility for its customers, enabling them to deposit cheques online.
July	Apple pay launched in the UK
August	Nationwide expanded balance check and other quick features to Apple watch customers.
October	Nationwide bank launched phone service offering special services to cancel patients.
November	24/7 real-time faster payments limit raised from 100,000 to 250,000. This means that customers can transfer large amount of money in seconds using internet banking.

2016

January	Barclays introduced “Barclays Collect service, allowing business customers to book their cash collection online either from the app or from their desktop.
February	HSBC introduced fingerprint and voice recognition technology into its mobile banking apps.
April	Barclays also introduced the Apple Pay system that enable its customer to pay for their purchases.
April	Santander even introduced online software that helps regarding working capital solution for small businesses.
July	UK monthly contactless card payments reached 1.3 billion.
July	Yorkshire Building Society and Clydesdale launched “smart money management app” for both current and saving accounts.

Digital technology has revolutionised in how people spend, move and manage their money. Today, millions of customers are harnessing the easy-to-use technology that allows them to bank wherever and whenever they want. Internet and mobile banking transactions have doubled since last year and is taking up at a very rapid pace. According to BBA (2016) for millions of people in the UK today, banking is on the move saving customer’s money and time. Digital technology is connecting banks and their customers more strongly than ever before, giving customers the opportunity to access and manage their money 24 hours a day and seven days a week. Today customers can do a range of banking services from the palm of their hands. A recent report by BBA (2016) revealed that 72% of interactions between HSBC and its customers are by telephone or through internet banking.

To further illustrate the speed of growth of internet banking in the UK, the industry has experienced the use of mobile and internet banking more than triple in the last three years from 8% in 2010 to 27% in 2014. This has now risen even further, with only 16% of the people not using mobile banking or internet banking. Below are the recent industry’s digital trends reported by BBA (2016).

- 40,000 Mobile banking apps downloaded a day in 2015, a 25% rise from the previous year.

- 4.3 internet banking logins a day a day in 2015, a 2% decline because customers shifted towards banking apps.
- 11 Million apps logins a day during 2015, a 50% rise from the previous year.
- 71 Average branch visits per day in 2015, a 32% fall since 2011 as customers move towards online banking.
- 347 Million number of payments using internet banking in 2015, a rise of 54% from the last year.
- 3 Million people registered for Barclays' mobile phone payment service "Pingit" up to September 2014.
- £1 billion investment by Lloyds Banking Group for digital banking technology over three years (2015- 2017).
- 7 Million of Lloyds Banking Group customers now bank through their mobile or computer.
- in 2015, 22.9 million number of apps were download, an increase of 8.2 million as compared to 2014.
- 43% decline in telephone banking service since 2008 because customers find it simpler and more convenient to bank online.
- 33% of Barclays personal loan applications were made and approved online, without customer having to visit the branch.
- 450,000 logins to Tesco Bank Mobile Banking App each week as of 2015.

To summarise, the UK banking sector has experienced a much change over the past decade due to the rise of new consumer technologies. Mobile and internet banking channels have dramatically changed how consumers interact with their bank. Anthony Brown, Chief Executive at the BBA says: "The advent of the internet and the smartphones has transformed the ability of customers to access their accounts digitally". (BBA, 2016). BBA (2016) predicts at by 2020, two thirds of British adults will be making use of internet banking services.

2.20 The Mobile Banking Boom in the UK

In the last few years, more and more customers have turned to mobile banking apps to manage their finances. According to British Bankers Association report (2016) Britons nowadays bank on smartphones and mobile devices more than all the other banking channels combined. The report also predicts that by 2020, current account customers in the UK will use their mobile devices more than internet, telephone and branch banking. It was recorded that almost 40,000 mobile banking applications were downloaded in 2015, 25% more than the last year. The industry figures also show that there were nearly 11 million logins a day to banking apps in 2015, a 50% rise from the last year. Studies suggest that mobile banking apps is the most preferred way of managing cash “on the go” among British consumers. In sum, with the emergence of internet banking technology and widespread ownership of smartphones, almost 60% of the UK adults are estimated to bank on their mobile.

Why have mobile banking apps become so popular? First and foremost, they are the most convenient way for customers to manager their daily banking needs. Mobile banking technology has enabled customers to squeeze their routine banking tasks into busy lives. Several banking chores which previously needed a customer to physically visit a bank branch can now be done from the convenience of home. Secondly, the mobile banking apps themselves are very fast and easy, allowing customers to access their account information in as little as three seconds. The popularity of mobile banking apps has soared due to the range of tasks they allow customers to do. Previously these apps only allowed customers to check their account balance; however, today making payments to friends and retailers has become very easy with the help of these apps. For instance, RBS mobile banking app allow customers to personal loan or overdraft while on the move. Similarly, Barclays “Ping It” app allow customers to transfer money to friends and family using just a mobile number. A recent report by BBA revealed nearly 80% of the payments were made through mobile banking app by Halifax customers. UK’s three largest banks (RBS, Barclays and Lloyds Group) have seen a skyrocketing usage of mobile banking. They have added millions of customers in the last three years, with consumer use of mobile banking increased by 356%.

Fig 2.12: Mobile Banking Users at Major UK Banks

Source: Business Insider (2017)

According to BBA (2016) approximately £1.7 billion is transferred every week, a rise of 15% from the last year. With excessive penetration of smartphones, alongside a stronger economy, it is projected that around £3.4 will be transferred on a weekly basis by 2020. The BBA claims that customers are the biggest winners from this technology-led revolution.

2.21 Decline in Branch Banking

Bank branches in Britain are closing at a very fast pace as customers move to online and telephone banking. The bank branch network has been declining steadily for nearly a decade now. According to House of Commons Library (2015) there were 20,583 branches in 1988, but only 8,837 in 2012 and 5,355 in 2015. Another report by BBA (2016) shows that there is a 32% decline in customer bank branch interactions since 2011, equating to 71 average branch visits per day. Major UK banks have shut around 1,700 branches across the UK in the last five years with many more planned. HSBC alone has closed more than a quarter of its branches since January 2015. Similarly, Lloyds Group announced that it is going to axe 200 branches by 2017, on top of 200 it has already axed for the period of 2014. BBC (2016) report revealed that more than 40% of bank and building society branches have been closed across the UK since 1989. The graph below shows that there were 17,840 branches in 1990, 9,755 in 2013 and only 8,340 by the end of 2015.

Figure 2.13: Decline in UK Bank Branches

Source: Management Today (2016)

The pace of branch decline has accelerated in recent years, and will continue to do so due to the emergency of advanced internet banking technologies. The reasons for decline in branch network are varied, but the primary reason is the rise of internet and mobile banking in recent years. These technologies allow customers to conduct range of their daily banking activities from whenever and wherever they please. No longer are they required to take time from their busy schedule to visit a branch when internet and mobile banking is available instead.

2.22 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter focused on the current state of internet banking in the UK and also shed light on its recent developments. It was noted that both internet banking and mobile banking is projected to rise further in the future with expectation that 66% of UK adults will be using internet banking by 2020. Due to the advent of internet banking technology in the UK, consumer bank branches interactions have dramatically declined over the past few years. It is recommended that banks in the UK must understand the critical factors of adoption in order to further boost the usage of this service.

Chapter 3

Conceptual Framework and Development of Hypothesis

3.1 Introduction

The previous chapter reviewed and compared the existing models and empirical studies to build foundation for hypothesis development and establish a conceptual model for this study. This chapter now aims to develop a conceptual framework of internet banking acceptance following the technology acceptance models explained in chapter 2, particularly the TAM. This chapter has two objectives. First, it will explain a rationale for choosing Technology Acceptance Model for this research. Secondly, this chapter will develop and explain the internet banking acceptance model based on the TAM. The original TAM is augmented by additional components, namely, the trust model in section 2 of chapter 3 and the role of customer's demographic characteristics explained in section 3 of the previous chapter.

3.2 Rationale for Choosing Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

As previously mentioned in chapter 2, the TAM has received significant attention due to its explanatory power, validity and reliability of its constructs and its parsimony. Several studies have confirmed that the TAM's ability to explain and predict consumer's intention towards the adoption of information systems is much better than other theoretical models (Bosnjak et al, 2006 and Lai et al, 2010). As per Pinho and Soares (2010) TAM is the most tested and widely used model for predicting behavioural intention towards the use of internet banking, internet shopping and the internet. Similarly, Lin and Chang (2011) states that TAM performs empirically well and predict behavioural intention more accurately than the TRA. Research suggests that TAM has better predictive and explanatory power than the TRA and TPB in terms of specific behaviours (Kim, 2010). Main rationale for choosing TAM for the present study is that it has a clear focus specifically on information system. Furthermore, TAM is easier to apply in practice and has more empirical advantages as compared to other theoretical models. Based on these reasons, the researcher believe that TAM-based conceptual framework is more appropriate as compared to TRA and TPB for studying the acceptance of internet banking in the UK. TAM will explain more variance as compared to other technology acceptance models.

However, considering the limitations and weaknesses of the TAM discussed in chapter two, the present study has included the trust construct and demographic characteristics in order to better explain the consumer's behavioural intention towards internet banking. The original TAM fails to consider other important factors related to environmental uncertainty such as perceived risk and perceived trust. Number of researchers have found that the concept of trust, risk and demographics play a crucial role in influencing customers' intention to engage in online banking behaviour (Kim and Ahn, 2005; Teo and Liu, 2007; Kim et al, 2009; Hahn and Kim, 2009). Therefore, the present study will integrate the trust model and role of demographics in the original TAM model. In summary, the present study proposes that customer's acceptance of online banking is jointly determined by perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEU) trust and perceived risk and demographic characteristics of customers. Combining these additional aspects will better predict and explain internet banking acceptance than the TAM could provide separately.

3.3 Conceptual Model for Internet Banking Acceptance

The conceptual framework developed for the present study is based on the Technology Acceptance model. The current framework proposes that consumers' intention to use internet banking is influenced by five direct determinants: *perceived usefulness*, *perceived ease of use*, *trust*, *perceived risk* and *customer's demographics*. As discussed in the above chapters, due to the uncertain nature of internet, trust and perceived risk plays a vital role in the acceptance of online banking and are theorized as direct determinants of intention. Therefore, the present study includes the issue of trust and perceived risk in the proposed model. Additionally, customer's demographics are also included in the model because they are also influential.

The conceptual model developed for the present study is shown below in Figure 3.1:

Figure 3-1: Internet Banking Acceptance Model
Source: This Research

3.3.1 Behavioural Intentions

Behavioural intention is the person's subjective probability that he/she will perform a target behaviour (Park and Pobil, 2003). Studies based on TRA and TAM suggest a strong and positive correlation between intention and actual use. In internet banking context, customer's behavioural intention will determine their actual use of internet banking services. In other words, behavioural intention will positively influence the actual use of internet banking. Based on this, the present study proposes that:

H1: Behavioural intention to use internet banking will positively influence the actual usage of internet banking.

As stated in chapter 2, the predictive and explanatory power of TAM will remain the same without the attitude construct (Hong et al 2002; Hwang 2005 and Venkatesh 2000). The attitude construct of the original TAM will not be included in the proposed model for this study. The present study will use behavioural intention as the ultimate dependent variable rather than the actual use of internet banking. The primary reason for this is that majority of the researchers have agreed on the fact that consumer's actual behaviour can be determined by their intention towards that behaviour (Davis et al, 1989, Moore and Benbasat, 2001). These studies have confirmed a strong and positive correlation between actual use and behavioural intention. Therefore, it is theoretically justifiable to use customer's behavioural intention as a dependant variable in examining customer's internet banking acceptance. The second main reason is that the present research focuses on the behavioural intention perspective of the UK customers. For this reason, it is appropriate to use behavioural intention as a dependant variable as compared to actual use.

3.3.2 Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) suggest that there are two main variables, perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEU) that affect user's intention to accept new technology. In the context of internet banking, this service provides the customers with numerous advantages and convenience in their daily lives. Internet banking service enable the customers to carry out their banking transaction from any location and at any time. Customers also have a greater control over managing their financial information. Considering the benefits that online banking offers, it is assumed

that customer who perceive this service as useful and ease to use will develop positive intention towards it and will adopt and use this service. Similarly, an easy and user-friendly internet banking website will facilitate the transactions and will be accepted by the customers. As per Law (2013) ease of use is one the primary factors that positively influence customer's intention towards electronic banking in Ireland and the UK. Previous studies have also found a strong and positive relationship between PU and PEU (Davis et al. 1989). Studies also confirm that both PU and PEU are related to intention, however, the relationship documented for PU is much stronger than that of PEU. The current study seeks to examine all the relationships between PU and PEU; thus, the following hypothesis have been developed:

- H2:** Perceived usefulness has a positive impact on UK's customers intention to use internet banking.
- H3:** Perceived ease of use has a positive impact on UK's customers intention to use internet banking.
- H4:** Perceived ease of use will positively influence perceived usefulness.

3.3.3 Perceived Trust and Risk

The importance of trust and risk in the acceptance of internet banking has been highlighted in chapter 3. It was also noted from the above discussion that customer trust and perceived risk has a direct impact on internet banking intentions. Based on this discuss, the following hypotheses have been proposed:

- H5:** High level of trust positively affects customer's intention to adopt internet banking.
- H6:** High levels of trust leads to low perceived risk.
- H7:** Perceived risk negatively affects customer's intention to use internet banking.

3.3.4 Perceived Security

It was noticed from chapter 3 (section 3.4) that the issue of security is one of the most significant barriers that user's decision to use internet banking. Customer's perception of security is based on timely, accurate and safe transmission of data. The present study proposes that positive perception regarding security leads to trust and confidence in the

relationship and this results in greater customer satisfaction. Based on this discussion, the present study proposes:

H8: Perceived security has a positive impact on customer trust.

3.3.5 Perceived Privacy

As discussed in chapter 3 (section 3.5.2) that in online environment customers have little control over the information they share, and this negatively affects their willingness to trust internet-based transactions. The fear of loss of personal and financial data plays a critical role in building online trust. Studies suggest that customers' high perception of online privacy positively influence their willingness to trust and use the internet banking service. Thus, the following hypothesis has been proposed:

H9: Perceived privacy has a positive impact on customer trust.

3.3.6 Perceived Bank's Trustworthiness

As discussed in chapter 3 (Section 3.5.2) that the amount of trust that a trustor will put on trustee is mainly based on the positive characteristics and attributes of the trustee. Several studies have confirmed that the positive characteristics and actions of the trustee motivates a trustor to trust a particular trustee. It was also noted from the above discussion that the perceived trustworthiness of a trusted party is mainly determined by attributes such as ability, integrity and benevolence. The present study proposes that the trustworthiness of the bank will directly and positively affect consumer's willingness to conduct internet banking with that bank. Considering the danger and uncertain environment of internet, banks must have the ability and integrity to deliver its internet banking services to its customers. As per McNeish (2015) bank's ability, integrity and benevolence plays a crucial role in influencing customer's decision to bank online. Thus, the following hypotheses have been proposed for this study:

3.3.7 Structural Assurance of the Bank's Website

The significance of the perceived structural assurance of the bank's website is discussed in the above chapter 3 (Section 3.5.3). Structural assurance of the bank's website is about the customer's belief that a website has the required legal and protective technological structure (such as, privacy and security policies, third party assurance and firewall encryption) that ensure that it is safe and secure to conduct financial transactions in this website (McKnight et al., 2002). Based on these discussions, the present study proposes that:

3.3.8 Integrating Trust with the TAM Variables

As discussed earlier, internet banking is considered as a sensitive exchange situation due to the absence of face-to-face interaction between the customer and bank staff. Similarly, due to the uncertain atmosphere of internet, customer trust is the key variable in internet banking usage. Furthermore, empirical literature also suggests that integration of trust construct with TAM variables (Naeem et al, 2001; Chircu et al. 2000; Pavlou, 2003). According to Lewis, Palmer and Moll (2010) trust increases customers' perception of the perceived usefulness of the interaction. If the customer cannot trust the ability and integrity of the bank, there is no point for customer to use internet banking even if it is useful. Gefen et al. (2003) claims that trust positively influences perceived usefulness (PU) and facilitate transactions between the customer and the Web retailer. Similarly, if the online vendor is not trustworthy, the customers may suffer loss from the financial transactions when the bank behave in a negative opportunistic way.

Researcher also indicate that customer's perception of perceived ease of use (PEU) of internet banking will also influence their level of trust. Mansour (2016) claims that the complexity of the IB website reduces adoption intentions of internet banking services. Similarly, Xio (2017) found that when customers perceive products and services as being complicated and problematic, they will perceive it risky to adopt and use. Internet banking websites that are unnecessarily hard to use will be perceived by customers as not being straight forward and honest. Although perceived ease of use (PEU) is not the main sole determinant of trust, it does to overall trust on internet banking. Linking trust with TAM variables leads the researcher to develop the following hypotheses:

H10: Customer trust in internet banking positively influences perceived usefulness.

H11: Perceived ease of use positively influences customer trust.

3.3.9 Role of Users' Demographic Characteristics

As discussed in the above sections, consumer's intention to adopt and use online banking are mainly determined by ease of use, usefulness trust and risk. These beliefs are related to technology or the bank and are called the technology-specific characteristics. However, individual's differences must also be taken into account in order for banks to correctly model customer behaviour towards internet banking adoption (See chapter 4 for more detail). These differences will help banks to determine how perceptions are formed towards internet banking service. As noted from the chapter 4, the demographic characteristics of the customers will moderate the relationship between perceptions and intention. The following hypothesis have been proposed:

H12: Gender has an impact on customer's choice to use internet banking.

H13: Age has an impact on customer's choice to use internet banking.

H14: Education level has an impact on customer's choice to use internet banking.

Summary of the Chapter

This present chapter developed a conceptual framework for internet banking acceptance for the purpose of achieving the main research objective outlined in chapter one. The conceptual model in this chapter proposes that intention towards internet banking is mainly influenced by four main direct factors: PU, PEU, trust and perceived risk. However, the customer's level of technology readiness and their demographic characteristics are proposed as moderators between perception and actual use.

Chapter 4

Research Design and Methodology

The main purpose of this chapter is to explain the research methods used for analysis of the data for this study. The chapter will discuss four major topics of the research methodology; the research philosophy, research approach, research strategy and research methods. Motivation and justification will be given as to why a particular research method or strategy is adopted. The chapter also aims to discuss both the advantages and limitations of each research method before employing it. Important concerns such as validity and reliability of data and as well as ethical issues will also be addressed in this chapter. Finally, how the data will be analysed are also mentioned in the last section of this chapter.

Research methodology refers to the techniques that the researcher will use to investigate a research problem. In general, research methodology answers two main questions: How was the data collected and generated? And, how should it be analysed? According to Bryman and Bell (2011) the research methodology is the crucial part of any research paper. Because unreliable research methods produce unreliable results and thus undermines the overall value of the interpretations of research findings (Saunders et al, 2009). In the past, several researches have received critics from authors for not adopting an appropriate research methodology. Although a perfect research methodology cannot be guaranteed, researcher can keep errors to minimum if he or she chooses an appropriate research method when addressing research questions and objectives.

For the present study, the researcher has taken every possible step to adopt suitable research philosophy and design that corresponds to the research questions, objectives and hypotheses developed in the previous chapter. The researcher also ensures that the adopted research method will minimise the errors and enhance the overall validity and reliability of the research. The researcher is aware that the choice of suitable research design plays a vital role and makes significant contribution towards the overall findings of the research.

4.1 Research Philosophy

According to Saunders et al, (2009) research philosophy is a belief about how data about a particular phenomenon should be gathered, used and analysed. In other words, research philosophy is the researcher's assumptions about a certain practice, method or outlook. The type of research philosophy adopted will have potential influence on the choice of research methods. Therefore, Cooper and Schindler (2016) suggest that it is of high importance to choose appropriate research philosophy as this will determine the overall research design, research strategy and research approach. There are many branches of research philosophy in different disciplines; however, within the scope of business studies research, ontology and epistemology are the two major ways of thinking about research philosophy. Each of these approaches are different in the way researcher thinks about the researcher process (Bajpai, 2011). For instance, researcher who believe in facts will have a very different view on the way research should be conducted to the researcher concerned with the attitudes and feelings of the people. Not only their research methods and strategies will be considerably different, but also their views on what is important and useful in the research process.

Ontology can be defined as the "science or study of being" and is mainly concerned with the nature of reality. In simple terms, ontology is associated with central question about what constitute as fact or reality. Ontology is mainly concerned with whether social entities should be perceived as objective or subjective. Ontology is subdivided in two conflicting forms: Objectivism and Subjectivism (constructivism). Objectivism is an ontological position that is based on the belief that social phenomena exist independently of the social actors (Saunders et al, 2007). This means that social reality is out there existing without any influence from the individuals. On the other hand, subjectivism is based on the opinions and perceptions of the social actors. (Murphy and Bhojanna, 2008). This means that social actors have an active and crucial role in the construction of social phenomena. The literature mainly underlines two distinctive approaches in answering research questions: Positivism and Interpretivism.

4.1.1 Positivism and Interpretivism

Positivism is generally regarded as scientific approach that follows methods which are highly formal, organised and measured using quantifiable observations. The positivists believe that there is a single objective reality to any research phenomenon without taking into account the researcher's perspective or belief (Rios and Campo, 2013). The positivists ontology follows a controlled and structured approach and has the objective to seek objectivity in the truth. Researchers following this approach works with observable social reality and the result is similar to physical or natural science researches (Bryant, 2012). An important reality of positivism philosophy is that the social world is independent of the researcher who examine it, meaning that the researcher is not influenced by the subjects of the study (Saunders et al, 2009). Positivism is mainly based on values of reason and validity and there is no room for subjective opinions.

In contrast, the interpretivist philosophy adopts a more personal research approach with views and attitude of the subjects being taken into account. This anti-positivist philosophy refuses to view the pattern set by natural sciences and suggests that research should be conducted in a truly subjective manner (Burns and Burns, 2011). Researchers adopting this approach believe that the social world is too complex and cannot be treated as science and analysed using quantifiable observations. Therefore, it is important to understand the differences between humans and their opinions. An important reality of this approach is that the social world can only be understood by exploring human's perspective involved in the situation being investigated (Bryman and Bell, 2015). As per Saunders et al (2009) interpretivists study the research phenomenon from the viewpoint of the subjects involved in that phenomenon. Interpretivism mainly adopts a qualitative form of inquiry in order to grasp the variety of views and opinions from the participants.

According to Price and Cameron (2009) positivism and Interpretivism philosophies are not competing views, but rather they complement one another by contributing to the information missed one by the other. However, Sekaran and Bougie (2016) disagree with this view and argue if these two methods are linked naively, it will have an adverse impact on the validity and credibility of the research findings. From these logical arguments, it is deduced that positivism and Interpretivism contradicts each other and thus require different analytical lenses for the same data. Similarly, Anderson (2013)

claims that these two philosophies diametrically oppose one another when researching a phenomenon. Table 4.1 Summarizes some of the key differences between positivism and Interpretivism:

Table 4.1: Differences between positivism and Interpretivism

Positivist	Interpretivism
Causation : Seeks to understand the causal explanation for a phenomenon	Interpretation : Seek to understand how people interpret phenomena
Objective Reality : Presumes the existence of facts	Subjective Reality : Construction of facts are seen as interpreted and subjective
Generality : Analysis seeks a law that extends beyond specific instance studied/research	Specificity : Analysis is context specific, only on subjective understanding
Replicability : Analysis can be tested and verified empirically against other cases	Self-Validation Analysis can only be self-validating through consistency and coherence of description

Source: Rooth and Metha, (2002)

4.1.2 Realism

Realism is another scientific paradigm which advocates that there is an external reality independent of the researcher's mind. Realism is also a branch of epistemology somehow similar to positivism, which follows scientific approach towards the development of knowledge. Realism philosophy is based on the belief that reality is existing quite independent of the researcher's mind. In social sciences research, there are two types of realism: Direct Realism and Critical Realism. Direct realism asserts that what you see is what you get. In other words, it assumes that what researcher experience through his or her senses portrays the world accurately. Critical realism, on the other hand, argue that what we see through our senses are the sensations, not the real things directly.

Realism philosophy is not widely used in business and management research and is therefore outside the scope of this study. The researcher therefore will not go into much detail of this branch of epistemology.

4.1.3 Pragmatism

Unlike positivism and Interpretivism, where philosophical is restricted to one paradigm of thinking, the pragmatism philosophical perspective evolves from actions and situations and advocates that more than one research strategy can be adopted in answering the research questions (Jr et al. 2015). Pragmatists mainly focus on research questions rather than research methods and thus give themselves the freedom to adopt any of the method. This is because pragmatists believe that every method has limitations and using more than one approach can be complementary (Cameron and Azorin, 2013). The pragmatists can adopt both qualitative and quantitative methods depending on the nature of research questions and objectives. In summary, this freedom of choices places no restriction on techniques, methods, procedures and assumption but mainly concentrate on what the best option is to choose that will provide answers to the research questions.

4.1.4 Justification for Adopted philosophy for this study

After analysing all the four main types of research philosophies, the researcher believes that the use of positivists philosophy will be more appropriate to answer the research questions of this study. First, the nature of the present study is objective and quantitative in nature because it revolves around testing an existing technology acceptance model. Secondly, several hypotheses were developed based on various technology acceptance models for this study. Therefore, to test and validate the hypotheses developed in the conceptual framework chapter, the current study will use positivist (quantitative) approach because it is more consistent with the topic. Additionally, the hypotheses developed for the present study are based on cause and effect relationships; therefore, positivist research approach is more suitable to validate those hypotheses.

There are other reasons as to why this study falls within the domain of positivists approach as compared to interpretivist approach. First, the researcher will test the formulated hypotheses using self-administered questionnaire to the customers. The researcher will remain detached from the problem being investigated. Secondly, this research philosophy allows the researcher to collect data in a more economical way and provide easily comparable data (Saunders et al, 2009).

Although one might argue that the use of pragmatist approach is more suitable for a mixed research, the present study is predominantly quantitative in nature and thus mainly based on a questionnaire survey. For this reason, the researcher believed that

the use of positivist approach will be more appropriate to answer the research questions of this study as compared to other philosophical approach This justification is also backed by the following articles in this field, Lee et al (2012); Yousafzai and Soriano, (2011); Law and Legohere (2013).

Based on these reasons, it is justified to use positivist research philosophy for studying customers' acceptance of internet banking.

4.2 Research Approach

There are three main approaches a researcher can follow in order to arrive at a conclusion: Deductive reasoning (theory → confirmation), Inductive reasoning (observation → theory) or abductive reasoning.

Deductive reasoning is also called a top-down approach where the researcher tests an existing theory by developing hypothesis (or hypotheses) to see if it is true (Bryman and Bell (2015). In other words, deductive research approach explores an existing theory or phenomenon and then design a research strategy to test if that theory is valid in a given circumstances. Deductive reasoning progresses through these five stages (as shown in figure 6.1): 1, begin with the theory, 2) deducing hypothesis (or hypotheses) from that theory, 3) test the hypothesis using one or more research strategies, 4) confirm or reject the hypotheses, 5) modify the theory as per the findings. According to Saunders et al (2009) deductive research approach is also called a testing-theory approach and is widely used in scientific researches.

Figure 4.1: The Process of Deduction (Source: Bryman, 2001)

Inductive reasoning works the other way, the researcher begins with specific observations, formulate one or more tentative hypotheses, and finally collect data to propose a theory based on those observed events (Kothari, 2004). Inductive research approach is also called a button-up approach that moves from more specific observations to more broader generalisations.

Studies have differentiated deductive and inductive reasoning in several ways. As noted above, the deductive reasoning moves from theory to data, while inductive approach moves from data to theory. Another major difference is that deductive approach owes more to positivism and associated with quantitative researches, while inductive approach is widely used in qualitative research approaches (Daniel and Sam, 2011). However, there are no set rules, some quantitative studies may use inductive approach as vice versa. Thirdly, deductive reasoning mainly focuses on causality, whilst for inductive approaches, the emphasis is more on exploring new phenomena. Saunders et al (2009) claims that no research approach is superior or inferior than the other, the choice between whether to use deductive or inductive reasoning mainly depends on the purpose and nature of research being conducted. Table 4.2 below summarizes the main differences between deductive and inductive reasoning.

Deduction emphasises	Induction emphasises
Scientific principles	Gaining an understanding of the meanings humans attach to events
Moving from theory to data	A close understanding of the research context
The need to explain causal relationships between variables	The collection of qualitative data
The collection of quantitative data	A more flexible structure to permit changes of research emphasis as the research progresses
The application of controls to ensure validity of data	A realisation that the researcher is part of the research process
The operationalisation of concepts to ensure clarity of definition	Less concern with the need to generalise
A highly structured approach	
Researcher independence of what is being researched	
The necessity to select samples of sufficient size in order to generalise conclusions	

Table 4.2: Major Differences between Deductive and Inductive Reasoning
(Source: Saunders et al, 2009, cited by Doorman, (2010))

4.2.1 Justification for Adopted approach for this study

The present study adopts a deductive reasoning for the purpose of understanding the factors affecting customers' adoption of internet banking in the UK. This approach is best suited because it is not only related to the chosen philosophy (positivism), but it will also allow the researcher to survey large number of online banking customers who are the main subjects of the study being investigated. The second main reason for adopting deductive approach is that the present study is testing an existing model/theory to study the customers' behaviour towards the acceptance of online banking in the UK. Various hypotheses were developed based on existing literature in this field. The researcher will collect quantitative data through survey questionnaire in order to accept or reject these hypotheses. Various statistical tests will be conducted to test these hypotheses, and the result from these tests will confirm whether the factors hypothesised for the present study affects the adoption of internet banking or not. Another main reason for adopting deductive approach is that the factors being investigated for this study have an objective and external reality; therefore, the adopted method will enable the researcher to arrive at a conclusion through statistical tests such as correlation analysis and t tests.

6.3 Research Design

Kumar (2010) defines research design as a blueprint or roadmap that describes how, when and where data for the research to be collected and analysed. Research design has three types: exploratory, descriptive or explanatory.

In exploratory research, the researcher explores a setting, phenomenon or an outlook that has not been identified or explored before (Dane, 2011). In exploratory research, the researcher has observed something for the first time and seeks to understand more about it. In sum, this type of research attempts to lay the initial groundwork for future studies. Exploratory studies tend to be more qualitative and data is collected through brainstorming session, interviews with experts, and open-ended questionnaire survey. Descriptive research, on the other hand, describes the characteristics of a particular situation or an outlook. Descriptive research is pre-planned and is more structured and formal as compared to exploratory research (Saunders et al, 2015). Unlike exploratory research, descriptive research can make use of either qualitative or quantitative data. Finally, explanatory research studies a problem or phenomenon by explaining the relationship between variables (Saunders et al, 2007). This research design explains

cause and effect relationship between variables. Explanatory research is more suitable when the primary objective of the study is to determine functional relationship between variables (causes) and the phenomena being investigated (effect) (Chawla and Sondi, 2011). Explanatory research is also called causal research and is normally pre-planned, structured and quantitative in nature. This research design has two objectives: 1, To define which variables are the cause and which are variables are the effect, and 2) to determine the relationship between the cause and effect variables.

4.3.1 Justification for Adopted research design for this study

Considering the aim and objective of this research, explanatory research design is adopted for the present study for three reasons. First and foremost, the nature of the present study is more quantitative and less qualitative; therefore, the explanatory research design will better explain the relationship between different variables. Secondly, the hypotheses developed in the previous chapter can better be explained and tested by adopting explanatory research because they are based on cause and effect relationships. This is in line with Saunders et al (2009) recommendations, who states that studies based on casual relationships between variables may adopt explanatory research design. Finally, hypotheses developed for the present study are based on causal relationship between variables. A change in one variable directly affect another variable. For instance, a change in perceived security of internet banking will affect customer intention to use internet banking. The use of explanatory research is best suited for explaining the relationships between such variables.

4.4 Research Choices

According to Thomas (2003) the choice of research method is driven by research questions, research design and underlying philosophical assumption of the research. Research choices are broadly split into quantitative, qualitative or the combination of both (mixed method). McDaniel and Gibbs (2008) states that these choices follow different procedures and each of these choices are suitable for different research settings.

4.4.1 Qualitative Research

Qualitative research is defined as the research method that uses and generate non-numerical data and non-quantifiable observations (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Qualitative research is exploratory in nature that has the objective of gaining an understanding of underlying reasons, motivations and opinions. Studies adopting qualitative approach focuses on norms, values and actions of the participants of the phenomena. Qualitative research provides the researcher with an in-depth picture of the research problem being investigated. As per Goertz and Mahoney (2012) qualitative research is conducted through different mechanisms such as in-depth interviews, focus group discussion, or open-ended questions. This type of research is mainly concerned with questions such as, why? And how?

4.4.2 Quantitative Research

Quantitative research, on the other hand, uses and generates numerical data to quantify the research problem. According to Creswell and Creswell (2017) quantitative approach is highly formal and systematic in nature and is widely used by positivists that view the world as an object. Moreover, this research approach study social phenomena using cause and effect relationships. As the name implies, quantitative research is used to quantify opinions, attitudes, behaviours and other defined variables. Researchers adopting this approach generally collects data from a larger sample population and then generalize the results. Quantitative research methods include various forms, such as surveys, structured interviews, close-ended questions and systematic observations.

Quantitative and qualitative research strategies differ on the basis of data sample, data collection, data analysis and as well as research outcomes (Daniel and Sam, 2011). Data collection in qualitative research is methodologically flexible using in-depth interviews or focus group discussion in order to elicit great detail and comprehensive view of the research participants. Whereas, quantitative research uses highly formal and systematic data collection process such as structured interviews. Qualitative research is exploratory, and its findings are not conclusive and cannot be used to make generalizations. Moreover, qualitative research is more subjective in nature where the researcher studies the problem from the point of view of participants of that problem. Whereas, quantitative research is objective and study the phenomena using cause and effect relationship. Table 6.3 below summarizes some of the main differences these two research choices:

Table 4.3: Qualitative and Quantitative research

Criteria	Qualitative Research	Quantitative Research
Purpose	Understanding social interactions of the participants	Based on cause and effect relationships
Sample	Small	Large
Type of data	Views, opinions and words	Statistics and numbers
Type of research	Exploratory	Descriptive or explanatory
Research approach	Inductive	Deductive
Epistemological assumption	Interpretivism	Positivism
Ontological assumption	Subjectivism	Objectivism
Nature of observation	Study phenomenon in natural environment	Study phenomenon under controlled conditions
Methods	Non-structured techniques, such as depth interviews and focus group discussion	Structured techniques, such as survey, observations and close-ended questionnaires
Result	Narrative reports	Statistical reports

Source: This research

Silverman (2016) states that there is no right and wrong answer to which method the researcher should choose. Both methods have their own characteristics, and the choice between qualitative and quantitative depends on the nature of research questions and objectives. It is also driven by the research design and philosophical assumption of the study.

4.4.3 Justification for Adopted Research choice for this study (Mixed)

As noted in the above discussion, the decision to adopt quantitative, qualitative or mixed method is mainly based on research topic, research aim and objectives and philosophical assumption of the research. Keeping in mind the nature of this research and throughout analysis of all the three methods, the present study will adopt a mixed method (both qualitative and quantitative). There are three main reasons for adopting a mixed research method for this study. First and foremost, the nature of the present study is related to the social world (which is about studying the perceptions and behaviour of consumers regarding the acceptance of internet banking), and thus cannot be analysed solely on the basis of natural science approach. Secondly, the nature and scope of the

current research and philosophical assumption adopted owes to both quantitative and qualitative; therefore, using a mixed method is more appropriate. Third, Saunders et al (2009) claims that quantitative and qualitative approaches have their own strengths and limitation; therefore, adopting a mixed method will offer complementary views, minimise the limitations and enhance the richness of the overall research. Furthermore, mixed method is adopted based on the recommendations of Clark and Ivankova (2016) who states that adopting a mixed method increases the validity and reliability of research findings. Likewise, Teddie and Tashakkori (2009) suggest that using a multi-method approach provides the researcher with an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon being investigated.

Both numerical and non-numerical data will result in an in-depth understanding of the research problem and will ultimately enable him to draw effective conclusions. On quantitative side, numerical data will answer questions such as what percentage of respondents agree or disagree with a particular opinion, what percentage of customers perceived internet banking as useful and easy to use and so on. On the other hand, non-numerical data will answer questions such as advantages and disadvantages of using internet banking, the issue of trust, privacy and security regarding the acceptance of internet banking in the UK. The present study will obtain qualitative data using literature review, focus group discussions and interviews with the managers. Whereas, quantitative data will be collected by distributing self-completion questionnaires to customers in bank branches.

Bryant (2012) claims that researcher can gain much by combining the respecting strengths of multi-method research.

4.5 Data Collection Method

The researcher will make use of both secondary and primary data collection methods in order to gain rich knowledge of the present study.

4.5.1 Secondary data collection

Secondary data is a pre-collected data that has previously been gathered by someone else for some other purposes (Veal, 2005). Secondary data is a second-hand information not specifically relating to the research problem. Secondary data for the research is obtained from sources such as such as books, journal articles, websites, censuses, case studies, government publications and so on. For the purpose of this study, secondary data is collected from highly authentic sources in order to ensure reliability and validity.

The data was collected from reliable sources such as Emerald, ScienceDirect, Ebscohost, Sage online journals, Newsbank and Google books. Both online and offline sources were consulted in order to obtain secondary data for this research. Among these, Emerald, and Ebscohost are very resourceful sources for business and enterprise subject. Emerald is a very powerful online reference system that contains a portfolio of nearly 300 journals and over 1,500 text cases. Its comprehensive database ranges from general reference collections to subject-specific concerns. The second main source for secondary source was ScienceDirect. ScienceDirect is a leading platform of peer-reviewed scholarly articles. This source contains millions of publications from full-text journals that covers around 24 subjects from various disciplines such as business management, economics, engineering and so on.

The advantages associated with secondary data include economies, time saving and extensive breadth of the data available. The major benefit of using secondary data is economies. Because someone else has already collected the data; therefore, no resources of the researcher are committed to the data collection process. The researcher does not need to devote time, money and other resources to collect such data. The second major benefit of secondary data is the ease of access. With the availability of online access, secondary data is openly accessed from anywhere and at any time. Third and most important benefit of secondary data is that it is already exposed to high level of expertise and professionalism (Ghuri and Gronhaug, 2005). For instance, data collected from authentic sources is often collected and analysed by researchers who have many years of experience and are specialised in that particular area. Small research projects do not have that level of professionalism and expertise.

The major weakness of secondary data is the non-involvement of the researcher in the data collection process (Saunders et al, 2009). The collected data may not be tailored to the present study and therefore may not answer some of the researcher's questions. This is because the data might not be collected in a specific geographical region or from the specific population that the researcher is intended to study. Similarly, the researcher will have little or no control over the content of the secondary data because the researcher himself or herself did not collect the data. Another major disadvantage of using secondary data is the issue reliability and validity. The researcher does not know how the data was collected and analysed and cannot anticipate how this data might be negatively affected by low response rate or respondent's misunderstandings of the questions of the survey. In summary, the use of secondary data provides significant

advantages to the researcher and provide in-depth understandings of the subject being investigated. However, the researcher must take great care when employing secondary data in the research.

4.5.2 Primary data Collection

Primary data is also called original data that is specifically collected for the research purpose in mind (Byrman and Bell, 2015). Primary data is fresh and collected for the first time by the researcher. In other words, primary data is tailored specifically to the current research questions and research objectives. Methods used to collect primary data includes interviews, surveys, observations, questionnaires, focus group discussion and so on. The main strength of the primary data is that it is highly authentic, confidential and specifically related to the current research. However, it is very costly and demands great amount of time to obtain.

For the present study, primary data is collected using both questionnaires and semi-structured interviews in order to capture variety of views of both the internet banking customers and bank's management about the drivers and barriers of internet banking in the UK.

Figure 4-2 below outlines the method of primary data collection for this study.

Figure 4-2: Primary Data Collection for the Present Study

Source: This Research

4.5.2.1 Questionnaire Survey

Questionnaire is a form of survey that is commonly used to obtain data from a larger population in a short period of time and in a relatively cost-effective way (Hak and Dul, 2008). There are mainly two types of questionnaires used in social science researches called structured questionnaire and unstructured questionnaire. According to Welman, Kruger and Kruger, (2001) **structured questionnaires** are commonly based on closed ended questions that produced data which can be analysed quantitatively. This type of questionnaire provides no or little flexibility to respondents to qualify their answers. On the other hand, **unstructured questionnaires** are based on open ended questions that provides respondents the freedom to express their views and allow greater flexibility in terms of qualification.

For the present study, around 400 questionnaires were developed and distributed in different forms in order to collect the primary data. The main target population for this study is the internet banking users in the UK. Therefore, approximately 400 questionnaires were distributed across three different sources. First, two hundred (250) copies of the final questionnaire were distributed to customers within different bank branches across London. The researcher has already obtained a permission from these banks to assist in this research. Customers were requested politely to participate in the survey when they visit the bank branch. There are two main reasons for distributing the questionnaire inside the bank premises rather than outside. First, the purpose of this research is to study the actual behaviour of respondents about internet banking acceptance and it was only possible in collaboration with the banks. Secondly, customers are more willing to participate in a questionnaire survey distributed inside the bank's premises rather than asked by a random person outside. Therefore, 250 copies of the final questionnaire were distributed inside the banks' premises across London. The customers were given the option to either fill the questionnaire in branch or take them home and fill it in their free time and then e-mail it to the researcher. The questionnaire took a maximum of 8 minutes to complete.

Apart from physical distribution, 150 internet version questionnaires were prepared and distributed electronically through Survey Monkey. There are two main benefits associated with this method. First, Survey Monkey enabled the researcher to collect larger data in a short period of time because people are more willing to participate in electronic surveys. Secondly, Survey Monkey will have allowed the researcher to get

instant feedback from internet banking customers across the UK. The data collected through Survey Monkey will be exported to SPSS for advanced statistical analysis.

4.5.2.2 Semi-Structured Interview

Interviews are classified into different types, depending on the types of research questions, research objectives and the availability of resources. The most common types of interviews used in social sciences research are structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews. Each type of these interviews has its own strengths and limitations.

Semi-Structured interviews method is more suited and appropriate to achieve the overall objective of the present study. This is because the researcher needs to conduct non-standardized interviews with UK bank managers and give them the opportunity to openly share their views and opinions regarding internet banking usage in the UK. Secondly, since this study is exploratory in nature; therefore, conducting one-to-one interviews is a suitable qualitative method to gain more reliable and accurate information for the present study. A total of 5 interviews were conducted in five major retail banks across London. These banks include: Lloyds, Barclays, HSBC, NatWest and RBS. These interviews took a maximum of 30 minutes and include series of questions.

4.6 Sampling Procedure

Once the researcher has identified the research problem, formulae appropriate research questions, and develop relevant research design and methods, the next step is to determine the sample from which the data is to be collected. The decision about the sample size is the crucial stage in any social research. The main steps in sampling procedure is to define population from which the data will be collected, identify sample frame, determine sample size and finally select the relevant sampling method.

4.6.1 Selecting Sampling Population

The first step in sampling procedure is to identify the intended population for the study. According to Stokes, (2011) population is the universe of units from which the sample is to be selected. Suri (2011) defines research population as the broader group of people to whom the researcher intends to generalise the findings of his or her study. Sample population can be in the form of whole nations, cities, firms, institutions, people etc.

The exact population will depend on the scope of the intended study and should include people to whom research results will apply.

For the present study, the population is all the internet banking customers in the United Kingdom. The intended population is selected based on these three main elements:

- **Geography:** The population for this study is all the internet banking customers who live in the main city of England: London. The population included both male and female individuals. There are two main reason for limiting the study to England and then to London only. First, London is the biggest city in England, accounting for almost 70% of the total internet banking users (Statista, 2016). Secondly, time, cost and other resources were also taken into consideration when administering the questionnaire.
- **Age of Individuals:** The population for the present study will include people of all ages who have access to bank services. However, the study will focus more on young individuals who frequently use internet banking services.
- **Individual Variables:** Since the study aims to investigate both the drivers and barriers to online banking, the population for this research are both the users and non-users of this service. The researcher will collect data from customers who are already adopting this service and as well as individuals who feel resistant to use this service.

4.6.2 Selecting Sampling Frame

The next step in sampling procedure is to identify the sample frame from the intended population. Gorman (2015) defines sampling frame as the list of all the units in the population from which the researcher intends to select the sample. For the present study, four major banks (Lloyds, Barclays, HSBC and NatWest) have been chosen to collect primary data. Questionnaire will be distributed among the customers of these four banks across different locations of London. These are the biggest high street banks in the UK and has the largest customer base as compared to other retail banks. The main reason for limiting the study to these four banks is to minimise the variances in responses that will adversely affect the final results, because differences exists between different service providers which might affect responses.

4.6.3 Selecting Sampling Size

According to Bryman and Bell (2009) when conducting research, it is practically impossible to collect data from the whole population that the researcher is interested in.

He or She must select a sample from that population and then generalise the findings. Sample size is the act of choosing respondents in such a way that they represent the total population as good and accurate as possible (Carsrud and Brannback, 2014). Research also suggests that choosing correct sample size is crucial for any research because a sample that is too small will not allow the researcher to gain reliable insights, while a sample that is too big will waste precious resources such as time and money. Moreover, sample size should be selected based on the availability of budget and time constraint. Similarly, sample size can also be selected based on what other similar studies have use in the same research field.

Considering the time, budget and other factors, the current study will use sample size based on what other researchers have used for similar studies. Previous internet banking studies have used a sample size of between 250 and 500. However, Bryman and Bell (2007) argue that increased sample size enhances the precision of the sample and reduces sampling error. Therefore, considering the available time and budget and comprehensive discussion with supervisor, the researcher will use a sample size of 400 respondents for the present study. Previous similar studies who administered questionnaires in similar scenarios have obtained response rate between 50% and 65%. Based on this assumption, the present study will administer 400 questionnaires to customers in different bank branches across London. Assuming 50% response rate will give the researcher 200 successfully filled questionnaires.

4.6.4 Selecting Sample Method

There are mainly two major method of sample, probability sampling and non-probability sampling.

Probability Sampling: Probability sampling is based on randomization where every unit of the population has an equal chance of being selected. According to Hair (2007) probability sampling is mainly used in quantitative studies and owes more to survey researches. Probability sampling has several variations, such as simple random, systematic, stratified, cluster random, and multi-stage random sampling.

Non-Probability Sampling: Non-probability sampling does not use randomization to select units from the population. In other words, not all the members have an equal chance to be selected from the population (Crowther and Lancaster, 2012). This type of sampling does not guarantee representation of the whole population. Non-probability sampling has the following subtypes: convenience, judgemental, purposive, quota and snowball sampling.

The present study will make use of both probability and non-probability sampling. First, 4 main branches of each bank in London will be selected using simple random sampling. Secondly, from each branch that have been selected, convenience sampling will be used to draw at least 60 respondents from each branch and the questionnaire will be distributed to respondents in these branches. This type of sampling is not only suitable with the scope and nature of this study but will also save researcher's time and financial resources. Other main advantages of self-completion questionnaire are that they are less costly and easier to administer and is very convenient for the participants to fill in.

As stated above, apart from physical distribution, 150 electronic questionnaires will also be designed and distributed using Survey Monkey Platform.

4.7 Questionnaire Development Process

The researcher will follow Churchill G.A (1999), a well recommended procedure for developing questionnaire for this study. This method consists of nine steps. Figure 4.3 below shows the process used to develop questionnaire:

Figure 4.3: The Process of Developing Questionnaire
Source: Churchill (1999)

Step 1: Specify what information will be sought: The researcher should be clear on what information he or she want to collect and then develop the questionnaire accordingly. The researcher should be able to specify the research purpose to the intended participants. For the present study, information will be collected based on the variable specified in the conceptual model in the previous chapter. The questionnaire will be designed mainly according to the hypothesis formulated in the previous chapter.

Step 2: Types of Questionnaire and method of administration: After the researcher determine the type of needed for the researcher, he or she must think about the structure of the questionnaires and how these questionnaires will be administered to the participants (Churchill, 1999). Different questions are administered differently such as e-mail, post, telephone or physical distribution. Considering the nature of this study, the researcher will use structured questionnaire with close-ended questions in order to collect primary data for this study. The questionnaires will be distributed to the participants through two different sources including physical distribution to customers inside bank branches and electronically using Survey Monkey. The researcher adopted this method of administration because it is less costly, less time-consuming and will collect data from large sample in a shorter period of time.

Step 3: Determine the content of questionnaire: The researcher should also consider whether the content of the questionnaire covers the topic being investigated, whether or not the format of the questionnaire is efficient and clear to the participants. Most of the questionnaire items were developed from literature review and previous internet banking studies.

Step 4: Determine forms of responses for each question: According to Churchill and Lacubocci (2015) the forms of responses are mainly based on the types of questions formulated. For the present study, close-ended questionnaire seems to be more appropriate. The main reason for this is because they are very simple and easy to design,

administer and analyse. To ensure greater uniformity of response rate, a five-point Likert scale will be used in the first three section of the questionnaire. The remaining section of the questionnaire have a 'tick' option allowing the respondents to answer questions closely related to their position regarding the subject.

Step 5: Determine the wording for each question: When designing questionnaire, it is very important for the researcher to avoid ambiguity and misunderstandings. According to Churchill (1999) researcher should easy to navigate and simple to understand for the respondents. Keeping this in mind, the researcher will pre-test the questionnaire through pilot studies in order to avoid any ambiguous words and questions. The researcher will also provide a short definition of internet banking at the top of questionnaire to make sure respondents do not confuse it with other forms of electronic banking.

Step 6: Determine sequence for each question: Once the researcher finalise the types of questions required for the survey, the researcher should put these questions in sequence to maximise the response rate. Studies suggests that questions in the survey should be simple, interesting and directly related to the static topic. The questionnaire for this study will comprise of three sections. Sections one will ask respondents about their general belief about IB. The second section will focus on respondents' general perception regarding internet banking acceptance. Questions regarding age, gender, ethnicity etc. will be asked at the final sections of the questionnaire.

Step 7: Determine physical characteristics of the questionnaire: According to Churchill (1999) respondent's willingness to participate in a survey is majorly influenced by how the questionnaire is designed and put forth. The researcher must ensure that the survey questionnaire does not look disorganised or sloppy and must directly reflect the importance of the study. If the presentation of the questionnaire is not organised, the respondent will unlikely to cooperate. For this reason, the researcher will ensure to achieve good physical appearance of the questionnaire. The researcher will conduct a pilot study before the final survey where respondents will be asked to provide feedback on the size, layout, format, font size and sequence of the questionnaire for the present study. Most importantly, a covering letter will also be enclosed with the questionnaire that will explain the importance of the study and will ensure that the respondent's answers will be kept highly confidential.

Step 8: Translation of the questionnaire: According to Churchill (1999) researcher must write design questionnaire in the native language of respondents in order for them to

understand. However, this will not be required for this study as the respondents are based in the UK and understands English.

Step 9: Pre-test questionnaire and revise if necessary: Zikmund (2003) suggest that the questionnaire must be pre-tested before final distribution to ensure respondents will not encounter any difficulties to answer the questions. Likewise, Churchill (1999) claims that researcher must conduct a pilot test to ensure the success of questionnaire and overall research project. Pilot test is considered as an aid for constructing good questionnaire and helps in detecting range of potential mistakes. For this reason, the researcher aims to conduct at least two pilot-studies before final distribution of the questionnaire.

4.8 Pilot Study

As mentioned above, to ensure research findings are valid and reliable, questionnaire should be tested through pilot studies before final survey. The researcher conducted pilot tests for two main reasons. First, pilot study will enable the researcher to make the required changes in terms of wording and sequencing of the questionnaire. Secondly, it allowed the researcher to eliminate unnecessary and unrelated questions. The researcher conducted two pilot tests.

First Pilot Test: In this pilot study, the researcher distributed questionnaire to 20 students randomly selected in UWS London campus. These students were not only asked to complete the questionnaire but were also requested to provide comments and feedbacks on the length and format of these questions. During this pilot study, the researcher received valuable feedbacks from these respondents about the improvement of the questionnaire.

Second Pilot Test: The researcher conducted a second pilot test to assess the validity and reliability of the questionnaire's item. This pilot study was conducted to further detect any issues or problems the respondents might encounter in the final survey. This time the researcher randomly selected a sample of 50 respondents from two main branches of Barclays and Lloyds Group in London using simple random sampling. These respondents were similar to the final survey respondents. After the completed questionnaire were received, Cronbach's alpha method was used to examine the consistency of the questionnaire. After the questionnaire was refined and validated using two pilot studies, a final version of the questionnaire was designed and distributed across different sources using both physical and electronic distribution.

4.7 Data Analysis Methods

The present study will use different data analysis techniques outlined below:

4.7.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data for the present study will be collected through questionnaire survey, distributed both physically and electronically using Survey Monkey. The quantitative data will be analysed using a software called SPSS. Among, the other quantitative data analysis software, SPSS has proven to be the most prominent and powerful tool for coding and interpreting quantitative data. Firstly, descriptive analysis of the study will be conducted in order to summarize the basic statistics related to the respondents' demographic profile and other constructs based on the percentage. Number of descriptive analysis techniques will be used, such as percentages, frequencies, mean, mode and median. The descriptive results will be illustrated with different bar charts, pie charts and Histogram.

After basic descriptive analysis, the present study will employ various statistical tests in order to test and evaluate the conceptual framework formulated in Chapter three. The tests that will be used are Spearman's rho correlation, Mann-Whitney U, Kruskal Wallis and multiple regression analysis.

4.7.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

Semi-structured interviews are conducted with bank managers in order to collect qualitative data for the present study. Since, the nature of this research is mainly quantitative and findings are based on statistical analysis, the researcher did not conduct an-in-depth qualitative analysis. Researcher conducted a basic narrative analysis regarding the views and opinions of banks' managers about the factors that affect the adoption of internet banking in the UK. The views and opinions of the managers together with questionnaire survey provided the researcher with much broader understandings of the phenomenon being investigated.

Figure 4.4 below outlines the data analysis method for the present study.

Figure 4.4: Data Analysis for the Present Study

Source: This Research

4.8 Reliability and Validity of Measures

According to Lee and Lings (2008) for research data to be of value and of use, it must be both reliable and valid.

4.8.1 Reliability

Reliability refers to the consistency, accuracy and reproducibility of measurement scale. Reliability in research is the degree to which an instrument is free from any random measurement error. An instrument is claimed to be reliable when it consistently measures for what is designed to measure. According to Bryman and Bell (2015) it is very important for the researcher to determine the measurement instrument’s quality as it will minimize inconsistencies and its adverse effect on final results. There are three main types of reliability. The first and most common estimate of reliability is test-retest reliability, which is measured across time and evaluate stability over time. The second most popular method for measuring reliability is the Cronbach’s coefficient alpha method, which measure the internal consistency of an instrument. In this method, reliability coefficient of 0.90 are considered as “excellent”, 0.80 are deemed as “very good” and coefficient around 0.70 are considered as reliable or satisfactory. The third

type of reliability is inter-rater reliability; this estimates reliability based on the rating decision of different judges and observers.

For the present study, the researcher will take the following key steps to ensure the reliability of data. First and foremost, the researcher will use the Cronbach's alpha coefficient method to confirm the reliability of the factors in the questionnaire. Factors with Cronbach's alpha coefficient value of 0.7 and above will be accepted and the rest will be excluded from the study. Secondly, the researcher will conduct at least two pilot studies prior to final survey to increase the reliability of collected data. Third, Conversation for all interviews will be recorded and well-documented notes will be taken for future references.

4.8.2 Validity

Validity is the accuracy and ability of measurement scale to measure what it is supposed to measure (Taylor, 2013). In social science research, there are two main types of validity: content validity and construct validity. Content validity is the extent to which the content of an instrument (questions, observations, logs etc.) accurately measures what the researcher is intending to measure. In simple terms, content validity is the degree to which the items in the questionnaire provide adequate coverage of the issue being investigated (Bryman and Bell, 2015). On the other hand, construct validity defines how well or efficient a measurement scale measures what it is intended to measure.

For this study, the researcher will take every possible step to ensure the data collected is valid. First, survey questionnaire and interview questions are developed according to the research problem, aim and objectives to ensure all aspects of the study are covered. Secondly, both the survey and interview questions will be tested through pilot studies to ensure all the questions are understandable and there are no ambiguities. In addition to pilot test, questionnaire will be reviewed by academic scholars before final distribution to ensure all items in the questionnaire are suitable and appropriate. Third, questionnaire survey and interviews will be conducted in English so there is no chance of ambiguity or error due to translation. Fourth, during the interview, participant will be given enough time to ensure they understand the questions and give correct answer. Fifth, survey questionnaire was also distributed electronically, thus giving the participant enough time to complete the questionnaire. Finally, this study is supervised by three supervisors who constantly monitor the research process to ensure the findings are in line with the overall aim and objectives of this study.

Although the following precautions were taken to ensure the validity and reliability of the overall findings of the research, there might still be some mistakes and errors.

4.9 Ethical Consideration:

Greener (2008) defines ethical consideration as the norms and standards for conducting a research. In other words, ethical consideration determines the difference between acceptable and unacceptable behaviours during research process. The issue of ethics in research is critical because it encourages an environment of trust, accountability and mutual respect among all parties (Pennink and Joker, 2010). The importance of ethics must be considered during all the stages of the research progress.

In the present study, ethics have been considered vigorously during all stages of the research. First and foremost, the researcher has obtained ethical approval from the UWS ethical committee before collecting primary data and will adhere the ethical standards as stated in the UWS code of practice. Secondly, during primary data collection, respondents were given enough time to decide whether or not they want to participate in the study. Covering letter was be attached with the questionnaire stating the purpose of the study which increased respondent's confidence and assurance while filling the questionnaire. Likewise, respondents were assured that the information they provide will be kept highly confidential and will be used and processed solely for the purpose of this research and not for any other purpose whatsoever.

4.10 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter outlined the research methods and strategies used for the present study. The chapter discussed different philosophical assumptions, research approaches and data collection procedures. Justification for the chosen research methods for this study were provided. The issues of ethics, validity and reliability were also highlighted in the last sections of this chapter. In sum, this chapter serves as a bridge between the proposed conceptual framework in the previous chapter and the empirical results which will be presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 5: Data Analysis and Results

5.0 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to conduct descriptive and statistical analysis of the primary data collected for this study. This chapter will summarize the basic statistics based on the percentage.

The final questionnaire survey was conducted over the period of 2 month between March and April 2018. The target population for the current research was the UK internet banking users. In order to maximize the response rate, the questionnaire survey was conducted both electronically (using Survey Monkey platform) and by physical distribution to customers in different bank branches across London. 275 completed questionnaires were received out of the total 400 distributed, giving a response rate of 68.4% of the original sample, which was more than double of what the researcher anticipated. To ensure reliability and validity of the questionnaire, the researcher conducted two pilot tests among 30 UK internet banking users including university students and bank customers. A convenience sampling technique seemed more appropriate for data collection because internet banking users were approached randomly with no restrictions and limitations.

The survey questionnaire had three parts. The first part was the main and most important part that asked respondents about their attitude towards internet banking such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, privacy, security, risk and technology readiness. A 5-point Likert Scale technique is used for the questionnaire (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). The second part of the questionnaire aimed at asking respondents about their general perceptions of internet banking and included mostly multiple-choice questions. The third part was about the respondents' demographic information, such as their age, gender, highest education and employment status etc.

Once the 275 completed questionnaires were received back, data was computed and coded into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Various descriptive and statistical tests were conducted using different techniques, including frequencies and descriptive, mean and standard deviation, independent *t*-tests, cross tabulation and correlation and as well as multiple regression analysis.

5.1 Reliability Analysis of Variables Using Cronbach's Alpha

Prior to conduct descriptive and statistical analysis, it is very important to check the internal consistency of the scales in order to ensure the accuracy of the findings. Cronbach's Alpha method was applied in order to examine the reliability of the measurement scales of the survey.

According to Khan Jan (2015) a coefficient of 0.70 or above are considered as "satisfactory", 0.80 are deemed as "very good" and coefficient of 0.90 or above are considered as "excellent". For the present study, the Cronbach's Alpha was applied to Likert scale questions. Table 5.1 below presents the results of this reliability tests conducted on all Likert scale items.

Table 5.1: Reliability Analysis of Variables of the Proposed Model		
Scale	Number of Item	Cronbach's Alpha Value
Behavioural Intention	3	0.931
Perceived Usefulness	3	0.832
Perceived Ease of Use	3	0.825
Trust	4	0.811
Perceived Risk	3	0.823
Perceived Privacy	2	0.809
Perceived Security	3	0.817
Total Average for all Items	21	0.813

Table 5.1: Reliability Statistics of Variables of the Proposed Model

Source: This Research

It can be noted from the above table that Cronbach's Value for all the scale items is above 0.80 and such high figures indicate that the items in the questionnaire is a good indication of what the researcher is aiming to investigate. The overall composite reliability for the entire questionnaire was also conducted and has a Cronbach's value of 0.813. This demonstrate a good internal consistency and high reliability among the items within factors.

Considering such high reliability, the researcher now moves on to conduct the analysis without removing any of the items from the questionnaire.

5.2 Overall Sample Demographics

The overall demographic profile of the survey respondents shown in Table 5.1 and figure 5.1 shows that out of 275 respondents 147 were male (representing 53.5%) and 128 were female (representing 46.2%). The largest age group who agreed to respond to our survey are those aged 26-35 years (representing 33.5%) followed by the age group 18-25 years (representing 23.6%) and 36-45 (representing 20.5%). 14.5% of the respondents belonged to the age group of 45-59 years, and the remaining 6.8% were at the age of 60 and above.

Majority of the respondents who participated in this study had an undergraduate qualification (accounts for 48.4%), followed by postgraduate or doctorate 25.8%. The remaining 20% of respondents attended college and 5.5% had a secondary school qualification. The employment distribution of the respondents also varied widely. The largest group of the participants were student (36.7%) followed by professionals (31.3%), employee (17.5%), self-employed (8.7%), retired (2.9%), and unemployed (2.9%).

Regarding the internet banking usage, 53.1% of the respondents have accessed and used internet banking for 2 years or more, 23.3% have used it for 1-2 years and 19.6% for less than a year. Only a small proportion of the respondents (3.64%) have not adopted and used the service yet. These findings are in line with the Ceber (2016) research which showed that more than 75% of adults in the UK have access to internet banking. Regarding the amount transferred, 58% of the respondents who have used internet banking have transferred £1,000 or more using online banking, another 28.18% have transferred between £500 - £1000, and the remaining 13.5% have transferred between £50 -£500.

This information is illustrated with bar graphs below in figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Graphical Representation of the Respondents' Demographic Profile
Source: This Research

Table 5.2: Overall Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents			
Demographic Variable	Category	Research Sample (n = 275)	
		Frequency	%age
Gender	Male	147	53.5%
	Female	128	46.5%
Age	18 – 25 Years	55	20%
	26 – 35 Years	92	33.5%
	36 – 45 Years	59	21.5%
	46 – 59 Years	48	17.5%
	60 Years and above	21	7.6%
Highest Education	Secondary School	15	5.5%
	College	55	20%
	Bachelor’s Degree	133	48.4%
	Masters and above	71	25.8%
Employment Status	Student	101	36.7%
	Employee	48	17.5%
	Professional	86	31.3%
	Self-employed	24	8.7%
	Retired	8	2.9%
	Unemployed	8	2.9%
Internet Banking Usage	Never	8	4%
	Less than a Year	54	19.6%
	1 – 2 Years	64	23.3%
	2 Years or More	146	53.1%
Frequency of Usage	Never	10	3.6%
	Once a Week	56	20.4%
	Biweekly	20	7.3%
	Three times a Week	29	10.5%
	Everyday	160	58.2%
Largest amount transferred	Under £50	50	18.2%
	£50 - £500	30	10.9%
	£500 - £1,000	58	21.1%
	Over £1000	137	49.8%

Source: This Research

Note: Data presented in the above Table 5.2 is extracted from SPSS output tables. The detailed SPSS tables containing this data are provided in Appendices.

5.3 Descriptive Analysis of Responses

This section of the chapter aims to conduct some basic statistics related to different constructs examined in the present study.

5.3.1 Respondents' Personal Bank Distribution

As the population for this study was selected on random basis, respondents were asked about their main bank they are banking with. Results revealed that majority of the respondents are customers of Lloyds Bank (35.6 %) which is currently a market leader in the UK retail banking sector. The second largest proportion of respondents were the customers of Barclays Bank (30.5%), followed by HSBC (representing 16.4%) and Royal Bank of Scotland which accounted for 5.5 % of the total population. Very small number of respondents were from Santander (5.5%) and Nationwide (2.5%). It is very interesting to note that majority of the participants are from the three larger banks of the UK, the sample is therefore claimed to be representative of the UK population. Results are presented with a bar graph below in figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Respondents Main Bank of Banking

5.3.2 Frequent Channel of Banking

Respondents were asked to indicate their frequent channel of banking for their daily banking needs. The results revealed that online banking usage was the highest among all channels (56%), followed by branch banking (25.8%). Telephone banking was

found to be the most unpopular banking channel among the respondents, which accounted for only 8% of the total sample. Figure 5.3 below presents these results.

Figure 5.3: Respondents' Frequent Channel of Banking

5.3.3 Frequency of Internet Banking Usage

Respondents were asked about their frequency of accessing and using internet banking on a weekly basis on a scale ranging from never to everyday. It is interesting to note that more than half of the participants (58.2) access and use internet banking every day of the week. The remaining 20.4% use it once a week, 10.5% three times a week and 7.3% use internet banking twice a week. Five respondents were screened out of the sample for this question because they mentioned they have never used internet banking. This information is illustrated with a bar graph below in figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: Respondents' Frequency of Using Internet Banking

5.3.4 Banking Operations Through Internet Banking

Participants were asked regarding the main banking services they use through online banking. It was found that accessing basic account information, making online transfers and managing direct debits and overdrafts are the most frequent banking activities, as they are being used by 75% - 80% of the participants every day. Banking activities such as online bill payments, international transfers and contacting bank were found to be the least frequently used among the participants through online banking.

5.3.5 Respondents Satisfaction with Internet Banking

Respondents for the present study were asked to indicate how satisfied are they with using internet banking services. Their level of satisfaction was measured on a Likert Scale ranging from very dissatisfied to very satisfied. It was found that 69.1% of the participants are happy and satisfied with using internet banking service. Figure 5.6 below shows the overall result for respondent's satisfaction with internet banking services:

Figure 5.6: Satisfaction with Internet Banking

5.3.6 Satisfaction with Internet Banking by Age

Respondents satisfaction level with internet banking was also compared between different age groups. The results found that customers satisfaction with internet banking greatly varies by age. It was found that younger participants are more willing and satisfied with internet banking as compared to older respondents. The largest number of respondents who were satisfied or very satisfied with internet banking are aged between 26 – 45 years, accounts for 44.6% of the total respondents. Whereas, the smallest group who were satisfied with internet banking services are those aged 60 years or above (representing 1.8%).

Table 5. 2 and figure 5.7 below presents users' satisfaction with internet banking according to their age.

How satisfied are you with Internet Banking? * By Age						
Count	Age					Total
	18-25	26-35	36-45	46-59	60 Years or above	
Very Dissatisfied	1	0	1	2	9	13
Dissatisfied	2	4	1	13	7	27
Neutral	5	9	5	22	4	45
Satisfied	27	47	28	9	1	112
Very Satisfied	20	32	24	2	0	78
Total	55	92	59	48	21	275

Figure 5.7: Respondents Satisfaction with Internet Banking by Age

The above results suggest that younger age groups are more technology-savvy and, therefore, have high propensity to use internet banking services. Whereas older individuals feel reluctant and are not satisfied with using internet banking services.

5.3.7 Factors for the Acceptance of Internet Banking

Eight main factors were identified from the literature that positively affect customers' behavioural intention to use internet banking. These factors are: 1) Efficiency, 2) 24/7 availability of banking services, 3) greater control over banking activities, 4) convenience, 5) save time and cost, 6) mobility and accessibility, 7) perceived usefulness, and 8) better communication.

Table 5.3 presents the findings from the survey. It can be noted from table 7-2 that convenience and efficiency has the largest percentage of 83.5% and this seems to be the major factor that positively affect customer's intention to use internet banking. 27/7 availability of banking services to customers is the second major factors of internet banking adoption (77.8%), followed by perceived usefulness, which accounts for 76.3% and as well as speed and efficiency, which accounts for 74.4%. On the other hand, some respondents (46.6%) use internet banking because it gives them greater control over their banking activities and fewer respondents (22.6%) use internet banking for better communication with bank.

Table 5.3: Respondents Acceptance of Internet Banking		
Positive Factors for the Adoption of Internet Banking Services (Multiple Answers)	Research Sample (n = 275)	
	Frequency	Percent %
Internet banking is fast and efficient	198	74.4%
24/7 availability of banking services	203	76.3%
Greater control over my banking activities	124	46.6%
Convenience and efficiency	222	83.5%
Save time and cost	96	36%
Mobility and accessibility	100	37.6%
Perceived usefulness	203	76.3%
Better information and communication	60	22.6%

Note: Detailed SPSS table showing above values are presented in Appendices

Information in the above tables is also illustrated with a bar graph below in Figure 5.3

5.3.8 Factors for Refusing to Use Internet Banking

Literature suggest that despite internet banking being the fastest growing channel, many customers still feel resistance and reluctant to use this service. From the literature 7 main factors were identified that inhibit the adoption of internet banking. these factors are: concern for privacy and security, risk of losing personal and financial data, trust issue, prefer other medium of banking channels, complexity of using the service, dependence on internet and lack of face to face advise. Results are summarized in table 5.4 below:

Customers' perception regarding privacy and security (79.2%) and risk of losing personal and financial data (76.6%) are the main inhibiting factors of internet banking adoption among customers. It is also noted that large number of customers are hesitant to use internet banking because they do not trust the internet banking medium (53.6%) and as well as due to the lack of assistance and face to face advice (35%). Furthermore, 31% of the participants prefer other medium of banking such as branch banking, telephone banking and ATM. On the factors hand factors such as dependence on internet and complexity of using the service are found to have minimum effect on the diffusion of internet banking. This information is also illustrated with a bar graph below in figure 5.4.

Table 5.4: Respondents Refusing to Use Internet Banking		
Reasons for Non-Adoption of Internet Banking (Multiple Answers)	Research Sample (n = 275)	
	Frequency	Percent %
Prefer other medium of services such as branch banking, telephone banking & ATM	85	31.4%
Concerned about privacy and security	217	79.2%
Risk of losing personal and financial data	210	76.6%
Do not trust the internet banking medium	147	53.6%
Internet banking is complex to understand and difficult to use	70	25.5%
Dependence on Internet	27	9.9%
Lack of assistance and face to face advise	96	35%

Note: Detailed SPSS table showing above values are presented in Appendices

Figure 5.8: Respondents Refusing to Use Internet Banking

5.4 Descriptive Analysis of Likert Scale Questions

This section aims to conduct a descriptive analysis of the 7 main constructs of the study. This section will analyse to what degree respondents agree/disagree with statements measuring their perception about internet banking acceptance. All variables are measured on a five-point Likert Scale, ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. Table 5-4 presents the descriptive analysis result for all the constructs.

5.4.1 Intention to Use Internet Banking

Initially, respondents were asked to indicate their intention to use internet banking in the future. Respondents' intention to use internet banking was measured by three items questions, using a five-point Likert Scale.

The findings show that:

1. 72% of the respondent agreed that they will continue to use internet banking in the future for most of their daily banking needs. (Mean = 3.61; SD = 1.01).
2. 73% agreed that in future they will increase the use of internet banking. (Mean = 3.60; SD = 1.08).
3. 68% of the participants recommend others to use internet banking services. (Mean = 3.62; SD = 1.06).

5.4.2 Perceived Usefulness

Respondents' perception of usefulness of internet banking was measured by three items questions. The findings below show that:

1. 68% of the respondents agreed that internet banking is very useful in helping them conduct their daily banking activities. (Mean = 3.73; SD = 1.01)
2. 66 % believe that internet banking offers 24/7 services which are very important to them. (Mean = 3.75; SD = 1.02)
3. 63% mention that internet banking offers them great benefits as compared traditional ways of banking. (Mean = 3.67; SD = 1.01)

5.4.3 Perceived Ease of Use

Respondents' perception regarding ease of use of internet banking was also measured using three-items questions.

The results show that:

1. 64 % of the respondents believe that internet banking services are very easy to use. (Mean 3.67; SD = 1.04)
2. 65% think that internet banking websites have clear and understandable procedures. (Mean = 3.70; SD = 0.981)
3. 69 % agree or strongly agree that conducting banking transactions over the internet does not need a lot of mental efforts. (Mean = 3.72; SD = 0.965)

5.4.4 Perceived Trust

Trust plays a key role in user's decision to accept or reject internet banking services. Respondents' perception of online trust was measure by four-items questions

The findings show that:

1. 53% of the participants trust their bank as a reliable service provider. (Mean = 3.46; SD = 0.960).
2. 54% believe that transactions done through internet banking are secure and private. (Mean = 3.45; SD = 0.940).
3. 53% think that their bank's website has a privacy statement that will guarantee the privacy of their personal data and financial data. (Mean = 3.40; SD = 0.997)
4. 37.9% of the participants considered internet banking as being safe. (Mean = 3.16; SD = 0.934).

5.4.5 Perceived Risk

Perceived Risk construct of internet banking was measured by three items using a five Point Likers Scale.

The findings below show that:

1. 62% of the respondents think that the decision towards the use of internet banking is an opportunity as compared to being a risk. (Mean = 2.50; SD = 1.09).
2. 62.5% believe that the risk of losing personal and financial data associated with internet banking is unlikely to occur. (Mean = 2.48; SD = 1.25).

3. 61% of the respondents consider their overall perception of risk associated with online banking as unlikely to occur. (Mean = 2.35; SD = 1.33).

5.4.6 Perceived Privacy

Respondent's perception of privacy regarding internet banking was measured through 3 items question. The findings suggest that while performing internet banking transactions:

1. 66% of the participants believe that while using internet banking, their personal data will be kept confidential. (Mean = 3.56; SD = 0.721).
2. 62.5% think that their bank confirms identify before accessing their account information. (Mean = 3.63; SD = 1.03).
3. 63% have the view that their bank will not allow unauthorised access to their bank accounts. (Mean = 3.60; SD = 1.03).

5.4.7 Perceived Security

The respondents' perceptions of security in internet banking was measured by three items questions.

The findings suggest:

1. 64% of the respondents think their bank provides 24-hour secure access to online banking. (Mean = 3.67; SD = 1.06)
2. 65% think that the bank has the latest security mechanisms and firewall in place to protect them against online fraud. (Mean = 3.67; SD = 1.04)
3. 67% believe that their bank has consistent online policies and practices. (Mean = 3.67; SD = 1.105).

Table 5.5 below outlines the percentage frequencies for all the above constructs, including the mean and standard deviation results.

Table 5.5: Descriptive Statistics for all Constructs of the Study								
Construct		Response Scale %					Median	SD
		(SD)	(D)	(N)	(A)	(SA)		
Intention	INT1	4.5	14.9	10.9	46.6	23.1	3.69	1.11
	INT2	9.5	10	10.9	45.2	24.4	3.65	1.22
	INT3	5.5	11.6	14.9	51.3	16.4	3.62	1.06
Perceived Usefulness	PU1	0.90	6.4	20.5	34.1	38.2	4.02	.963
	PU2	1.4	7.7	21.8	37.3	31.8	3.90	.982
	PU3	1.4	7.7	21.8	37.3	31.8	3.90	.982
Perceived Ease of Use	PEU1	0.90	11.8	16.4	39.5	31.4	3.89	1.012
	PEU2	0.5	9.5	20	37.3	32.7	3.92	.974
	PEU3	0.5	11.4	21.8	39.1	29.1	3.87	.958
Perceived Trust	TRUST1	1.8	4.1	13.6	42.3	38.2	4.11	.915
	TRUST2	0	1.4	3.2	46.4	39.1	4.23	.725
	TRUST3	0.5	0.9	17.7	38.6	42.3	4.21	.797
	TRUST4	0.5	3.2	14.5	47.7	34.1	4.12	.802
Perceived Risk	RISK1	9.1	17.7	27.7	32.3	13.2	3.23	1.160
	RISK2	9.5	20	21.4	28.6	20.5	3.30	1.265
	RISK3	10.9	18.6	20.9	34.1	15.5	3.25	1.1236
Perceived Privacy	PRIV1	0.5	3.2	14.5	48.2	33.6	4.11	.800
	PRIV2	0.5	0.90	10.5	43.2	45	4.31	.732
	PRIV3	1.9	5.4	14.9	49.7	28.1	4.11	.697
Perceived Security	PSEC1	0.5	1.8	11.4	38.2	48.2	4.32	.781
	PSEC2	0	0.90	11.4	42.3	45.5	4.32	.709
	PSEC3	0	0.5	9.1	45.9	44.5	4.35	.661
	PSEC4	0.90	1.4	11.4	47.3	39.1	4.22	.771

Source: This Research

5.5 Role of Demographics in the Acceptance of Internet Banking

One major objective of this study was to investigate the role of demographic characteristics on user's adoption decision process. This section focuses on the impact of respondents' gender, age and education level on their internet banking adoption decision. Table 5.5 below presents the results.

Table 5.6 Role of Demographics in Internet Banking Adoption

Demographic Variable	Perceived Usefulness	Ease of use	Behavioural Intention
<i>Age</i>			
18-25 years	4.35	4.11	4.25
26-35 years	4.21	4.09	4.33
36-45 years	4.11	4.12	4.09
46 years and above	2.89	3.22	2.89
<i>Gender</i>			
Male	4.11	4.31	4.09
Female	4.09	4.22	4.02
<i>Education Level</i>			
No formal Education	4.20	4.12	4.09
Secondary School	4.11	4.04	3.89
College	4.34	4.11	4.27
Bachelor's Degree	4.21	4.35	4.01
Master and above	3.98	4.21	4.23

Note: Results are based on mean responses

It can be noted from the above table 5.6 that there are differences between the age groups on all dimension of TAM ("PU", "PEU" and "Behavioural Intention"). Among the three dimensions of TAM, respondents aged 26-36 years had a more favourable perception of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness when compared to other aged groups. It is noted from the table that younger respondents are more IT savvy and, therefore, are more willing to use internet banking as compared to older participants. More specifically, majority of the users of internet banking are younger aged groups, and these finding are consistent with Shiraz (2014) who claims that customer's age significantly influence their internet banking usage. The findings also revealed that

older respondents do not favour internet banking usage and they are more likely to stick to traditional banking services.

Gender, on the other hand, was found to have no significant impact on all the three dimensions of TAM. The results indicate that males and female participants rate all three dimensions (“PU”, “PEU”, “Behavioural Intention”) in the same direction and with same level of importance. These findings are consistent with Sharma et al (2014) who claims that there are no differences in the way males and female perceive new technologies.

Regarding the level of education, findings revealed that differences occur only in the “perceived ease of use” among different level of education. Ease of use is rated lower by respondents with low level of education as compared to those with higher education level. However, perceived usefulness and behavioural intention were rated similar among the respondents with different educational background. In sum, education level is not considered to be a significant moderator of internet banking acceptance. These findings are in line with Marakarkandy & Dasgupta 2015 and Lassar et al (2005) who stated that customer’s education level does not affect in the way they perceive new technology products and services.

5.6 Statistical Analysis

This section of the chapter aims to present statistical analysis using SPSS version 25.0. In the present study, various statistical tests were used to test the hypotheses presented in chapter six. The first thing in any statistical procedure is to decide whether to use parametric or non-parametric test.

5.6.1 Parametric vs Non-Parametric Test?

Statistical testing procedure generally falls into two categories: parametric and non-parametric. The choice between parametric and non-parametric statistical approach depends on the normality of the data being examined. Parametric test is based on the assumption that the data being tested is normally distributed and the dependent variable is measured on a continuous scale (Mustafa et al, 2003; Fareed, 2007; Hair et al, 2009). On the other hand, if the data is not normally distributed and the dependent variable is measured on a nominal or ordinal scale, then a non-parametric testing approach is more appropriate to use.

Therefore, prior to conduct inferential statistics, the present study measures the normality of data using two tests: Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk analysis. If the results from these tests are statistically significant (i.e., p value <0.05) then this suggests that the data is not normally distributed. Results are presented in Table 5.7 below:

Table 5.7: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Behavioural Intention	.314	272	.000	.814	272	.000
Perceived Usefulness	.282	272	.000	.858	272	.000
Perceived Ease of Use	.266	272	.000	.873	272	.000
Trust	.243	272	.000	.890	272	.000
Perceived Risk	.298	272	.000	.858	272	.000
Perceived Privacy	.395	272	.000	.699	272	.000
Perceived Security	.272	272	.000	.869	272	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Since the p value is less than 0.05 for all the variables, this confirms that the data for this research deviates from normal distribution. The present study therefore will follow the non-parametric route. Detailed normality assessment using Histogram and Skewness and Kurtosis is presented in Appendices.

5.6.2 Non-Parametric Statistical Tests Used for This Study

Since the data for the present study was measured on Likert Scale and is also not normally distributed, several non-parametric statistical tests are used to test the hypotheses. Spearman's rho correlation was used to show the relationship between dependent variable (intention to use internet banking) and six independent variables – PU, PEU, Trust, Perceived Privacy, Perceived Security and Perceived Risk. The strength of a correlation ranges from -1 (representing strong negative relationship) to +1 (representing strong positive relationship).

Mann Whitney U test and Kruskal Wallis tests were carried out to compare the means between different groups of respondents.

Finally, Multiple Regression analysis was conducted to examine the combined effect of five independent variables on customer intention to use internet banking.

Table 5.8 below outlines different statistical tests used for this study and as well as their purpose.

Table 5-8: Non-Parametric Statistical Tests Used for this Study.	
Test Used	Purpose
Spearman's rho Correlation	To examine the relationship between main variables of this study.
Mann Whitney U Test	To assess the role of gender on the adoption of internet banking.
Kruskal Wallis Test	To investigate whether respondents' gender, age and education level have an effect on their intention to adopt internet banking.
Multiple Regression Analysis	To investigate the combined effect of PU, PEU, Trust, Perceived risk and Age on customer intention to use internet banking.

Source: This Research

5.6.3 CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Spearman's rho correlation was used to show the relationship between different variables of the study. Correlations varies from strong negative to positive according to the guidelines presented by Fink (1995). These guidelines are illustrated in the Table 5.9 below:

Coefficient Range	Strength of Association
± .80 to ± 1.00	Strong relationship
± .61 to ± .80	Moderate relationship
± .41 to ± .60	Weak relationship
± .21 to ± .40	Very weak relationship
± .00 to ± .20	Little or no relationship

Source: Fink (1995)

The correlations for every independent variable that affects the dependent variable (behavioural intention) are analysed and discussed individually.

5.6.3.1 PU, PEU and Intention to Use Internet Banking

It was noted from the literature and conceptual framework that customer's behavioural intention (BI) to use internet banking is directly influenced by two independent variables, namely perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEU). Spearman's correlation was used to examine this relationship and the results revealed that there is a moderate positive relationship between perceived usefulness and intention to use internet banking (0.649, $p=0.000$) and perceived ease of use and intention to use internet banking (0.667, $p=0.000$). The below table 5.10 illustrates the correlations result:

		Behavioural Intention	Perceived Usefulness	Perceived Ease of Use
Perceived Usefulness	Spearman's rho Correlation	.649		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
Perceived Ease of Use	Spearman's rho Correlation	.667	.626	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	275	275	275

Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher's own work

The data presented in Table 5.10 clearly demonstrates that both PU and PEU has an impact on the likelihood to use internet banking. The *p value* for both the variables is < 0.05, meaning that the relationship between PU, PEU and behavioural intention is truly significant, providing that *H2* and *H3* should be accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected. Moreover, it is also noted from the above table that both PU and PEU are positively correlated (0.626, $p=0.000$). Thus, *H4* should also be also be supported.

5.6.3.2 Trust and Intention to Use Internet Banking

The second most important factor affecting customer's intention is the issue of trust. The present study hypothesized that high level of online trust positively influences customer's intention to accept and use internet banking services. Spearman's rho correlation was used to examine this relationship, and the findings are provided in Table 5.11 below:

		Behavioural Intention	Trust 1	Trust 2	Trust 3
Trust 1	Spearman's rho Correlation	.530			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
Trust 2	Spearman's rho Correlation	.545	.626		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
Trust 3	Spearman's rho Correlation	.591	.626	.455	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	275	275	275	

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

KEY

Trust 1 = I trust my bank as a reliable service provider.

Trust 2 = Transactions conducted over internet banking are secure and private.

Trust 3 = My bank's website has a protective legal and technological structure that will protect me against online fraud.

Correlations result shows that all the three dimensions of trust has a significant positive impact on customer's intention to use internet banking services. The *p value* for all trust the items is < 0.05 which is a clear indication that online trust positively affects behavioural intention. However, customer's perception regarding the structural assurance of bank's website was found more significant than the other dimensions of trust (0.591, $p=0.000$). Based on these findings, *H5* of the present study should be accepted and null hypotheses of no relationship should be rejected.

5.6.3.3 Perceived Privacy and Online Trust

Internet banking literature suggests that the issue of privacy plays an integral role in user's intention to accept or reject online banking. The present study hypothesises that high level of perceived privacy positively influences customer's willingness to trust and use online banking. Spearman's rho was carried out for investigating the link between perceived privacy and online trust. Results are presented in Table 5.12:

		Online Trust	Privacy 1	Privacy 2	Privacy 3
Privacy 1	Spearman's rho Correlation	.452			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
Privacy 2	Spearman's rho Correlation	.550	.511		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
Privacy 3	Spearman's rho Correlation	.583	.508	.623	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	275	275	275	

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

KEY

Privacy 1 = My personal information on internet banking is kept confidential.

Privacy 2 = My bank confirms my identity before accessing my account information.

Privacy 3 = My bank will not allow unauthorised access to my bank account.

Results from Table 5.12 suggests significant positive relationship between privacy and online trust. Since the *p value* for all dimensions of privacy is < 0.05 , *H8* of the present study should also be supported. It can be concluded from the above results that high level of perceived privacy positively affects customer’s perception of online trust.

5.6.3.4 Perceived Security and Online Trust

Customer’s perception of security was assumed to positively affect customer’s perception of online trust. Correlation analysis was conducted to examine this relationship. Results are presented below in table 5.13.

Table 5.13: Correlation Analysis of Perceived Security and Trust					
		Online Trust	Security 1	Security 2	Security 3
Security 1	Spearman’s rho Correlation	.612			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
Security 2	Spearman’s rho Correlation	.634	.615		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
Security 3	Spearman’s rho Correlation	.654	.692	.624	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	275	275	275	

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

KEY

Security 1 = My Bank provides 24/7 secure access to online banking

Security 2 = My bank has the latest security mechanisms in place to protect me against online fraud.

Security 3 = My bank has consistent online policies and practices.

The correlation result from Table 5.13 suggests the existence of moderate positive relationship between perceived security and online trust. The *p value* for all the dimensions of security are < 0.05 , which suggest significant correlations between security and trust. This analysis leads the researcher to the conclusion that *H9* of the present study should be accepted and the null hypothesis of no relationship is rejected.

5.6.3.5 Risk and Intention to Use Online Banking

The present study hypothesised that customer's perception of risk negatively affects their willingness to engage in electronic banking services. Customer's perception of risk was measured by two items questions (see risk 1 and risk 2 below). This relationship was also examined using Spearman's rho correlation. Results are provided in Table 5.14 below:

		Behavioural Intention	Risk 1	Risk 2
Risk 1	Spearman's rho Correlation	-.552		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
Risk 2	Spearman's rho Correlation	-.609	.756	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	275	275	275

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table 5.14 clearly illustrates that there is a strong negative relationship between perceived risk and intention to use internet banking ($-0.680, p = 0.000$; $-0.745, p = 0.000$). These findings are in line with Kumar et al, (2009) that customer's risk perception negatively affect their willingness to engage in electronic banking behaviour. Based on these findings, the present study support $H7$ and rejects the null hypothesis.

This relationship is also illustrated with a scatterplot below in figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9: Relationship Between Perceived Risk and Behavioural Intention
Source: This Research

From the scatterplot, we can discern that a line descending from right to left showing a negative correlation between behavioural intention and risk. It can be noted that as perceived risk increase, intention to use internet banking decreases.

5.6.3.6 Trust and Perceived Risk

It was found from the above discussion that customer’s risk perception negatively affects his/her intention towards the use of online banking. However, the present study hypothesised, based on literature, that high level of customer trust leads to low perceived risk. Spearman’s rho Correlation was used to examine this relationship and the findings show that:

		Perceived Risk	Perceived Trust
Perceived Trust	Spearman’s rho Correlation	-.578**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	275	275

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

It is evident from Table 5.15 there is a moderate negative relationship between trust and perceived risk. This mean that as the level of trust increases, customer’s perception of risk will decrease. Therefore, *H6* of the present study is accepted and null hypothesis of no relationship is rejected.

5.6.3.7 Trust, Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use

Based on trust literature, it was hypothesised that high level of online banking trust positively influences customer’s perception of PU. Furthermore, it was also assumed that PEU has a positive impact on customer’s trust. These relationships are examined using correlation analysis and the results are provided in Table 5.16 below:

		Trust	Perceived Usefulness	Perceived Ease of Use
Perceived Usefulness	Spearman’s rho Correlation	0.057		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.173		
Perceived Ease of Use	Spearman’s rho Correlation	0.128	.626	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.02	.000	
	N	275	275	275

** . Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation analysis indicates no relationship between online trust and perceived usefulness. The *p value* is > 0.05 , the present study accepts the null hypothesis of no relationship and rejects the alternative hypothesis. In sum, the *H10* of the present study is not supported, meaning that there is no relationship between PU and online trust. The findings also suggest a weak correlation between PEU and online trust (0.012, $p = 0.02$). *H11* of the present study is supported; however, the relationship is not significant.

5.6.2 KRUSKAL-WALLIS ANALYSIS BY AGE

The present study carried out Kruskal – Wallis analysis in order to investigate if customer’s age has an impact on their decision to use internet banking services. Kruskal-Wallis analysis is used because the data for the present study is non-parametric and not normally distributed.

Kruskal-Wallis test (alternative to the one-way ANOVA) is a non-parametric test that is used to determine if there is statistically significant difference between two or more groups of an independent variable, for example age of respondents in this study. If the group means are not significantly different then it is concluded that age does not have an effect on online banking adoption. Results are provided in Table 5.17 below:

Table 5.17 Kruskal Wallis by AGE (Internet Usage Behaviour)						
Usage	Age	N	Mean Rank	SD	H-Value	Sig
Intention to use internet banking					124.5	P <0.001
	18-24 years	55	169.43			
	26 -35 years	92	167.02			
	36- 45 years	59	158.08			
	45 -59 years	48	60.81			
	60 and above	21	47.17			
Perceived usefulness (PU)					94.6	P <0.001
	18-24 years	55	169.55			
	26 -35 years	92	164.38			
	36- 45 years	59	155.19			
	45 -59 years	48	68.19			
	60 and above	21	51.07			
Perceived ease of use (PEU)					104.6	P <0.001
	18-24 years	55	166.92			
	26 -35 years	92	171.41			
	36- 45 years	59	151.76			
	45 -59 years	48	61.78			
	60 and above	21	51.45			
Perceived Trust					47.4	P <0.001
	18-24 years	55	166.92			

	26 -35 years	92	158.52			
	36- 45 years	59	152.25			
	45 -59 years	48	84.46			
	60 and above	21	82.79			
Perceived Privacy					65.3	P <0.001
	18-24 years	55	156.75			
	26 -35 years	92	158.60			
	36- 45 years	59	149.74			
	45 -59 years	48	78.40			
	60 and above	21	87.00			
Perceived Security					83.6	P <0.001
	18-24 years	55	163.65			
	26 -35 years	92	160.86			
	36- 45 years	59	161.89			
	45 -59 years	48	75.55			
	60 and above	21	46.31			
Perceived Risk					78.09	P <0.001
	18-24 years	55	108.01			
	26 -35 years	92	116.99			
	36- 45 years	59	118.62			
	45 -59 years	48	207.93			
	60 and above	21	203.21			

Source: This Research

The results displayed in Table 5.17 clearly shows significant differences in means between the age groups for each internet banking category. These findings suggest that younger age groups are more willing to use internet banking services as compared to older individuals. We can see that the *p value* for all internet banking categories is less than 0.05 which suggests that there is statistically significant difference between the age groups of respondents. These findings lead us to conclusion that customers' age does play a significant role in his/her acceptance of internet banking. Therefore, *H12* of the present study should be accepted and null hypothesis of no difference is not supported. **Note:** Data presented in the above Table 5.17 is extracted from SPSS output tables. The detailed SPSS tables are provided below in Appendices.

5.6.3 KRUSKAL-WALLIS ANALYSIS BY EDUCATION LEVEL

Apart from age, the present study also hypothesised that customer's level of education plays a role in their adoption decision process. To investigate this, Kruskal-Wallis test is carried out to find the mean differences between respondents based on their level of education. Results are presented in Table 5.18 below:

Table 5.18: Kruskal Wallis Analysis by Education Level					
Usage	Education Level	N	Mean Rank	H-Value	Sig
Intention to use internet banking				7.087	P = .69
	Secondary School	15	175.53		
	College	55	138.40		
	Bachelor's Degree	133	129.98		
	Masters & Above	71	144.54		
Perceived usefulness (PU)				6.090	P = .107
	Secondary School	15	180.97		
	College	55	139.06		
	Bachelor's Degree	133	131.24		
	Masters & Above	71	138.82		
Perceived ease of use (PEU)				3.562	P = .313
	Secondary School	15	166.70		
	College	55	136.46		
	Bachelor's Degree	133	131.47		
	Masters & Above	71	143.42		

Source: This Research

It is clearly noted from the above Table 5.18 that there are no significant differences in means between the education level of respondents. Since the *p value* for all the three dimensions of internet banking is greater than 0.05, level of education is found to have no effect on customer's intention to accept and use online banking. Therefore, *H13* of the present study is not supported and null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted.

5.6.4 MANN-WHITNEY U TEST

Mann-Whitney U Test is carried out to compare the means between the gender of respondents (male and female). This test will help to determine whether male and female perceive internet banking differently or not.

Mann-Whitney U test is used to compare differences between two independent groups from the same population, for instance, gender of respondent in this study. Mann-Whitney U test is chosen because the data for this research is non-parametric and not normally distributed.

Table 5.19 below shows the results:

Table 5.19: Mann Whitney Test for Gender of Respondents					
Usage	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Z-Value	Sig
Behavioural Intention (BI)				-1.056	P = .291
	Male	147	132.90		
	Female	128	142.75		
Perceived usefulness (PU)				-0.088	P = .930
	Male	147	137.61		
	Female	128	138.45		
Perceived ease of use (PEU)				0.203	P = .839
	Male	147	137.11		
	Female	128	139.02		

Source: This Research

It is clearly noted from the above Table 5.19 that there are no differences between mean ranks for male and female for all the dimensions of internet banking. The *p value* is greater than .05 suggesting that customer's gender does not influence their decision to accept and use internet banking services. This leads us to conclusion that null hypothesis of no differences across the gender should be accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected. In summary, *H14* of the present study is not supported.

The above data is graphically illustrated below in figure 5.10.

Intention to Use Internet Banking

Perceived Usefulness

Perceived Ease of Use

Figure 5.10: Mann-Whitney U Test for Gender

It is clear from the above figures that there is no significant difference between the mean rank of male and female towards using online banking. Therefore, customer's gender does not significantly influence the adoption of internet banking.

Note: Data presented in the above Table 5.19 is extracted from SPSS output tables. The detailed SPSS tables containing this data are provided in Appendices.

5.6.5 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis is conducted to examine how and to what extent the various internet banking factors affect customer intention to use internet banking. Multiple regression is a useful technique that is used to analyse the link between one or more independent variables and a single dependent variable (Fareed et al, 2005). This analysis will help the researcher to obtain the overall variance explained by the model (also known as R²) and as well as the individual impact of each independent variables on the dependent variable (intention to use internet banking).

Assumptions for Multiple Regression Analysis:

One of the main assumptions of the MRA is that the dependent variables should be interval (i.e., it should be measured on a continuous scale). However, for the present study the dependent variable was measured on a Likert Scale and is ordinal in nature. To meet this assumption of MRA, the researcher treated the dependent variable (intention to use internet banking) as interval by computing three question items, which measured behavioural intention, into a single variable. The new computed dependent variable became an interval variable. This process is carried out based on the recommendation of previous researches including Hair et al, (2003); Jamieson, S (2004) and Carifeo and Perla (2007). From these discussions, it can be concluded that by computing the independent variable into a single variable, this study now meets the assumption of multiple regression analysis (Hair et al, 2005).

Regression Analysis Results:

The present study carried out multiple regression using five main variables: perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived trust, perceived risk and customer's age as the independent variables and "intention to use internet banking" as the dependent variable. Table 5.20 to Table 5.22 provide the results of the regression analysis.

Table 5.20: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.872 ^a	.760	.756	.48551	1.821

a. Predictors: Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Trust, Perceived Risk, Age

b. Dependent Variable: Behavioural Intention

From Table 5.20 it can be observed that the coefficient of determination (also called R²) is 0.760, representing that the regression model explained 76% of the variance in the model. In other words, 76% of consumer intention to use internet banking is explained by five independent variables. (perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust, perceived risk and customer age). Based on Cohen's (1990) rule of effect size, the independent variables for the present study explained a relatively large variance in the dependent variable. Furthermore, the Durbin-Watson value is 1.82 which is more than 1 and less than 3. Therefore, the Multicollinearity assumption of the multiple regression analysis is also met (Hair et al, 2010; Joseph et al, 2010). The next table 5.21 provides the model of fit statistics.

Table 5.21: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	200.186	5	40.037	169.849	.000^b
	Residual	63.174	268	.236		
	Total	263.360	273			

a. Dependent Variable: Behavioural Intention

b. Predictors: Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Trust, Perceived Risk, Age

From Table 5.21, it can be noted that the model is statistically significant at 0.05 percent level (p -value = 0.000). This means that the regression model was reasonably fit and there was statistically significant relationship between the combination of independent variables and customer intention to use internet banking. In sum, the p value is less than

0.05 which suggest that the regression model is appropriate, and results are reliable. The individual coefficient results are provided in Table 5-22 below.

Table 5.22: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.650	.288		5.733	.000
	Perceived Usefulness	.328	.043	.338	7.561	.000
	Perceived Ease of Use	.236	.043	.251	5.499	.000
	Trust	.168	.037	.164	4.510	.000
	Perceived Risk	-.147	.037	-.164	-3.959	.000
	Age	-.131	.031	-.161	-4.218	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Behavioural Intention

Looking at the individual variables of the model, it was found that perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.338$, $p < 0.01$), perceived ease of use ($\beta = 0.251$, $p < 0.01$) and Trust ($\beta = 0.164$, $p < 0.01$) had a positive and significant impact on customer intention to use internet banking. Therefore, H2, H3 and H4 of the present study is supported. It should also be noted that perceived usefulness has the highest influence on the dependent variable ($\beta = 0.338$, $p < 0.01$) as compared to perceived ease of use and perceived trust. This indicate that perceived usefulness is the most important determinant of internet banking adoption. Meanwhile, perceived risk ($\beta = -0.147$, $p < 0.01$) and consumer age ($\beta = -0.131$, $p < 0.01$) were negatively related to customer intention to use internet banking. Hence H7 and H12 of the present study is also supported.

To summarize, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and trust were positively and significantly related to customer intention to use internet banking. However, perceived risk and customer age were found to have a negative impact on customer intention. And these independent variables together predicted **76%** of the variance on customer intention to use internet banking.

The next section provides the summary of hypothesis testing.

5.7 Summary of Hypothesis Testing

Fourteen hypotheses generated in the conceptual framework chapter are reviewed and tested individually in this section. The decision whether to support or reject these hypotheses is based on the above statistical analysis:

H2: There is a positive relationship between perceived usefulness and intention to use internet banking.

The correlation analysis for this hypothesis was both positive and significant (0.649, $p < 0.000$). This suggests the existence of significant effect of perceived usefulness on the adoption of internet banking services. Therefore, this hypothesis is supported. Usefulness of internet banking significantly influences customer's intention.

H3: There is a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and intention to use internet banking.

The correlation analysis for this hypothesis was also positive and significant (0.649, $p < 0.000$). Ease of use of internet banking was found to have strong and positive effect on behavioural intention. Therefore, this hypothesis is supported, and the null hypothesis of no relationship is rejected.

H4: PEU of internet banking positively influences perceived usefulness.

The correlation result for the above hypothesis suggests a positive and significant relationship between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness (0.649, $p < 0.000$). Therefore, this hypothesis of the present study is also supported.

H5: There is a positive relationship between online trust and intention to use internet banking services.

The impact of trust on behavioural intention was measured through a 3-items question related to online trust (trust 1, trust 2 and trust 3). The correlation results indicated a positive and significant relationship between all the three dimensions of trust and behavioural intention. The *p value* for all trust items was < 0.001 suggesting the existence of significant effect of online trust on customer's intention. Therefore, this hypothesis is supported.

H6: High level of customer trust leads to low perceived risk.

The correlation results for this hypothesis was both positive and significant (0.649, $p < 0.000$). This result supports the above hypothesis that high level of online trust reduces customer's perception of risk regarding internet banking usage. Therefore, this hypothesis is accepted, and null hypothesis is rejected.

H7: There is a negative relationship between perceived risk and customer's intention to use internet banking.

The correlation results for this hypothesis was negative and significant. Both the dimensions of risk were negatively correlation with intention to use internet banking services (0.649, $p < 0.000$); 0.649, $p < 0.000$;). These findings support the above hypothesis that customer's perception of risk negatively affect their intention towards internet banking). Thus, this hypothesis is supported.

H8: There is a positive relationship between perceived privacy and online trust.

The correlation result for this hypothesis is also both positive and significant. Both dimensions of perceived privacy were found to be significantly correlated with online trust (PRI 1= 0.649, $p < 0.000$); PRI 2= 0.649, $p < 0.000$;). This hypothesis of present study is accepted.

H9: There is a positive relationship between perceived security and online trust.

The correlation result for the above hypothesis is both positive and significant. All the three dimensions of perceived security were found to significantly correlate with online trust (sec 1= 0.649, $p < 0.000$); sec 2= 0.649, $p < 0.000$; sec 3= 0.649, $p < 0.000$). This hypothesis is supported, and null hypothesis is rejected.

H10: High level of trust in internet banking positively influences perceived usefulness of internet banking.

The correlation analysis for this hypothesis was both weak and insignificant (0.649, $p < 0.000$). The result indicates no significant relationship between online trust and perceived usefulness. Therefore, this hypothesis is rejected, and null hypothesis is supported.

H11: Perceived ease of use of internet banking has positive impact on customer's trust. The correlation result for the above hypothesis was positive but weak (0.649, $p < 0.000$). Although this hypothesis is supported, the relationship is very weak.

H12: Customer's age has an impact on their choice to use internet banking. This hypothesis was tested using a Kruskal-Wallis test by comparing the mean scores of respondents towards different internet banking categories. The results for this hypothesis were both positive and significant. The *p value* for PU, PEU, and BI was < 0.001 , thus suggesting a significant difference between different age groups of respondents. Based on this result, this hypothesis is supported that customer's age has an impact on their choice to use internet banking.

H13: Customer's education level has an impact on their choice to use internet banking. The Kruskal-Wallis analysis for this hypothesis was both weak and insignificant (0.649, $p < 0.000$). This suggest that customer's level of education does not impact on their choice of internet banking use. Therefore, this hypothesis is rejected.

H14: Customer's gender has an impact on their choice to use internet banking. Mann-Whitney U test analysis for this hypothesis was also weak and insignificant (0.649, $p < 0.000$). This suggest that customer's gender does not impact their choice of internet banking use. Therefore, this hypothesis is also rejected.

In summary, majority of the proposed hypotheses were supported as expected by the researcher (see Table 5.23 and Figure 5.11 below). Three main hypothesized factors (Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and online trust) were found to have significant positive impact on behavioural intention. However, perceived risk was found to be negatively correlated with behavioural intention. Regarding the impact of demographic characteristics, gender and level of education was found to have no effect on customer's choice of internet banking; however, age was found to be influential. Table 5-23 presents the summary of hypotheses testing.

Table 5.23: Summary of Hypotheses Testing			
No	Hypothesis Description	Significance	Result
H2	Perceived Usefulness → Behavioural Intention	0.001	Supported
H3	Perceived Ease of Use → Behavioural Intention	0.001	Supported
H4	PEU → PU	0.001	Supported
H5	Online Trust → Behavioural Intention	0.001	Supported
H6	Online Trust → Perceived Risk	0.001	Supported
H7	Perceived Risk → Behavioural Intention	0.001	Supported
H8	Perceived Privacy → Online Trust	0.001	Supported
H9	Perceived Security → Online Trust	0.001	Supported
H10	Online Trust → Perceived Usefulness	0.173	Not Supported
H11	Perceived Ease of Use → Online Trust	0.02	Supported
H12	Age → Behavioural Intention	0.001	Supported
H13	Gender → Behavioural Intention	0.291	Not Supported
H14	Level of Education → Behavioural Intention	0.721	Not Supported

Source: This Research

These hypothesized relationships are also illustrated in figure 5.11 below.

Figure 5.11: Internet Banking Acceptance Model

Source: This Research

5.8 One-One Interviews with Bank Managers

Apart from the questionnaire survey, the present study also collected primary data through semi-structured interviews with the bank managers. The researcher interviewed a total of 5 bank managers from 5 major high street banks, including Lloyds, Barclays, NatWest, HSBC and RBS. The views and opinions of these banks' managers provided the researcher with in-depth information of the factors influencing the adoption of internet banking in the UK. Table 5-24 outlines the interview respondents who agreed to participate in this study. Detailed interview questions are provided in Appendices.

Table 5.24: Face-to-Face Interviews for the Present Study			
	Bank Name	Interviewee Position	Date and Time of Interview
Interviewee 1	Barclays (Edgware)	Branch Manager	12/06/2018 1:30pm – 2pm
Interviewee 2	Lloyds (Edgware)	Branch Manager	15/06/2018 3:15pm – 3:45pm
Interviewee 3	HSBC (Kilburn)	Business Development Manager	16/06/2018 10:30 am – 10:50
Interviewee 4	NatWest (Hendon)	Branch Manger	20/06/2018 11 am – 11:30am
Interviewee 5	RBS (Finchley)	Business Manager	30/06/2018 12:15 pm – 12:40

5.8.1 Interviewees' Responses

Question One: *Do you think the usefulness of internet banking influence customer's intention towards its usage?*

Result: All the respondents agreed that usefulness of internet banking positively influence customer's intention to accept and use internet banking services.

The most positive view was presented by interviewee 1 who stated that: "Internet banking is providing our customers with far more advantages and convenience as compared to branch banking, and this is one of the main reasons why these customers prefer this channel of banking".

Interviewee 2 also agreed to the above statement and answered that:

"Our customers are shifting from traditional banking to using online banking because of the numerous advantages it offers". He further states that internet banking benefits

such as convenience, time saving, and mobility are the some of the main factors that encourage our customers to shift from branch banking to digital banking

Interviewee 3 answer to the above question was also not very different. He mentioned that “based on a very recent survey we found that our consumers find online banking as more user-friendly and innovative self-service technology that give them more autonomy in performing their daily banking transactions. He extended his view by stating that “greater the perceived usefulness of internet banking, the more likely our customers will adopt and use this service”.

Interviewee 4 added that “our customers enjoy various tangible benefits associated with internet banking such as faster transactions, increased financial transparency, and the availability of 24/7 services and because of these benefits they are shifting towards this channel at a very fast pace”.

Interviewee 5 stated that “digital banking saves time and cost, allow our customers to see their banking data instantly, and make their life much easier and enjoyable and due to these perceived benefits, our bank have experienced a huge shift from traditional banking to digital banking”.

Main Themes Derived from Question 1:

- Internet banking provides numerous advantages
- Internet banking is far more convenient
- Internet banking is more user-friendly and innovative than traditional banking
- Faster transactions, increased financial transparency and greater perceived usefulness

Brief Discussion of Results

It can be noted from the above themes and responses that all the Interviewees agree that perceived usefulness does influence the adoption and acceptance of internet banking in the UK. The main points from derived from the above responses shows that perceived usefulness in the form of relative advantage, abundant information, reliability, time and monetary savings are all critical to the success of online banking. Furthermore, the above responses suggest that internet banking users are more likely to perceive the relative advantage of the service. Another interpretation is that customers do not use internet banking for its own sake but instead use it because its attributes that drive value.

Literature suggests two types of benefits customers will get through internet banking; direct and indirect. Direct benefits refer to immediate and tangible benefits customers would enjoy by using internet banking such as faster transactions, speed, and increased financial transparency. Indirect benefits are less tangible and difficult to measure such as allowing customers to perform banking transactions anywhere in the world and enjoy a 24-hour service. For this reason, this research verifies PU to have great effect on attitude and intentions of customers to adopt and use internet banking in the UK.

Question Two: *As a bank manager, to what extent do you think the ease of use of internet banking affects customer's intention towards using this service?*

Result: Almost all the participants agreed that the ease of use of internet banking positively affects customers' intention towards using this service.

Interviewee 1 outlined his view by stating that "our bank believes that the ease of use of internet banking is the strongest predictor that keeps our customers continued acceptance and usage of internet banking. He further mentioned that "we continue working in making sure that our internet banking platform are as user-friendly as possible for our customers".

Interviewee 2 reply was also not very different than that of interviewee 1. He states that "in UK's highly competitive retail banking market if customer find internet banking too hard to use they will shift to our competitor".

Interviewee 3 answer to the above question was "when our internet banking platforms are easier to use and navigate, it is more likely to be adopted by our customers. He also stated that "perceived ease of use has a dual effect, direct as well as indirect, on our customers' intention to continue using internet banking and this is the reason our bank continuously ensure the provision of effortless and user-friendly service".

Interviewee 4 stated that "banks in the UK must continually redesign its website with an intention to enhance usability and ease of use.

Interviewee 5 also fully supported the view that ease of use positively affects customers' intention to use internet banking services. He stated that "today customers are extremely impatient about not receiving immediate assistance and feel resistance to adopt technology that is complicated to operate".

Main Themes Derived from Question 2:

- User-friendliness
- Enhance usability and ease of Use
- Complex and complicated technology is not accepted by customers

Brief Discussion of Results

It is clear from the interviewees' responses and above themes that perceived ease of use has a significant and positive impact on the adoption of internet banking. Almost all the managers were of the view the perceived ease of use is the strongest predictor that keeps customers continued acceptance and usage of internet banking. The lack of user-friendliness and ease of use are the factors that will diffuse the acceptance of internet banking among customers. It was found from the quantitative analysis that even if potential customer believe that internet banking is useful, they will at the same time believe the system is too hard to use and that performance benefits of usage are outweighed by effort of using the application or system.

The success of the acceptance of internet banking depends on the level of its ease-of-use and user-friendliness. Customers will only conduct online banking transactions only if they find that the website is enjoyable and easy to navigate. Based on the above discussion, the present study suggest that higher the ease of use and user-friendliness of internet banking website, the more likely it will be adopted by the customers.

Question three: *Does online trust play an important role in affecting customers' intention to accept and use internet banking?*

Result: The results from the interviews regarding this question was not very different from the questionnaires. All the participants strongly agreed that trust plays a significant role in affecting user's intention to adopt internet banking.

Interviewee 1 states that "due to the degree of uncertainty and virtual setting, trust plays an important role in the context of internet banking. He further states that "for our bank, trust is the most crucial and highly influential factor for building positive long-term relationship with our valued customers".

Interviewee 2 outlined his view by stating that "the openness of internet structure possesses great threat to our users; therefore, the mutual trust relationship between our bank and customers is highly important.

Interviewee 3 answer to the above question was “trust is of the major reasons why our customers are willing to release their sensitive and private information and conduct sensitive financial transactions. He also outlined that “the issue of trust is even more important in electronic banking environment than it is in the traditional branch banking environment.

Interviewee 4 mentioned that “internet banking is highly uncertain because parting involved in transactions are not present in the same place. Therefore. Customer trust is a major contributor towards the growth of internet banking.

Interviewee 5 mentioned that “evidence suggest the mains reason why some customers feel resistant to using internet banking are related to online security and lack of trust”. For this reason, banks in the UK must make banking on the internet as secure and reliable as possible.

Main Themes Derived from Question 3

- Uncertainty and Virtual Settings
- Trust build long term relationship with customers.
- Mutual trust relationship between customers and the bank
- Trust is a major contributor to internet banking growth
- Online security

Brief Discussion of Results

From the above interview responses, it can be deduced that trust plays a significant role in any e-commerce interactions which involves high level of uncertainty and dependency. Since online transactions are subject uncertainties; therefore, trust is the critical factor that ensures the successful proliferation of e-commerce. In other words, customer trust is considered as the key driver in the growth and adoption of internet banking services. It was also found from the literature and questionnaire survey that for retail banks to success in this highly competitive environment they must build, confirm and maintain trust with their customers. For this reason, online trust is considered as the major and sole contributor to internet banking growth.

As mentioned above the banking sector is highly associated with the issue of trust because of privacy and security concerns. In the electronic world, due to the uncertain nature of online environment and the absence of physical communication between the customer and staff, trust is of high importance. Furthermore, it is also noted from

above responses that when customers are not confident about the characteristics of their bank and the online environment, they will unlikely to use internet banking. Overall, the present study finds customer trust as the highly important element for the adoption of online banking services. Banks must have trust-based collaboration process in place to build mutually valuable relationship with their online customers. Trust is the foundation of electronic banking and plays a crucial role to facilitate the interaction between the customers and the bank.

Question Four: *Does privacy and security concerns play a role in customers' decision to accept internet banking? Are there any measures taken by your bank to activate and increase the internet banking security and privacy?*

Result: Similar to the question of trust, interview participants also strongly agreed to the fact that the issue of privacy and security concerns are the key determinants of customers' internet banking adoption.

Interviewee 1 stated that "privacy is a serious issue in electronic banking because our customers have little control over the information they share, and this negatively affects their willingness to engage in online transactions". He further stated, "high perception of online privacy positively influences our customer s' willingness to trust online banking".

Interviewee 2 also outlined that "privacy and security is a major concern in online banking that and this is the reason our bank regularly monitors security vulnerabilities and constantly assess, evaluate and resolve any issues arising".

Interviewee 3 outlined his view by stating that "privacy and security concerns simply cannot be avoided in any e-commerce-based transactions. He also stated that "for internet banking to reach its full potential, banks in the UK must have optimum technologies in place to protect its customers' privacy and security of the digital transactions".

Interviewee 4 also agreed to interviewee 1, 2 and 3 and stated that "due to the unpredictable and open nature of the world wide web, protecting our customers against privacy and security threat is our ultimate priority and an integral part of the overall strategy".

Interviewee 5 shared his view by stating that “privacy and security concerns has an immediate effect on the customers’ internet banking adoption and usage”. He also outlined that “based on a very recent survey, our bank found that for 48% of our customer, privacy and security concerns were the biggest issue when sharing their personal and financial information online”. The survey also found that “two third of the customers are worried about protecting their personal information over the internet.

Main Themes Derived from Question 4

- Privacy and security are a major concern
- Vulnerabilities
- Integral part of the overall strategy
- Personal and financial information

Brief Discussion of Results

It is clear from interviewee responses that the issue of privacy and security plays an integral part in the overall diffusion of online banking services. Almost all the interview respondents agreed that customers privacy and security concerns significantly influence their intention to adopt and use internet banking services. The responses to question four suggest that security and privacy are the customers’ subjective expectations about the financial loss due to uncertain environment of internet media. Customers’ perception of security is based on timely, accurate and safe transmission of data. Without adequate privacy and security measures in place, customers will not conduct sensitive financial transactions over the internet.

The growth and trust upon internet banking totally depend upon the security and privacy policy of the bank. The present study found that in order for banks to maintain privacy and security measures in electronic banking, a complete and secure system is required. Customers will feel hesitation in conducting online banking transactions unless the system is more secured and convenient. In summary, it can be concluded from the above responses that privacy and security are sensitive issues and must become an integral part of the overall strategy when marketing internet banking products to the customers. Furthermore, it was found that high perception of online privacy and security positively influence their willingness to trust and use internet banking services.

Question Five: *From your point of view, who are more willing to use online banking service according to the following categories:*

- *Age (Younger/Older)*
- *Gender (Male/Female)*
- *Education Level (Low Level/High Level)*

Result: Almost all the respondents agreed customers' demographic plays a vital role in the adoption and usage of internet banking.

Interviewee 1 stated that “younger individuals are more prone to using internet banking than older customers who focus more on relationship building and face-to-face customer service and give less emphasis to using technology in their daily life”. He further stated that “I do not believe that customer gender and education level will have any influence on their choice of banking channel, especially in today's highly technology-based era”.

Interviewee 2 view was not very different from interviewee 1. He mentioned that “older bank customers are more accustomed to seeking traditional non-technological solutions to their daily banking needs than younger customers. He extends his view by stating that “although internet banking is designed to be easy to use and with easy to match user interface, the problem of using this service among older people still prevail”.

Interviewee 3 stated that “majority of our mobile and internet banking users are middle-aged (between 24-39) years of the age”. “They are the ones who conduct most of their daily banking transactions over mobile banking”. However, it is very challenging to convince older customers towards internet banking because they prefer to conduct their banking transactions over the branch counter”. Regarding the age and IT competence interviewee 3 stated that “I do not believe this can be a barrier or an obstacle in the usage of internet banking services”.

Interviewee 4 presents his view by stating that “our customers aged between 18-30 only use internet banking to conduct their basic banking transactions such as fund transfers, checking account balance and pay bills. He further stated that younger individuals are the most technology-oriented people who conduct their banking transactions online.

Interviewee 5 also stated that “customers' gender and level of education have no impact at all on their choice of using online banking”. however, their age does play a role in shaping their intention to use online banking services.

Main Themes Derived from Question 5

- Face-to-face customer service
- IT Competence
- Younger people are more technology oriented

Brief Discussion of Results

It is noted from the above responses that all the interview respondents agreed that customers' demographics can play a major role in influencing their decision to adopt and use internet banking services. The interview responses are in line with quantitative data analysis which suggest that customers' age does play a vital role in influencing their decision to use internet banking services; however, gender and level of education was found to have no effect. It can be deduced from the interview responses that young people tend to be more literate, have higher social status, seek higher occupational status and are more likely to adopt new technology. In other words, young people are more abreast and more inclined to innovation than the old people. Furthermore, younger groups are more technology-savvy and have high propensity towards the acceptance of internet banking. Older people, on the other hand, tend to have a negative view of new technologies and feel reluctant to accept and use them. Research on technology acceptance suggest that individuals with increased age are less optimistic about new technologies as compared to younger aged groups.

Regarding the gender, it was found that in today's highly technological environment, gender gap towards the acceptance of new technology has decreased and does not have direct effect on user's behavioural intention. Education level of customers was also found to have no significant impact on the adoption of internet banking services. Based on the above findings, the present study suggests that Banks should develop targeted strategy in order to provide personalized service to different customers segments in order to meet their specific needs and preferences. For instance, the present study indicated that customers' age has an impact on their choice to use internet banking. Older consumers have negative view of internet banking technology and, therefore, not willing to accept and use this service. For banks to overcome this, they should develop a targeted strategy in order to have a better understanding regarding their requirement and provide them with a well customized internet banking products and services.

Question Six: *In your opinion, what do you think are the major inhibiting factors that prevents customers from using internet banking services?*

Result: Interviewee participants presented different views when answering this question.

According to interviewee one, main factors that inhibit the adoption of internet banking are customers' concern for privacy and security and trust issues. He also stated that "complexity of using internet banking is also a major reason why older people do not use this service.

Interviewee 2 stated that "majority number of customers do not use online banking because they do not trust the internet banking medium.

Interviewee 3 presented his view by stating that "one of the main factors that put our customers off from internet banking are lack of assistance and face-to-face advise. He further mentioned that "sometimes the technology does not offer the expected results, and this can be very frustrating for customers.

Interviewee 4 stated that "most of our customer fear that that their money could be ticked during online transfer. He summarised that "the fear of losing personal and financial data are the main reasons for the resistance of internet banking use".

Interviewee 5 mentioned that "security and privacy and lack of trust on internet banking medium are the major reasons for the non-adoption of internet banking services.

Main Themes Derived from Question 6

- Concern for privacy and security
- Complexity of using internet banking services
- Do not trust internet banking medium
- Lack of assistance and face-to-face advise
- Fear of losing personal and financial data

Brief Discussion of Results

The interview respondents mentioned several factors for the non-adoption of internet banking services among UK customers. Majority of the respondents perceived security and privacy risks as the major inhibitor of using internet banking services. A common and widely recognized obstacle to electronic commerce adoption has been the lack of security and privacy over internet. It demonstrates risk as an additional dimension in diffusion and adoption. This has led many to view internet

commerce as a risky undertaking. Thus, it is expected that only individuals who perceive using internet banking as a low risk undertaking would be inclined to adopt it. The second main reason for non-adopting internet banking services is not trusting the internet banking medium. Due to the uncertain nature of online environment and the absence of physical communication between the customer and staff, the issue of privacy and security is of high importance. Some 20% of respondents commented that there were no human interactions when sourcing financial services over the internet.

The present study also found that customers do not use internet banking because of the complexity and difficulty of the service. Complexity of using a technology negatively affect user's intention towards its adoption. Technologies such as online banking, ATM and mobile banking are not accepted by customers, particularly by elderly individuals, because they consider them as highly technological complex services.

Other most important factors inhibiting the diffusion of internet banking are lack of user-friendly technology and customer demand, lack of suitable skills, high initial set up costs. Demographic and personal factors can also play a role in delaying the diffusion of internet banking channels. For example, some customers might not conduct online banking transactions due to low income, low education level or the lack of information about this channel.

Question Seven: *What do you think banks should do to ensure customers use internet banking in an environment that is that is free from all the risks?*

Result: Interviewee 1 stated that “banks in the UK must maximise the security measures for customers to bank in a safe environment. He further stated that “internet banking websites must have security mechanism and firewall in place to protect its customers against online fraud.

Interviewee 2 stated that “banks must require strong password and other encrypted security codes to access their sites online”. He further stated that “other added steps could be answering different security questions and requesting a security code to the mobile”.

Interviewee 3 extend his view by stating that “banks must regularly educate its customers to access their online banking from secured network or else the data will be compromised”. He further mentioned that “another important step banks should take is to enables a two-factor authentication (2FA) login system in their websites because passwords and security codes alone are not good enough as they can be easily guessed through the social media sites.

Interviewee 4 also mentioned that “banks must also provide online training to its customers to educate them against online fraud and scams”. “Training sessions can be delivered in branches or online through the mobile apps”. “This will not only protect customers against online fraud but will also boost internet banking use among customers”.

Main Themes Derived from Question 7

- Security mechanism and firewall in place
- Strong passwords and other encrypted security codes
- Two factor authentications
- Educate customers against online fraud and scams

Brief Discussion of Results

The interview respondents mentioned numerous steps banks must take in order to create the risk-free environment for customers to bank securely online. Interview respondents suggested that banks must introduce multi-layered security approach for customers when logging in to online banking. Banks must have legal and protective technological structure (such as, privacy and security policies, third party assurance and firewall encryption) that ensure that it is safe and secure to conduct financial transactions in this website. Moreover, the interview respondents also suggested that online banking systems should employ multi-factor authentication to prevent unauthorized access to customer accounts. This risk-based authentication method should use a combination of challenge questions and security images when logging in.

Another important suggestion that was made is skip public Wi -Fi for private banking. With public network, customers cannot be totally secured unless each page they visit is encrypted. The security of customers’ home network is always ideal. Furthermore, as discussed above, customer online trust largely depends on the structural assurance of internet medium. In online banking context, structural assurance of the transaction medium (internet) plays a key role, since it reduces

consumers' uncertainty related to system errors and security and privacy policies. Such protection assures customers that it is safe and secure from any unauthorised activities and financial loss. Considering the nature of electronic finance that is highly sensitive, banks must have maximum assurance in place for consumers to trust them. Following this discussion, the present study proposes that banks must have the above security mechanism in place. This will positively influence customer trust and promote their intention towards internet banking services. When customer perceive that they are protected by regulatory frameworks, it is likely that they will trust the bank website to conduct their financial transactions.

5.9 Overall Summary of the Findings

This chapter presented analysis of the findings. To test the formulated hypotheses, various non-parametric statistical tests were carried out. Spearman's rho correlation was used to examine the relationship between various constructs of this study. It was found that PU, PEU and trust are positively correlated with intention to use internet banking. Meanwhile perceived risk was found to negatively affect consumer intention to use internet banking. Additionally, perceived privacy and perceived security were also positively correlated with online trust.

Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis tests were conducted to investigate the role of demographic in the adoption of internet banking. It was found that customers' age significantly influences their decision to adopt and use internet banking. Age was found to be a major determinant of internet banking adoption. However, gender and level of education was found to have no impact on customer's choice of internet banking services.

Finally, multiple regression analysis (MRA) was used to investigate the combined effect of PU, PEU, perceived trust, perceived risk and age on customer intention to use internet banking services. It was revealed that all these five factors significantly predict consumer intention to use internet banking. These factors combined explained 76% of the variance in customer intention to use internet banking.

Majority of the proposed hypotheses were supported as expected by the researcher. The hypothesised paths (PU to INT; PEU to INT; PU to PEU; TRST to INT; PRISK to INT; PPRI to TRST; PSEC to TRST; TRST to PRISK and AGE to INT) were found to be

statistically significant. The other three hypothesised paths (TRST to PU; Gender to INT and Education Level to INT) were found insignificant.

Apart from the quantitative data analysis, 5 interviews were conducted with bank managers. The findings from the interviews were in line with the findings from the survey. It was found from the interviews that perceived usefulness, ease of use and trust plays a vital role in the adoption of internet banking services. The findings also confirmed that security and privacy concerns are positively correlated with online trust. Based on the above findings, the present study would call on retail banks in the UK to pay close attention to these adoption factors in order to encourage customers to use internet banking. The next chapter aims to discuss the results of the findings and provides recommendation for future researches.

Chapter 6

Discussion, Conclusion and Direction for Future Research

6.0 Introduction

The primary objective of this chapter is to summarise the overall findings of the thesis and suggest direction for the future research. The chapter also aims to discuss how this thesis will contribute to both practice and knowledge. Finally, the chapter provides key recommendations to UK retail banks.

6.1 Overview of the study

The main aim of the present study was to provide a conceptual model investigating the drivers and barriers of internet banking acceptance in the UK. To accomplish this aim, the following five research questions were formed: (1) How consumers' intention to use internet banking are formed and what factors directly influence their decision to use and adopt this service? (2) What is the role of customer's trust in the acceptance of internet banking, and how consumer trust is developed? (3) Are there adoption differences between segments of customers based on their demographics characteristics? (4) What are the main factors impeding consumer decision to adopt and use internet banking? (5) What strategies should UK banks adopt to facilitate and maximise the adoption of internet banking?

To answer the above questions, the researcher conducted a critical review of the literature in relation to technology acceptance. Chapter 2 discussed and compared main models and theories of technology acceptance, such as, IDT, TRA, TPB and TAM. It was found through the discussion that TAM is the most parsimonious and appropriate theory to be selected for this study. However, the researcher acknowledged that TAM's original constructs are not enough to reflect upon the customer's internet banking acceptance behaviour and; therefore, suggested additional variables. Section 2 of chapter 2 discussed the role of customers' trust and perceived risk in internet banking adoption. This section also proposed a trust model for internet banking based on trust literature. Section 3 of chapter 2 was about the general discussion of internet banking research where the benefits and limitations of the service were compared. The chapter also discussed the role of customer's demographic characteristics. Chapter 3 developed the conceptual framework and formulated set of hypotheses. Chapter 4 discussed different research methods and justifications were given to the chosen research method

for this study. Chapter 5 was the most important and critical part of the overall thesis. This chapter presented the descriptive analysis of the survey respondents and conducted various statistical tests to purify and confirm the hypotheses formulated in chapter 3 of the present study.

6.2 The Internet Banking Acceptance Model

The model of internet banking acceptance proposed for the present study is based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). It was found in the literature that TAM is the most powerful and appropriate model for predicting and explaining customer behaviour towards the acceptance of new technology. The present study grounded new variables into the original TAM in order to apply it to the new context of internet banking acceptance. It must be noted that two new variables – perceived trust and perceived risk are added to the original TAM. The integration of these new variables into the original TAM model is not only theoretically appealing but also practically significant, since it better explains how intention towards internet banking are formed. The present study proposed that the most important variables that affect internet banking adoption are PU, PEU, trust, perceived risk, perceived privacy and perceived security. The critical linkage between these variables and their comparative impact on customer's behavioural intention provides reasonably good variance.

There are several new findings from this study that previous researches, based on the original TAM, failed to point out. First, perceived trust and risk were found to have a significant direct impact on customer's behavioural intentions. This suggest that banks must pay closer attention to these new constructs in order to reduce customer's uncertainty when using online banking services. Secondly, since trust directly impact behavioural intention, it also has an indirect positive impact on perceived risk and perceive usefulness. These findings confirm the crucial role of trust in the acceptance of internet banking as proposed by previous researches.

6.3 Discussion of Results

The main aim of this research was to investigate the drivers and barriers towards the use of internet banking in the UK. Intention to use internet banking was evaluated through TAM in addition to some other important external factors (perceived trust, perceived risk and the role of demographic variables).

This section now aims to provide discussion of the main findings from the research and where applicable, link the literature to the research outcomes. The section will analyse if the findings are backed by authors in this field or there is divergence of opinions.

6.3.1 Effect of Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use on Intention

The current internet banking literature suggest that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are a significant determinant of internet banking adoption. The present study also hypothesized that both PU and PEU positively affects user's intention towards using internet banking. (H1, H2). The results from statistical analysis provided concrete support to both hypotheses, demonstrating that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use directly influence customers' intention towards the use of internet banking. The present study found that that the more positive the perception of usefulness and ease of use, the more willing customers will be to adopt and use internet banking services. These findings are in line with various researches in this field (Davis, 1989); (Hanakul and Fink, 2005); (Nor et al, 2008); (Mohammadi, 2014) and Dong et al (2017). Such positive and significant relationship suggests that when customers perceive internet banking services as useful and easy to use hence it is more likely to be accepted. In summary, the results of this research are in agreement with TAM findings and other existing researches (Davis 1989); (Kesharwani and Bisht, 2012); (Shanmugam, 2015) and (Bashir and Madhavaiah, 2015) that PU and PEU plays a vital role in shaping the behavioural intention of users to adopt internet banking services.

6.3.2 Effect of Online Trust on Intention

The present study presumes that trust positively influences customer's willingness to adopt and use internet banking services (H4). The statistical result provided in the previous chapter found that trust is strongly and positively correlated with behavioural intention. It was found that the higher the level of customers trust on internet banking, the stronger their intentions will be to adopt and use this service. If banks do not have the required privacy and security mechanism in place customers will not use internet

banking services. This is because online banking involves monetary transactions which are highly sensitive in nature. Customers therefore will be more cautious while conducting such transactions over the internet. The findings of this research are in line with trust literature (Pavlia, 2009) and (Ong and Lin; 2015) that online trust is an essential factor in influencing user's behavioural intention. The present study therefore suggest that banks must build and maintain customers trust through advertising campaign, privacy guarantee, security assurance and monetary loss compensation. This will boost customer's confidence on banks and online banking.

6.3.3 Effect of Perceived Privacy and Security on Online Trust

The present study hypothesized that customers' perception of privacy and security positively influence online trust. It was found that there is a strong and positive correlation between perceived privacy and security and online trust. Customers are more willing to trust and use internet banking services if they believe that consistent privacy and security policies are in place. These findings are also in line with the findings of Luis et al (2017) and Urumsah (2015) who claims that privacy and security are the strong and direct determinants of online trust and ultimately online banking adoption. The findings are also positively correlated with Alain et al (2010) and Rawashdeh (2015) research findings who suggest that the higher the level of privacy and security, the more willing customers will trust online banking.

6.3.4 Effect of Perceived Risk on Intention

Perceived risk in internet banking refers to the customers' perception of the negative outcomes that might arise in the course of using this service. The present study hypothesised that perceived risk has a negative impact on user acceptance of internet banking services. The findings revealed that customers' perception of risk is negatively and significantly associated with their intention to use internet banking services. Customers' perception regarding financial loss and personal data loss was found to negatively affect their willingness to accept and use online banking. These findings are in line with existing research, which suggest that perceived risk is negatively correlated with behavioural intention Kesharwani and Bisht (2012); Dimitrios et al (2013); Yun Zhang et al (2018) and Chaushen (2013). In summary, the present study found that the higher the customers' perception of the risk associated with online banking, the lower and weaker their intention to adopt such service.

6.3.5 Effect of Internet Banking Trust on Perceived Risk

Based on the previous studies, the present study hypothesised that high level of customer trust reduces their risk regarding internet banking services. The results from the statistical analysis indicate that high level of trust leads to low perceived risk. In other words, as the level trust increases, customer's perception of risk will decrease. The present study found that customers will perceive online banking less risky when (i) their bank has consistent online policies and practices in place; (ii) their bank's website has the latest security mechanism in place to protect them against online fraud; and (iii) the internet banking medium itself is secure. The findings from the primary data is consistent with existing literature in this field. For instance, Benazic and Music (2015); Santhanamery and Ramayah (2016) Ryu et al (2018) claims that higher the level of trust, the lower will be the perceived risk in any e-commerce transaction. Based on these findings it is suggested that banks must establish and maintain customer trust in order to reduce customers' concern regarding the risk associated with internet banking services. Bank should; (i) provide reliable internet banking services; (ii) reassure customers that they will be compensated for any loss that occur; and (iii) build customer's confidence that the internet medium is safe and secure for sensitive transactions.

6.3.6 Customers' Demographics and the Adoption of Internet Banking

In the proposed conceptual framework, it was hypothesised customers' demographics such as their gender, age and level of education plays a vital role in their internet banking adoption decision. The findings show that customer's age plays a role in online banking acceptance. It was found that younger age groups were more technology-savvy and, therefore, are more willing to accept internet banking as compared to older individuals. Older customers (aged 46 and above) were more willing to use traditional banking channels as compared to internet banking, because they believed on the physical relationship with the bank staff to conduct their sensitive banking transactions rather than a computer. These findings are in line with the findings of Greene and Norbury (2011); Shiraz (2014) and Sun and Zhang (2006) who claims that customer's age is a key influential factor in new innovation adoption (see chapter 2).

However, the findings from the research contradicts with Payman et al (2010) who states that gender, income and education level have significant positive impact on the

choice of customers to adopt internet banking (see chapter 2). Gender and education level of customers were found to have no impact on their choice of internet banking. The present study found that both male and female have similar perception towards all the three dimensions of TAM (PU, PEU and Intention). Similarly, education level was also not considered to be a significant moderator of internet banking acceptance.

Below Table 6-1 compares the findings from the current research with the various authors in this field. Majority of the of the findings from this study are in line with existing literature. It can be noted from the table that most of the findings from the present study are supported and backed by technology acceptance literature.

Table 6.1: Comparison of Research Findings with Existing Literature

Research Variables	Davis et al (1989)	Hanakul and Fink (2005)	Pavlia (2009)	Ong and Lin (2015)	Luis et al (2017)	Rawashdeh (2015)	Kesharwani and Bisht (2012)	Benazic and Music (2015)	Greene and Norbury (2011)	Payman et al (2010)
Perceived Usefulness on Intention	√									
PEOU on Intention	√	√								
Perceived Trust on Intention			√	√						
Perceived Privacy and security on Trust					√	√				
Perceived Risk on Intention							√	√		
Perceived Trust on Risk										
Demographics Impact on Intention									√	√
Inhibiting factors of Internet Banking										

Source: Many as stated above

6.4 Review of Research Objectives

Based on the findings in previous chapter, the following conclusions are drawn for each research questions formulated in Chapter one.

1. Critically review the literature on internet banking and relevant theories/models to develop a conceptual framework for this research.

The first objective of the present study was designed to develop a conceptual framework based on a critical review of the literature related to technology acceptance. The present study critically reviewed and compared different models /theories and as well as discussed the importance of customer trust. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was used as the foundation to develop a conceptual model for the present study. Although TAM is claimed to the most powerful and parsimonious model of technology acceptance, it fails to consider other important external factors such as the issue of perceived risk and perceived trust. Therefore, the present study augmented the original TAM with additional constructs such as trust and demographic characteristics in order to better explain the customers' acceptance of internet banking in new and more contemporary context.

Upon extensive review of the literature related to technology acceptance models, a conceptual framework was introduced in chapter three. The main reason for developing a conceptual framework was to facilitate answering the research questions in a more systematic way. The need for a fresh model for internet banking acceptance became evident after a careful revision of the literature. The new proposed internet banking acceptance model suggest that customer acceptance of internet banking is jointly influenced by perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEU), perceived trust, risk and customers' demographic characteristics. The researcher believe that additional variables combined with the original TAM model provided a more holistic and deeper understandings of customers' acceptance of internet banking in the UK.

The proposed model in the present study not only added new dimensions and insights to the literature but will also prove very useful to future bank marketing researchers to effectively study the acceptance of internet banking. Based on the above discussion, the present study has been successful in achieving its first objective.

2. Identify the factors influencing UK customers' intention towards the adoption and usage of internet banking.

This objective was designed to investigate the main factors that influence customers' adoption of internet banking in the UK. To achieve this research objective, a model of internet banking was proposed in chapter 3 showing all the possible factors influencing internet banking adoption. The main factors that influence the adoption of internet banking include perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived trust, perceived risk, perceived privacy and perceived security. Upon assessing the impact of these factors on the adoption of internet banking, Spearman's rho correlation and multiple regression analysis were consulted in chapter 5.3.1. chapter 5.2.5 presents justification for selecting the particular statistical test in answering this research objective.

The findings of this research objective demonstrate that perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and trust directly influence customer's intention to use internet banking services. Perceived usefulness in particular was found to heavily impact customers' online behaviour as compared to perceived ease of use. On the other hand, perceived risk also plays a crucial role in influencing user's behavioural intention. It was found that customer's perception of risk negatively affects their intention. However, high level of customer's trust reduces customer's risk perception associated with internet banking services.

The findings of this research objective add several new insights to the literature. To the best of researcher's knowledge, no study was previously done to collectively study the combined effect of these factors in retail banking context. Moreover, the present study modelled TAM attributes with perceived trust and perceived risk for the first time to assess how these factors differ in affecting customers' intention to use internet banking. The findings revealed that both Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived trust has a positive and significant impact on the adoption of internet banking. However, customers' perception of risk was found to negatively impact the adoption of internet banking services.

To conclude, the findings of this research objectives not only fill the knowledge vacuum by answering unexplored phenomenon but also provide concrete guidance to retail bank managers to for enhancing customers' perception of internet banking adoption in the UK. The second objective, therefore, was fully achieved.

3. Examine the role of customers' trust in the acceptance of internet banking.

This objective of the present study was aimed to assess the critical role of customers' trust in the acceptance of online banking. To achieve this objective, first the role of trust in IB was considered vigorously throughout the research. Secondly, conceptual framework was proposed in chapter 3 showing the impact of trust on the adoption decision of IB. Correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship of trust and customer acceptance of internet banking.

Findings for this research objective demonstrates that the issue of customer trust plays an integral role in the adoption and acceptance of internet banking services. The findings from the statistical testing revealed that trust significantly and positively impact on customer intention to use internet banking. The study also found that lack of customer trust, both in online environment and the characteristics of bank, act as an obstacle when using internet banking. The issue of trust was highly ranked by customers when using internet banking. It is therefore suggested that banks should have a trust-based collaboration process in place in order to build mutually valuable relationship with their online banking customers.

Number of factors contributing to online trust were identified. The present study found that perceived privacy, perceived security, bank's trustworthiness and structural assurance of bank's website positively affects customer's perception of trust. Among these, the issue of perceived privacy and perceived security was frequently cited by respondents as the primary drivers of trust in internet banking. It was found that customer will only consider the additional features of internet banking such as PU and PEU, after the privacy and security mechanism are in place by the bank. Many customers feel reluctant to use internet banking simply because of privacy and security concerns. Therefore, it is suggested retail banks must have effective privacy and security policies in place in order to gain customer trust.

Findings of this research objective makes significant contributions to both the literature and practice. The researcher believe that no previous study was done to examine the critical role of trust in UK retail banking context. Secondly, the present study modelled the trust feature with the TAM model for the first time to analyse how customer trust affect customer perception of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. In summary, the findings from this research objective not only contributed to theory but

will also act as guidelines for retail banks to understand that internet banking should be managed with the overall aim of creating a usefulness service that is based on the trusting relationship between the bank and its customers.

4. investigate whether differences between customers' demographic characteristics have any effect on their perception to adopt internet banking?

This research objective was aimed to assess whether customers' demographics, such as gender, age and education level, moderate their intention to use internet banking services. First, critical review of the literature was conducted to assess whether customers' demographics have any influence on their internet banking decision. The literature provided mixed results. Based on the literature, conceptual framework was proposed showing how customers' demographic characteristics are linked to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). To assess the impact of customers' demographics, Mann-Whitney U Test and Kruskal Wallis analysis were used.

Findings from both the statistical analysis and semi-structured interviews indicates that only customers' age affect their choice of internet banking. However, gender and level of education does not exhibit any sort of influence on the internet banking adoption process. Statistical findings from the previous chapter (section 5.5) shows significant differences between the age groups of respondents on all dimensions of TAM ("PU", "PEU", and "Behavioural Intention"). It was found that younger customers are more IT savvy and, therefore, are more willing to accept and use internet banking as compared to older individuals. In other word, younger individuals had a more favourable perception of PU, PEU and behavioural intention as opposed to older age groups.

By understanding that customer's age directly influences their behavioural intention, bank should not neglect older customers who exhibit a more negative attitude towards internet banking. Banks in the UK should adopt strategies that specifically concentrate on older customers who are hesitant to use electronic banking.

Findings of this research objective also add several new insights to the literature. To the best of researcher's knowledge, no study was previously done to analyse the impact of customers' demographics on TAM attributes. Moreover, this is the first study that examined how different types of customers, based on their demographic characteristics respond to perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Apart from theoretical contribution, findings from this research objective also act guideline for retail bank

managers to understand how to maximise the acceptance of internet banking among customers who are hesitant to use this service. Based on the above findings, the fourth objective is also achieved.

5. Contribute to the body of knowledge in the area of technology acceptance and make recommendations to banks about how to improve the acceptance of internet banking.

The researcher believe that the fifth objective was the most important part of the overall thesis. The sole purpose of the present research was to contribute to the body of literature in the field of technology acceptance, particularly internet banking acceptance. Apart from theoretical contributions, the present study also aimed to provide practical recommendations to bank managers about the key factors affecting internet banking acceptance. The present study has made significant contributions to both theory and practice. Please refer to the next sections 6.5.1, 6.5.2 and 6.6 of the present chapter for a more detailed explanation of the original contribution of this study. Objective 5 of the present study is also achieved.

6.5 Contribution of this Research

This research makes a significant contribution to both theory and practice. These are discussed in below section 6.5.1 and 6.5.2.

6.5.1 Managerial Contribution

1. Previous studies have focused on the positive aspects of internet banking with little or no focus on the issues of barriers to this service. The present study is the first comprehensive examination of both the drivers and barriers towards the use of internet banking in the UK. This pioneering empirical research investigated factors that both diffuse and inhibit the adoption of internet banking. Understanding of these factors will help banks to implement measures that overcomes the inhibiting factors and increase the adoption of internet banking among UK customers.
2. Findings from this research will prove very useful for banking sector to understand the relative importance of trust in the acceptance of internet banking. This research will act as guidelines for retail banks to understand that internet banking should be managed with the overall aim of creating a usefulness service that is based on the trusting relationship between the bank and its customers. Banks must ensure that the internet banking website is not only useful and easy to use, but it should also include a trust-building mechanism. Findings from this research suggests that banks must invest more in building trust relationship with its customers in comparison to provide an efficient and useful service. Such understanding will provide bank's strategists and managers to come up with effective strategies to build online trust, which will promote the adoption of internet banking among UK customers.
3. Third important contribution for the banking sector is the need to recognise the importance of privacy and security concerns in the acceptance of internet banking. Results from this study can be used as guiding principles to reduce privacy and security concerns among customers. Banks must ensure they have the required protection and safeguard mechanisms in place that will protect its customers against online fraud. Similarly, banks' website should include a concise and well-presented policy statement to reduce customers perception of risk. Customers are more willing to trust internet banking services if they are confident that their bank stands behind the service.

4. The present study examined how different types of customers, based on their demographic characteristics, have different perceptions towards the same technology (internet banking). The findings from this research suggest how different segments of customers perceive TAM and trust dimensions. Banks must understand these individual differences among customers about how and why they make different choices towards the same technology. Results from this research suggest that user analysis must not be taken for granted and rather, should become a centre piece when designing marketing strategies. For banks to maximise the adoption of internet banking among customers, they should target each segment of customers with appropriate marketing strategies. For instance, this study found that older respondents are techno-resistant customers who are not willing to trust and use internet banking services. It is therefore advisable for banks to target this segment of customers with tailored marketing strategies to assist them in using the internet banking.
5. The present study proposed a model of internet banking acceptance which identified the critical factors affecting customers' intention towards using this service. This model will serve as an effective tool for retail banks when promoting internet banking services to customers.
6. Lastly, the source of the primary data collected for this research is from the perceptions of customers of internet banking in the UK. Therefore, the findings from this study directly reflects the factors that affect UK customers' behavioural intention towards internet banking usage which have never been investigated by their banks. The information from this research will prove very usefulness for banks in order to pinpoint areas of strengths and weakness and as well as provide opportunities for expansion. Managers can use the findings from this study as a guiding principle to better understand the factors that affect UK customers' intention.

6.5.2 Theoretical Contribution

The findings from this study have some significant theoretical implications towards the technology acceptance literature:

1. The present study modified the original TAM model by adding additional variables that influence the adoption of online banking in the new context. The inclusion of trust construct and demographic characteristics in the TAM model would help researchers to further understand how perceptions towards internet banking are formed and the subsequent role of demographic variables in user's intention. Several researchers have criticised the TAM model for failing to include other important variables that might play a crucial role in predicting user's technology acceptance behaviour (Mathieson, 1990 and Venkatesh, 2000). However, the present study proposed an extended model which highlights that the relationship between perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and behavioural intention is moderated by user's demographic characteristics, such as gender, age and education level. The present study also examined how online trust act as direct antecedent of behavioural intention. In sum, the integration of trust construct and the role of demographics with the original TAM is both theoretically appealing and empirically significant.
2. The present study also makes significant contribution to trust literature by examining the role of trust in the context of internet banking and also the key factors that affect online trust. This research has integrated trust and perceived risk with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and proposed a model of trust for internet banking acceptance. This model suggest that trust is a multi-dimensional construct that directly influences behavioural intention to accept internet banking.
3. A major contribution to of this study to knowledge is the conceptual framework of internet banking acceptance (see figure 3.1) which was developed through critical review of literature of different technology acceptance theories and models with a particular focus on TAM. The internet banking acceptance model identifies several critical factors that influence the adoption of internet banking, such as perceived trust, risk, privacy and security. Therefore, this comprehensive and parsimonious model can be employed in several web-based transactional systems, such as online shopping or e-commerce.

6.5.3 Methodological Contribution:

Apart from practical and theoretical contribution, the present study also makes important contribution to research methodology as well:

1. The methodological contribution of this thesis is the research method of this thesis itself. As shown in chapter 4, the research method which was tailor-customized for this research is comprised of an extensive literature review, expert review, interviews, pilot research and its analysis, main questionnaire development, and hypothesis testing. This mixed method approach utilized reviews and analyse the main constructs formulated for the present study. Essentially, the research method followed in this study improves an approach followed by Al-Eisawi (2014) by simplifying it. The current study conducted questionnaire survey and structured interviews among highly qualified internet banking users in the UK. As discussed in section 4.5.2, the use of mixed method approach was very helpful in gaining critical insight of the phenomenon being investigated; this would not been accomplished through a card-slot exercise.
2. Literature evidence on similar studies adopting one-method or parallel multi-method approaches for answering the research questions can be seen in the literature. Adopting such approaches could either limit the researcher from identifying new insights or raise the findings' generalisability related concerns. The sequential research approach adopted in this thesis was successful in answering the research questions while enhancing the reliability of the findings. Therefore, the research method designed for this study makes a significant contribution to the body of knowledge as well as guides future researchers for producing generalizable findings.
3. A mixed method was employed in the data collection and data analysis for optimism. This is considered a methodological contribution due to the laborious set of steps using Questionnaires and interviews. This complementary, where quantitative and qualitative methods are united to avoid the basic biases and problems that come from single method, because the results of one method may develop the other method. It has also increased the comprehensiveness of overall findings, by showing how qualitative data provided explanations for statistical data and helped gain deeper and detailed understanding of the research problem.
4. Finally, another significant methodological contribution lies in the experience gained through the application of both the scientific and interpretive approach and techniques applied for data collection. This experience maybe very useful for future

studies on the adoption and use of such approach in any business and management researches.

6.6 Key Recommendations for UK Retail Banks

Based on the findings from literature and the present study, it is recommended that now retail banks in the UK should play a leading and aggressive role in improving the factors that positively affect the adoption of internet banking. The researcher proposes the following recommendations in order to increase the acceptance of internet banking and reduce customers' perception of risk:

1. Best-in-Class Customer Services Relationship: First and foremost, for the successful diffusion of internet banking services among customers, banks in the UK should provide an extensive and deep level of customer support that works around the clock. Customer services representative should regularly assist internet banking users and provide immediate solutions in case of any technical faults or difficulty using the service. Creating such relationships will lead to greater customer satisfaction and this, in turn, will result in increased internet banking adoption.

2. Build Customer Trust: The issue of trust was considered vigorously throughout the research and it was found that customer's trust perception has a significant positive impact on behavioural intention. Based on these findings, the present study recommends that banks should have consistent online policies and practices in place in order to gain the trust of its customers. Internet banking website should also contain a privacy statement that will guarantee the privacy of its customers. Banks should have a trust-based collaboration process in place in order to build mutually valuable relationship with their online banking customers.

3. Increase security measures: The study indicated that security and privacy fears restrict customers from using internet banking services. Banks therefore must continually improve their security and privacy measures in order for customers to bank in a risk-free environment. Internet banking websites should have security mechanisms and firewall in place in order to protect its customers against online fraud. Banks should use eye scanning and voice recognition security in order to prevent unauthorised access. It is also suggested that banks should educate its customers in developing secure internet banking practices and risk management procedures. These combined security measures will alleviate customer's concerns about security and privacy problems.

4. User-friendly and easy to use website: PEOU was found to positively influence the adoption of internet banking. Therefore, banks must make the internet banking

websites very user-friendly and simple to use. Banks must regularly improve the design and navigation of the website in order to make it accessible to customers.

5. Collect customers feedback: The present study also recommends that banks should regularly ask its customers about their feedbacks and opinions regarding the internet banking experience. When banks have solid and unified feedbacks from its customers, they will have better understandings of the needs and preferences of these customers. Additionally, these feedbacks will serve as blueprints for improving customer experience in using internet banking.

6. Train and empower employees: It's the bank's employees who are in direct contact with customers. Therefore, they need to have the right skills and resources in order to provide exceptional customers service. Banks should ensure their employees not only have the answers to customers questions, but also understand the technology the bank is employing. Furthermore, banks should regularly monitor the performance of its employees to make sure they provide the required standard of service to internet banking customers.

7. Educate customers on the benefits of internet banking: As discussed above, despite the wide popularity and growth of internet banking, many people still feel resistant to adopt this service. Banks, therefore, should attract the attention of both the current and potential customers towards internet banking services through effective marketing strategies. Banks should inform customers about the relative advantages, features and convenience associated with this channel. Actions such as marketing campaigns and awareness sessions will prove useful in drawing customers attention towards internet banking. The present study also suggests that banks should provide incentives, such as low interest rates, increased overdraft limit, cashback offers to encourage customers to shift them from traditional banking methods to internet banking. This will increase the diffusion of internet banking in general.

8. Segment client base and provide personalized service: Banks should develop targeted strategy in order to provide personalized service to different customers segments in order to meet their specific needs and preferences. For instance, the present study indicated that customers' age has an impact on their choice to use internet banking. Older consumers have negative view of internet banking technology and, therefore, not willing to accept and use this service. For banks to overcome this, they should develop a targeted strategy in order to have a better understanding regarding

their requirement and provide them with a well customized internet banking products and services.

6.7 Implications and Suggestions for All Stakeholders

The present study will benefit key stakeholders including banks, customers, investors and academics, and will help in the implementation of policies, future research and enhancement of practices. This thesis identifies how internet banking improve customer experience, satisfaction and loyalty. This information is important for existing and new banks for improving the adoption of internet banking services among customers in the UK. The thesis has reviewed various literature, documented results and models through different perspectives, and has finally created an integrated framework (see chapter 3). The thesis makes significant contributions to both knowledge and practice which bring new insights and benefits to all stakeholders.

6.7.1 Implications for Banks

Through the thesis, banks will be more equipped with clear requirements in internet banking utilisation to provide services and survive in the 21st Century competition when fraud and fines are common, and margins are tight. ‘Perceived Risk’ negatively affects digital banking experience. Internet crime and security breaches result in financial losses and brand damage, which negatively affects customer experience and financial performance. The present research suggests that with investment and innovation banks can protect their digital platforms and minimise these risks. It is also suggested that enhanced security can be achieved through ‘Service Customisation’ on digital devices, which can shorten customer journeys. Customers want quick and easy access to their digital banking rather than a long log in process. This evidence shows there is a clear trend in customer needs emerging, which recognises that every customer is unique and should be treated individually through service personalisation to improve security and experience. These are important demands and issues banks should consider.

The research shows that banks and customers derive different digital banking value. The present study found that ‘Perceived Usefulness’ is a key driver for customer uptake and better experience. Therefore, retail banks in the UK need to provide value to customers in respect of improved customer experience and satisfaction, before being rewarded with customer loyalty and improvement in financial performance. Banks can innovate in digital channels to offer a better, value-added and efficient service to maintain competitive advantage. For instance, offering better deals online, and online

chat and text alerts which prevent customers from getting overdrawn. Customers want user-friendly, reliable and easy to use digital banking, hence making. 'Perceive Ease of Use', 'Service Quality' and other factors identified in the research important. Implementing some of these can be costly, but they add to customers' value. Therefore, banks should always seek to create value for customers through innovation, to receive value in return. The research provides clear evidence of how to use digital banking to build customer relationship and enhance banks' financial performance.

Customer Acceptance of internet banking is on the increase due to changing customer behaviours, expectations and experience. Customers want better experience and to manage their finances conveniently from any location. The questionnaire survey with internet banking customers and interviews show that customers are demanding more services than banks can provide, especially through mobile devices. This has implications for banks of the area to develop for customers to harness maximum benefits.

The present study also suggest that employee engagement and training are important in digital banking innovation and customer experience improvement. Employees' knowledge about customer requirements is key to this achievement, therefore employees should engage more with customers to have appropriate information to build digital banking that is attuned to customers' needs. In the open-ended questions, some customers commented that banks should consult them when promoting internet banking services. Through engagement, banks understand employees' feelings about the services they offer to customers. The research implication is that customers and employees are engaged adequately to build digital banking knowledge and enable employees to innovate, as other research also suggests that employee engagement and satisfaction improve financial performance. It will help employees understand how they contribute to the banks' digital banking scorecard and strategic vision.

The findings in chapter 4 highlight the importance of keeping some bank branches open. Although digital banking is improving customer experience, there are still customers who want to bank through the branches. They see digital banking as an addition rather than a full branch alternative, as it cannot satisfy all their needs. Some of them are also conscious of security. The implication for banks is that until every banking function can be done through digital banking, some branches still need to remain open, otherwise they will lose business, and there should be security education for these customers.

The present study provides detailed insight into UK banks, helping understand the efficiencies, capabilities and any weaknesses in their current digital strategy. The results of this thesis are useful for formulating effective appraisal, benchmarking and improvement of the banks' digital banking position. It offers new insight into different factors affecting digital banking uptake, experience, financial performance and reasons for its uptake from different perspectives. The results have wider marketing, business and technical implications for similar e-commerce businesses and work in other industries. The findings from this research will create digital banking awareness and knowledge sharing.

6.7.2 Implications for Shareholders

This research builds a business case for digital banking implementation, investment and innovation within banks by highlighting its importance on customer experience and financial performance. This research is important in economic development and serving customers well and improving profit for shareholders which is the main objective of banks. After the financial crisis of 2008, some customers felt unhappy with mainstream banks, hence this thesis offers investors the comprehensive information required to fill the gaps in the financial market. It forms the basis for investment in the new challenger banks, by offering insight about the viability and potential economic value-adds from digital banking (e.g. efficiency savings, profitability and sales growth, ROE, Cost-to-Income ratio, NIM and profit through CLV).

6.7.3 Implications for Customers

This research illuminates new knowledge into current UK digital banking and how banks are delivering services to customers. It has highlighted information on how banks can work with customers to bring good experience, satisfaction and loyalty. It has provided an opportunity for customers to express their feelings, how banks can create value for them and recommendations on what they want to be implemented to improve their experience and satisfaction even further. For customers, security, privacy, trust, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are important. The investment and work banks are doing around security can offer customers reassurance.

6.7.4 Implications for Policy Makers

In addition to the implications for the above stakeholders, the present study will also help create awareness and knowledge sharing within banks and government agencies about digital banking, and how it can be utilised more effectively. The new insight will

help regulators implement policies to protect customers and banks and create awareness of security issues. Policies in this area are still unclear. Security, data protection and privacy are still issues, and banks are vulnerable and at risk of attack. The research findings recognise the importance of employees' views and knowledge, and customers' feedback in innovation and implementation of digital banking, which banks should consider.

6.7.5 Implications for Academics

The researcher aims to publish the findings from this thesis in the nearer future. The results will be presented in conferences and published in journals such as E-Commerce, Information Management, Marketing, Modelling in Management and Business, Organisational Performance and Service Improvement Research. Through presentation, awareness and knowledge sharing, the general public are informed, and publications help to disseminate new knowledge to academics and other researchers. The thesis forms the basis for future research.

6.7 Limitation of the Study

The present study as like any other research has several limitations which are summarised below:

First, the sample size of the present study was only 275 respondents which is very low as compared to the number of people accessing and using internet banking across the UK who might have different perception towards the service. This can possibly give rise to the issue of generalisability and can make conclusions doubtful. However, the questionnaire survey was backed by 5 face-to-face interviews which possibly would have minimise, if not totally eliminated, the issue of generalisability.

Secondly, the sample of the present study comprised only active internet banking users. Data was not collected from non-users and dormant users who might have completely different perceptions. Results are interpreted based on the behaviour of current internet banking users with no attention paid to non-users. They might have been different affected by the drivers and barrier factors of internet banking. It is, therefore, advisable for future studies to investigate behaviour of users and non-users individually.

Third, due to the limited number of internet banking studies specifically focusing on UK customer's perception, the conceptual model for this research was developed based on literature from other countries and settings. This possibly might not have described the internet banking phenomenon in the UK, especially because of the cultural differences.

Another major limitation of this study is that it investigated the phenomenon from customers' perspective only; however, perceptions of business customers, corporate entities and other banking executives have not been recorded. The findings from this study needs to be further validated as the empirical results provides an investigation of the factors affecting internet banking adoption from only customers point of view.

6.8 Direction for Future Study

Customer acceptance of internet banking is a vast subject and there is always room for further researches in this area. The following future research opportunities arise from this research:

Future research should focus on non-users of internet banking in the UK. The present study ignored the perceptions of non-users of internet banking and how they are affected by the factors discussed in this study. Future researches can compare current users and non-users of this service and analyse differences in perceptions between these two groups. A comparison of perceptions of current users and non-users will provide a much greater and deeper insight into the online customer behaviour research in general. Secondly, additional research is required to extend the conceptualizations of online trust. The present study hypothesized that ability, integrity, benevolence, privacy and security are the antecedents of trust. However, as discussed in Chapter 3 there are other important factors that affect online trust such as reliability and loyalty, predictability and kindness and possessing personal attraction etc. Therefore, future studies should shed light on these aspects of trust and how they affect customers' intention towards acceptance of internet banking in general.

The present study suggests that customers' risk perception plays a vital role in the acceptance of internet banking. Yet the issue of risk is discussed at an abstract level. Perceived risk has different dimensions, such as financial, time, performance, psychological and social risk. Therefore, the present study calls for further research to conduct a more detailed examination of facets of risk and how these affect customers' behavioural intention individually. This will help internet banking researchers and practitioners to understand the role of perceived risk in more detail.

The present study suggests that customer acceptance of internet banking merely depends on TAM and trust beliefs. There are, however, many other important issues and factors affecting the acceptance of internet banking, such as customer loyalty (Venkatesh et al, 2000), behavioural expectation (Khan and Jan 2004), service quality (Shahid, 2007), system reliability and accessibility (Saudi, 2012), and customer satisfaction. According to Kumar et al (2009) in addition to PU and PEU, there are other critical external factors influencing the adoption of internet banking. Therefore, future study should attempt and test the influence of these additional constructs on the acceptance of internet banking in the UK.

Understanding the impact of demographic variables on the acceptance of internet banking is of high importance. The present study investigated the role of customers' gender, age and education level only. However, there other important demographic characteristics such as social or cultural background, computer literacy, and income level, that can have a profound impact on individuals' perception of internet banking, Therefore, future studies can improve the model proposed in the present study by conducting a more detailed analysis of the effect of these demographic characteristics on behavioural intention. This will enable bank strategists to come up with effective marketing strategies that is not only efficient but also tailored and suitable for all types of bank customers.

Finally, it is suggested that the proposed model for this study should be extended and tested in other cultural settings, particularly in Asian or Arab countries. It would be interesting to apply the findings from this study to investigate cross-cultural effect of these factors on the adoption of internet banking.

6.9 Concluding Remarks

The primary objective of this study was to investigate the drivers and barriers towards the use of internet banking in the UK. The present study also examined the role of customers' trust and their demographic characteristics in internet banking adoption. A comprehensive model of internet banking acceptance was developed based on existing literature. TAM was used as a basis for designing the conceptual model for this study However, additional variables such as trust, perceived risk and user's demographic characteristics (gender, age and education level) were integrated into the original TAM model.

The empirical result from the analysis shows that (1) perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust and perceived risk are direct antecedents of customers' intention; (2) customers' perception of privacy and security directly affects their level of trust on internet banking. (3) trust is also an indirect antecedent of intention, meaning high level of trust reduces user's perception of risk and act as a key component in customer's adoption of internet banking. (4) Among the barriers, customers' perception regarding privacy and security and the risk of losing personal and financial data are the main inhibiting factors of internet banking adoption in the UK. (5) Regarding the role of demographics, customers' age was found effect on their choice of internet banking.

However, gender and level of education were not influential factors of internet banking acceptance.

The present study suggested that although TAM is a powerful and usefulness model in explaining user behaviour towards acceptance of technology, the inclusion of new variables related to environmental uncertainty (perceived risk and trust) and moderators (gender, age and education level) provides a much deeper insight into understanding the underlying phenomenon. By integrating these new constructs with the original TAM model the researcher was able to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the factors influencing internet banking adoption and usage in the new era.

To conclude, user acceptance of internet banking remains a vast and complex issue. Over the last three decades, researchers have made significant contributions towards this topic. The proposed model of this study also adds to the body of knowledge in this area. However, many more explanatory studies need to be conducted for better explanation and understanding of the key factors that influence the usage of internet banking across the globe.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Introductory Cover letter of the Questionnaire

Internet Banking Perception Survey

Dear Respondent,

I am a full-time doctoral student at the University of the West of Scotland, London campus, and my research seeks to investigate the drivers and barriers towards the use of internet banking in the UK. As a part of this research, I would like to invite you to participate in this questionnaire survey, which aims to collect information relating to your perceptions and opinions on internet banking and other related issues. It is highly anticipated that the analysis of this questionnaire will contribute significantly to my research.

It is estimated that this questionnaire will take no longer than 12 minutes to complete. Instructions on how to complete this questionnaire are provided in each section. Some of the questions may seem repetitive, however, please respond to all questions as instructed. Your participation will be most helpful in completing my research.

All the information you provide will be treated with confidentiality, and your anonymity will be protected. This information will be used only for academic purposes, and no individual responses will be identified.

Should you have any questions about my research or this survey, please contact me at my mailing address given at the end of this questionnaire. Thank you very much for your participation.

Your sincerely

Ajmal Mohammad Yosaf

Appendix 2: Questionnaire Survey

Drivers and Barriers Towards the Acceptance of Internet Banking in the UK

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WEST of SCOTLAND

Dear Respondent,

In this questionnaire, the term **internet banking** refers to the situation when customers use internet to manage and conduct their daily banking activities.

It is estimated that this questionnaire will take no longer than 10 minutes. All the answers will be treated confidential and anonymous. Please circle the appropriate number to indicate your level of agreement and disagreement with the statements.

Part 1: Attitude Towards Internet Banking

I use the following for my banking transactions (Please circle all that applies)	Daily	Few times a week	Once a week	Once a month	Once a year	never
Branch Banking						
Telephone Banking						
Cash Machine						
Internet Banking						

Question 1. Please circle one number to indicate your level of agreement with each of the following statements.

<u>Q1A: Perceived Usefulness</u>	Strongly Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
I believe that			
Internet banking is very useful in helping me conduct my banking transactions.	1	2	3
Internet banking offers 24/7 services which are very important.	1	2	3
Internet banking offers me great benefits as compared to branch banking.	1	2	3
<u>Q1B: Perceived Ease of Use</u>	Strongly Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
I believe that			
Internet banking is very easy to use.	1	2	3
Internet banking websites have clear and understandable procedures.	1	2	3
Conducting banking transactions over the internet does not need a lot of effort.	1	2	3
<u>Q1C: Perceived Trust</u>	Strongly Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree
I believe that			
Trust plays a key role in the acceptance and adoption of online banking.	1	2	3
My bank must have the required protection and safeguard mechanisms in place to protect me against online fraud.	1	2	3

My bank's website must have a privacy statement that guarantee the privacy of my personal data.	1	2	3	4	5
High level of perceived trustworthiness of my bank will positively influence my willingness to trust online banking.	1	2	3	4	5
Q1D: Perceived Risk I believe that.....	A Significant Risk		Neutral		Significant Opportunity
The decision towards the use of internet banking to conduct banking transaction is	1	2	3	4	5
I would rate my overall perception of the risk associated with online banking as:	1	2	3	4	5
Q1E: Perceived Risk	Very likely To occur		Neutral		Very Unlikely to occur
I would rate the risk of financial loss and personal data loss associated with internet banking as:	1	2	3	4	5
Q1F: Perceived Privacy I believe that my bank should.....	Strongly Disagree		Neutral		Strongly Agree
Confirm my identity before accessing my account information.	1	2	3	4	5
Does not allow unauthorised access to my bank account.	1	2	3	4	5
Q1G: Perceived Security I believe that my bank should.....	Strongly Disagree		Neutral		Strongly Agree
Provide 24-hour secure access to online banking.	1	2	3	4	5
Have the latest security mechanisms and firewall in place to protect its customers against online fraud.	1	2	3	4	5
Have consistent online policies and practices.	1	2	3	4	5

Question 2. Below are some of the reasons which inhibit the usage of internet banking. Please circle one number to show your level of agreement with the following statements.

	Reasons for Non-Adoption of Internet Banking	
1	Prefer other medium of services such as branch banking and telephone banking	
2	Concern about privacy and security	
3	Risk of losing my personal and financial data	
4	Do not trust internet banking medium	
5	Benefits of internet are not clear to me	
6	Internet banking services are very complex to understand and difficult to use	
7	Lack of information and fear of change	
8	Lack of face to face advise	

Q3. Below are the factors that positively affect your decision to adopt and use internet banking services. Please circle one number to show your level of agreement with the following statements:

Factors for Adoption of Internet Banking		
1	Internet banking is fast and efficient	
2	24/7 availability of banking services	
3	Greater control over my banking activities	
4	Convenience and efficiency	
5	Saves time and cost	
6	Mobility and accessibility	
7	Perceived usefulness	
8	Better information	
9	Better communication	
10	Variety of features and services that are offered	

Part 2: Your General Perception about Internet Banking

1, Overall, how satisfied are you with online banking service?

- Very Satisfied Neutral
 Satisfied Unsatisfied

2, How likely you intend to use online banking in the next twelve months?

- Very Likely Neutral
 Likely Very Unlikely

3, Do you trust the security of online banking?

- Completely Dubious
 Somewhat Not at all

5, Do you think human contact is important for good banking relation?

- Completely Unsure
 Somewhat Not at all

6, What are for you the 2 main disadvantages of online banking?

- Difficulty of using the service Unreliable
 Lack of assistance Dependence on internet service
 Limited Service Other (Please Specify)
 Security Concerns

7, Do you think banks should invest more in promoting their online banking services to encourage customers to use them?

- Yes I do not know
 No

8, What do you think banks should do to encourage people to use online banking services in the UK? (Please tick all that apply)

- Increase security measures on their websites
- Educate customers on the benefits of online banking
- Improve response time to online customer queries
- Provide services free from technical problems
- Improve download speed from the host bank server
- Other: _____

9, Do you think internet banking will replace traditional banking methods?

- Yes No

Part 3: About Yourself

Please answer the following questions about yourself. Please tick at the appropriate box.

1. How long have you used internet banking?

- Less than a year Two years or more
 1-2 years Never

3, Which banking services do you always use through internet banking? (Please tick all that apply)

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Basic account information | <input type="checkbox"/> International Payments |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Inter-account transfers | <input type="checkbox"/> Apply for overdraft |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Make online bill payments | <input type="checkbox"/> Manage direct debits |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Make online transfers | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |

4, The largest amount I have transferred using internet banking is.

- Under £50 £ 500 - £1,000
 £50 - £500 Over £1,000

5, What is your gender?

- Male Female

6, What is your age?

- Under 18 46 - 60
 18 - 24 60 years or above
 25 - 45

7, What is your highest educational level?

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> No Formal Education | <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor Degree |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Secondary School | <input type="checkbox"/> Master and Above |

College

8, What is your employment status?

- Part-time Retired
 Full-time Other/Prefer not to say
 Unemployed

9, Where do you mainly access online banking from?

- Personal Computer Mobile
 Tablet

Are there any other comments that will help us better understand customer behaviour towards the acceptance of internet banking? If so, please use the below box to provide your suggestions.

THE END OF SURVEY

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME AND VALUABLE CONTRIBUTION TO THIS STUDY

Should you have any questions about this survey or my research, please contact us on the following address:

University of the West of Scotland
235 Southwark Bridge Road
London

Email

Appendix 3: Interviews with Bank Managers

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS FOR BANK MANAGERS

Q1: Do you think that the usefulness of internet banking services influence customers' intention towards using it?

Q2: As a bank manager, to what extent do you think the ease of use of internet banking affect customers' intention towards using this service?

Q3: Does online trust play an important role in affecting customers' intention to accept and use internet banking?

Q4: Does privacy and security concerns play a role in customers' decision to accept internet banking? Are there any measures taken by your bank to activate and increase the internet banking security and privacy?

Q5: From your point of view, who are more willing to use online banking service according to the following categories:

- Age (Younger/Older)
- Gender (Male/Female)
- Education Level (Low Level/High Level)

Q6: In your opinion, what do you think are the major inhibiting factors that prevent customers from using internet banking service?

Q7: What do you think banks should do to ensure customers use internet banking in an environment that is free from all the risks?

Thank you very much for your time and co-operation

Appendix 4: SPSS Output Tables

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	147	53.5	53.5	53.5
	Female	128	46.5	46.5	100.0
	Total	275	100.0	100.0	

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	55	20.0	20.0	20.0
	26-35	92	33.5	33.5	53.5
	36-45	59	21.5	21.5	74.9
	46-59	48	17.5	17.5	92.4
	60 Years or above	21	7.6	7.6	100.0
	Total	275	100.0	100.0	

Employment Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	101	36.7	36.7	36.7
	Employee	48	17.5	17.5	54.2
	Professional	86	31.3	31.3	85.5
	Self-Employed	24	8.7	8.7	94.2
	Retired	8	2.9	2.9	97.1
	Unemployed	8	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	275	100.0	100.0	

Education Level

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Secondary School	15	5.5	5.5	5.8
	College	55	20.0	20.0	25.8
	Bachelor's Degree	133	48.4	48.4	74.2
	Master and Above	71	25.8	25.8	100.0
	Total	275	100.0	100.0	

Internet Banking Usage

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	10	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Once a Week	56	20.4	20.4	24.0
	Biweekly	20	7.3	7.3	31.3
	Three Times a Week	29	10.5	10.5	41.8
	Everyday	160	58.2	58.2	100.0
	Total	275	100.0	100.0	

Frequency of Usage

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	10	3.6	3.6	3.6
	Once a Week	56	20.4	20.4	24.0
	Biweekly	20	7.3	7.3	31.3
	Three Times a Week	29	10.5	10.5	41.8
	Everyday	160	58.2	58.2	100.0
	Total	275	100.0	100.0	

Larger Amount Transferred

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Under £50	50	18.2	18.2	18.2
	£50 -£500	30	10.9	10.9	29.1
	£500-£1,000	58	21.1	21.1	50.2
	Over £1,000	137	49.8	49.8	100.0
	Total	275	100.0	100.0	

Respondents' Refusing to Use Internet Banking

		Responses		Percent of Cases
		N	Percent	
\$Negative	Prefer other medium of services	86	10.1%	31.4%
	Concerned about privacy and security	217	25.4%	79.2%
	Risk of losing my personal and financial data	210	24.6%	76.6%
	Do not trust the internet banking medium	147	17.2%	53.6%
	Internet banking services are very complex to understand and difficult to use	70	8.2%	25.5%
	Dependence on internet service	27	3.2%	9.9%
	Lack of face to face advise	96	11.3%	35.0%
Total	853	100.0%	311.3%	

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Respondents' Acceptance of Internet Banking

		Responses		Percent of Cases
		N	Percent	
\$Positive	Internet banking is fast and efficient	198	16.4%	74.4%
	24/7 availability of banking services	203	16.8%	76.3%
	Greater control over my banking activities	124	10.2%	46.6%
	Convenience and efficiency	222	18.3%	83.5%
	Saves time and cost	96	7.9%	36.1%
	Mobility and accessibility	100	8.3%	37.6%
	Perceived usefulness	207	17.1%	77.8%
	Better Communication	60	5.0%	22.6%
Total		1210	100.0%	454.9%

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Kruskal Wallis Analysis by Age

Ranks

	Age	N	Mean Rank
I Intend to Use Internet Banking in the Future	18-25	55	169.43
	26-35	92	167.02
	36-45	59	158.58
	46-59	48	60.81
	60 Years or above	21	47.17
	Total		275
Internet Banking is Very Useful in Helping me Conduct my Banking Transactions	18-25	55	169.55
	26-35	92	164.38
	36-45	59	155.19
	46-59	48	68.19

	60 Years or above	21	51.07
	Total	275	
I find Internet Banking very easy to use	18-25	55	166.92
	26-35	92	171.41
	36-45	59	151.76
	46-59	48	61.78
	60 Years or above	21	51.45
	Total	275	
I trust my bank as a reliable service provider	18-25	55	156.20
	26-35	92	158.52
	36-45	59	152.25
	46-59	48	84.46
	60 Years or above	21	82.79
	Total	275	
I believe that my personal information on internet banking will be kept confidential.	18-25	55	156.75
	26-35	91	158.60
	36-45	59	149.74
	46-59	47	78.40
	60 Years or above	21	87.00
	Total	273	
I believe my bank provides 24 hours secure access to online banking.	18-25	55	163.65
	26-35	92	160.86
	36-45	59	161.89
	46-59	48	75.55
	60 Years or above	21	46.31
	Total	275	
The decision towards the use of internet banking to conduct banking transaction is	18-25	55	108.01
	26-35	92	116.99
	36-45	59	118.62
	46-59	48	207.93
	60 Years or above	21	203.21
	Total	275	

Test Statistics							
	Behavioral Intention	Perceived Usefulness	Perceived Ease of Use	Perceived Trust	Perceived Privacy	Perceived Security	Perceived Risk
Kruskal-Wallis H	124.563	94.698	104.609	47.415	65.312	83.695	78.097
df	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Age

Kruskal Wallis Analysis by Education Level

Ranks			
	What is Your Education Level	N	Mean Rank
	I Intend to Use Internet Banking in the Future	Secondary School	15
College		55	138.40
Bachelor's Degree		133	129.08
Master and Above		71	144.54
Total		274	
Internet Banking is Very Useful in Helping me Conduct my Banking Transactions	Secondary School	15	180.97
	College	55	139.06
	Bachelor's degree	133	131.24
	Master and Above	71	138.82
	Total	274	
I find Internet Banking very easy to use	Secondary School	15	166.70
	College	55	136.46
	Bachelor's degree	133	131.47
	Master and Above	71	143.42
	Total	274	

Test Statistics^{a,b}			
	Behavioral Intention	Perceived Usefulness	Perceived Ease of Use
Kruskal-Wallis H	7.087	6.090	3.562
df	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.069	.107	.313

- a. Kruskal Wallis Test
- b. Grouping Variable: What is Your Education Level

Mann-Whitney U Test for Gender of Respondents

Ranks				
	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Overall Intention	Male	146	132.90	19403.00
	Female	128	142.75	18272.00
	Total	274		
COMPOSITE PU	Male	147	137.61	20228.50
	Female	128	138.45	17721.50
	Total	275		
COMPOSITE_PEU	Male	147	137.11	20154.50
	Female	128	139.03	17795.50
	Total	275		

Test Statistics^a			
	Overall Intention	COMPOSITE PU	COMPOSITE_PEU
Mann-Whitney U	8672.000	9350.500	9276.500
Wilcoxon W	19403.000	20228.500	20154.500
Z	-1.056	-.088	-.203
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.291	.930	.839

- a. Grouping Variable: Gender